

Photometry and Blends – The Rubin Photo-z Challenges

A Dissertation Presented

by

Shuang Liang

to

The Graduate School

in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

for the Degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

in

Physics

Stony Brook University

May 2022

Stony Brook University

The Graduate School

Shuang Liang

We, the dissertation committee for the above candidate for the Doctor of Philosophy degree, hereby recommend acceptance of this dissertation.

Anja von der Linden – Dissertation Advisor
Assistant Professor, Department of Physics and Astronomy

Will M. Farr – Chairperson of Defense
Associate Professor, Department of Physics and Astronomy
Center for Computational Astrophysics, Flatiron Institute

Matthew Dawber
Associate Professor, Department of Physics and Astronomy

Robyn E. Sanderson
Assistant Professor
Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Pennsylvania
Center for Computational Astrophysics, Flatiron Institute

This dissertation is accepted by the Graduate School.

Eric Wertheimer
Dean of the Graduate School

Abstract of the Dissertation

Photometry and Blends – The Rubin Photo-z Challenges

by

Shuang Liang

Doctor of Philosophy

in

Physics

Stony Brook University

2022

Weak Gravitational Lensing is a powerful probe for cosmology, and is one of the main goals for the Vera C. Rubin Observatory’s Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST). LSST will observe $\sim 10^{10}$ galaxies and measure their redshifts with broad-band photometry (photometric redshift; photo-z). This dissertation consists of three projects dedicated to improve LSST systematic uncertainties including photo-z measurements:

1. improve photometric calibration of u -band imaging;
2. identify overlapping galaxies (blends) with machine learning;
3. quantify the impact of blends in galaxy clusters on photo-z.

Motivated by the photo-z challenges of Rubin-LSST, this work also has applications beyond photo-z or Rubin (e.g. cluster cosmology, galaxy shape measurements, Milky Way structure, or any optical observation with deep u -band imaging).

Contents

Acknowledgements	vi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Modern view of the Universe	1
1.2 Gravitational Lensing and Photo-z	4
1.3 This Thesis	7
1.3.1 Photometry in u -band	8
1.3.2 Galaxy Blends	9
1.3.3 Blends in Galaxy Cluster Fields	10
2 Photometric Calibration in u-band	12
2.1 Abstract	12
2.2 Introduction	13
2.3 Data Description	15
2.3.1 SDSS data	16
2.3.2 KiDS data	16
2.3.3 ATLAS data	18
2.3.4 NSC data	18
2.3.5 PanSTARRS data	19
2.3.6 ATLAS-RefCat2 data	19
2.3.7 Catalog Cross-Matching	19
2.3.8 Color Equations	20
2.4 Method Construction	21
2.4.1 Detecting the “Blue Tip”	23
2.4.2 Disk Contamination Model	26
2.5 Re-calibration of the Validation Sets	30
2.5.1 The g -band calibration	30
2.5.2 The u -band calibration	33
2.6 Summary and Discussion	35

3	Color-based Galaxy Blends detection	38
3.1	Abstract	38
3.2	Introduction	38
3.3	Data Description	40
3.3.1	The COSMOS Data Set	40
3.3.2	The HST Data Set	41
3.3.3	Spectroscopy Data Sets	42
3.3.4	Catalog Matching	44
3.4	Methods	47
3.4.1	The SOM Configurations	47
3.4.2	Identification of Blends with SOM	48
3.5	Results	50
3.5.1	The Removed Sample	51
3.5.2	The Rest Sample	54
3.6	Summary And Discussion	54
4	Cluster Blends on Photo-z	57
4.1	Introduction	57
4.2	Quick Example	58
4.3	Future Plans	59
5	Summary and Future Plans	62
5.1	Project 1: <i>u</i> -band photometry	62
5.2	Project 2 and 3: Galaxy Blends	63
	Bibliography	65
.1	Detailed Data Acquirement	84
.1.1	SDSS data	84
.1.2	KiDS data	86
.1.3	ATLAS data	87
.1.4	NSC data	88
.1.5	PanSTARRS data	89
.1.6	ATLAS-Refcat2 data	90
.1.7	SHELA data	91
.2	Color Equations from Photometry	91
.3	Color Equations from Synthetic Magnitudes	95
.4	Gaia parallax and proper motion	97
.5	Calculating the Luptitudes	99
.6	Jupyter Notebook: Quick Example	100
.7	Jupyter Notebook: Ellipse Matching	117

Acknowledgements

I'd like to thank my advisor Prof. Anja von der Linden for for her support, patience and encouragement during my Ph.D. career. Many thanks also go to Dr. Ricardo Herbonnet, Dr. Tae-hyeon Shin, Dr. Lucie Baumont, Dr. Eli Rykoff, Dr. Robert Lupton, Dr. Remy Joseph, Prof. Will Farr, Prof. Robyn Sanderson, Prof. Patricia Burchat, Prof. Camille Avestruz and Dr. Alex Malz for illuminating discussion on my projects. Special thanks to Radhakrishnan Srinivasan and Hsin Fan for sticking to my reading club – it has been a lot of fun.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Modern view of the Universe

Modern cosmology began when Einstein's theory of General Relativity (GR) was applied to the whole universe. Under the assumption of a homogeneous and isotropic universe, Alexander Friedmann first derived the solution to the universe in 1922 [1], known today as the Friedmann – Lemaître – Robertson – Walker (FLRW) metric. However, unlike other applications of GR where it is almost always successful, cosmology has been continuously challenged starting from its birth in 1922 and all the way through today. Some of the greatest challenges led to the introduction of extra “dark components” of our universe, whose essences are to this date still mysterious to us.

In as early as 1937, Fritz Zwicky already noticed that galaxies in the Coma Cluster were moving too fast to be explained by the stellar material in the cluster. He postulated that additional mass in the form of some “dark matter” must be providing the extra gravity [2]. Later in 1980, Vera C. Rubin found that the normal stellar mass in galaxies, traced by visible light, cannot provide enough gravitational pull to sustain the observed high stellar velocities [3]. *Gravitational lensing* provides another strong support for extra matter around galaxies: in 1979, Walsh et al. [4] discovered a pair of quasars which turned out to be a single object being imaged twice, due to a galaxy in the line-of-sight to the Earth. Matter in the galaxy distorts space-time around it, causing the nearby passing light rays to be deflected as if crossing a lens. Many more lensing systems have been found today in galaxies and galaxy clusters (and on smaller scales too). However, generally, the amount of stellar material is not enough to cause the amount of space-time distortion observed. More evidence for the existence of dark matter include galaxy rotation curves [5, 6], cluster lensing (off-)center [7, 8], etc. On a larger scale, dark matter is also deeply

involved in the evolution of our universe. The Big Bang Nucleosynthesis (BBN) predicts 25% Helium-4, 10^{-5} Deuterium, and 10^{-10} Lithium-7 abundance by mass. These predictions exactly match the observations as long as atoms are only 5% of the total components of the universe. The strongest evidence for dark matter so far comes from the Cosmic Microwave Background [CMB; 9] which measures the temperature fluctuation at redshift of ~ 1100 , where baryonic matter alone could not have caused enough fluctuation as observed.

Dark Energy is another extra component needed to explain our universe. Back in the 1920s, with improved instruments, luminous nebulae were observed in the night skies, which were soon proved to be extragalactic galaxies [10]. Later in 1929, Hubble [11] showed that these galaxies are moving away from us at a constant speed H_0 , the *Hubble constant*. In the next decades, when improved techniques allowed further measurements, we find that galaxies are receding at a speed proportional to their distances, known as the Hubble's Law. The Hubble's Law can be explained well with the expansion of the universe described by the FLRW metric. However, in 1998 and 1999, when distance measurements based on supernovae were pushed even further, the expansion of universe was found to be accelerating [12, 13]. It was a surprising discovery, as the matter content of the universe known to us (baryonic matter and dark matter) could only slow down the expansion. Therefore, a constant Λ , invented by Einstein to sustain a static universe as what he believed, was picked up again to drive the acceleration. Today, we associate Λ with a mysterious *Dark Energy*, whose pressure is negative, equation of state is -1, and energy density remains constant as the universe expands.

Combining General Relativity with *Dark Matter* and *Dark Energy*, we reach the Λ CDM model, the standard model for cosmology today. Despite the puzzles on the origin of the dark components, Λ CDM has been very successful in explaining our universe. It predicts and explains well the elemental abundances and acceleration of expansion mentioned above, the anisotropic structures in the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB), and the large-scale structure in the distribution of galaxies. However, over the years, more observations/simulations of our universe have been made that challenge the validity of Λ CDM, to the point that some cosmologists now believe that alternative theories should be considered. The major challenges come from the Hubble tension [14] and the S_8 tension [15], elaborated in the following paragraph. Other (arguable) challenges include but not limited to: the cusp-core problem [16, 17], the missing satellite galaxies problem [18] and the planes of satellite problem [19], etc.

The Hubble tension and the S_8 tension are the major challenges to the Λ CDM model, and they are shown in Fig. 1.1. The upper panel of Fig. 1.1

Figure 1.1: The Hubble tension [21] and the S_8 tension [22].

shows the *Hubble constant* measured locally from supernovae or derived from early-universe measurements (from CMB [9]). Supernovae measurements yield great precision in relative distance per se, but in order to constrain H_0 , their “zero point” needs to be calibrated with nearby sources (lower “rungs” of the distance ladder). The blue points in Fig. 1.1 show the supernovae measurements anchored by Cepheids [20], and the red points are anchored by tip of the red giant branch [TRGB; 21]. A clear discrepancy is seen between the local and early-universe measurements, indicating an issue with the Λ CDM model which bridges the two. It is worth noting that in 2021, the discrepancy in H_0 between the Cepheids and the CMB has exceeded 5σ [20]. The lower panel of Fig. 1.1 shows a similar comparison for $S_8 = \sigma_8 \sqrt{\Omega_m/0.3}$, a parameter sensi-

tive to the large scale structure probed by various surveys. S_8 is made up of Ω_m , the fraction of the matter components in the universe, and σ_8 , the spatial fluctuation of matter filtered with 8 Mpc windows. When comparing measurements of S_8 from local observations [22] to the derived value from CMB [The *Planck* Results; 9], disagreement again rises.

Alternative theories have been proposed to address the challenges. They typically fall into two categories: Dynamical dark energy, where the dark energy is no longer a constant but evolves with an equation of state ω and its derivative ω' ; Modified gravity, where Einstein's theory of relativity breaks down at low densities/large scales. The two kinds of theories can predict the same expansion history of the universe, but different growth rate of inhomogeneity structures [23]. Therefore, probes for structure growth are essential tools to distinguish between the two alternative theories.

1.2 Gravitational Lensing and Photo-z

Gravitational Lensing is a very powerful probe of structure growth in our universe. The discrepancy in S_8 between measurements from lensing surveys and the derived value from early-universe observations is one of the major challenges to Λ CDM. Moreover, future galaxy lensing surveys (e.g. Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time [LSST; 24]) have strong potential to constrain the evolution of *Dark Energy*, providing one step forward to understanding its nature.

Fig. 1.2 shows a typical lensing system, where a source at a distance D_s and position β is lensed by an object at distance D_d and appears to be at direction θ . For a source whose size is small comparing to θ , we can write down the response matrix \mathbf{A} at the first order:

$$\mathbf{A} = \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial \theta} = \delta_{ij} - \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \phi_i \partial \phi_j} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \kappa - \gamma_1 & -\gamma_2 \\ -\gamma_2 & 1 - \kappa + \gamma_1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.1)$$

Here, ϕ , κ and γ are the *lensing potential*, the *convergence* and the *shear* of the lens, defined as

$$\nabla^2 \phi(\theta) = \Sigma(\xi) / \Sigma_{\text{crit}} \quad (1.2)$$

and

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \phi(\theta) \quad (1.3)$$

and

$$\gamma = \gamma_1 + i\gamma_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta_1^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta_2^2} \right) + i \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta_1 \partial \theta_2}, \quad (1.4)$$

Figure 1.2: Sketch of a typical gravitational lens system [25].

Figure 1.3: Demonstration of galaxies being lensed.

where $\Sigma(\xi)$ is the surface mass density of the lens, and Σ_{crit} is a geometrical factor

$$\Sigma_{\text{crit}} = \frac{c^2}{4\pi G} \frac{D_s}{D_{\text{ds}} D_d}. \quad (1.5)$$

For extended sources such as galaxies, gravitational lensing alters their sizes and shapes. Fig. 1.3 illustrates this lensing distortion of galaxies. In practice, the distortion of shapes (the gravitational shear) is not directly obtainable, since when a galaxy is lensed, we have no means of knowing its true shape. However, when millions of galaxy shapes are measured, a correlation analysis allows us to extract information about the large structure matter distribution. This is usually achieved with a tomographic analysis, where galaxies are binned by their redshifts into lens bins and source bins, and correlations between their shapes and positions are calculated. It is worth emphasizing that gravitational lensing requires two key measurements: shape of galaxies and their redshifts. Shapes are needed to measure their shear, and redshifts are needed to make tomographic bins.

Such gravitational lensing experiments are powerful tools for cosmology, which is reflected in the number of lensing surveys: The Kilo Degree Survey [KiDS; 26], the Dark Energy Survey [DES; 27], the Hyper Suprime Cam survey [HSC; 28], and the planned *Euclid* satellite mission [29], the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope [30], and the Rubin-LSST [24] mentioned above. It is worth noting that such measurements are extremely difficult, as shown in Fig. 1.4. From left to right, galaxies with unknown intrinsic shapes are lensed

Figure 1.4: Demonstration of shape measurements for lensing surveys [31].

by an object whose mass we aim to infer. The shape then gets blurred as the light rays go through the atmosphere and the telescope optics, equivalent of being convolved with a point-spread function (PSF). Next, the shape gets pixelized on the telescope detector which also reads in various noise: environmental reflection, sky background/emission, Poisson noise due to finite amount of photons hitting the detector, and electronic reading noise. In the end, we observe panel 5 in Fig. 1.4, and aim to infer the difference between panel 1 and 2.

With the difficulties of shape measurements in mind, it is easy to understand that lensing surveys require a large number of measurements (typically $10^8 \sim 10^{10}$) to beat down the noise. Immediately, this imposes a challenge on the other side of the measurements: the redshift of galaxies. Due to the sheer number of sources required, it is impossible to perform spectroscopy on each of them, and we are left with photometric-redshifts (photo-z) – redshift estimates with only several broad-band photometry. Fig. 1.5 illustrates the estimation of redshifts from 5-band photometry. Photo-z is itself also a difficult task, yet it is very important to weak lensing measurements. [32] show that 2% wrong spectroscopic redshifts (used for photo-z training) can cause 15% error in ω for DES. [33] also show that only the modification of photo-z can ease the S_8 tension between Planck and KiDS/DES.

1.3 This Thesis

This dissertation consists of three projects dedicated to improve photo-z measurements:

1. improve photometric calibration of the u -band imaging using blue halo stars;
2. identify unrecognized galaxy blends with machine learning;

Figure 1.5: Illustration of photometric redshift measurement [34].

3. quantify the impact of blends in galaxy clusters on photo-z.

A brief introduction for the three projects are in the following sections.

1.3.1 Photometry in u -band

Photometry is the procedure of measuring the brightness of celestial objects. In optical astronomy, the brightness is often expressed in magnitude

$$m = -2.5 \log \frac{F}{F_0}, \quad (1.6)$$

where F is the flux density of an object and F_0 is a reference flux density. If an object emits a flux density $F = F_0$, its magnitude is 0, thus F_0 is also referred to as the zero-point flux. We can write equation (1.6) as

$$m = -2.5 \log F + m_0 \quad (1.7)$$

with $m_0 = 2.5 \log F_0$ the zero-point of magnitude. Calibration of the zero-point lies in the core of photometry. Thanks to the linear response of modern astronomical detectors (usually Charge-Coupled Device, CCD), calibration of zero-point for an instrument is the same as measuring the instrumental magnitude of an imaginary source with flux density F_0 .

In modern astronomy, the most common magnitude system is the “AB

magnitude”, where the imaginary source has a flat spectrum with $F_0 = 3631$ Jy (Oke and Gunn [35]), with $1 \text{ Jy} = 10^{-26} \text{ W Hz}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$, or, in the cgs units, $1 \text{ Jy} = 10^{-23} \text{ ergs s}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Therefore, in the cgs units, the AB magnitude is defined as

$$m = -2.5 \log F - 48.60. \quad (1.8)$$

In practice, the measured flux is always integrated over some range of wavelengths through the filter transmission and CCD response, so the definition of AB magnitude becomes

$$m = -2.5 \log \frac{\int d \log(\nu) F_\nu S_\nu}{\int d \log(\nu) S_\nu} - 48.60, \quad (1.9)$$

where S_ν is the total response of the instrument (atmosphere + system throughput). The $\log(\nu)$ term is present because CCDs are essentially photon counting devices.

Out of all the optical bands, the near-ultraviolet band – usually the u -band – is notoriously difficult to calibrate due to the steep cut-off in atmospheric transparency. Yet the u -band photometry is a key measurement to photometric redshift estimates, as it is able to break low- vs. high-redshift degeneracies [36]. The goal for Rubin-LSST photometric calibration is 15 mmag in the *grizy*-bands, while the u -band may be worse but with less than a factor of 2 (table 15 of LPM-17¹). Chapter 2 of this thesis describes a new approach for the photometric calibration of u -band imaging using blue galactic halo stars. This approach meets the Rubin photometric requirement. This work has been submitted to the MNRAS for peer review.

1.3.2 Galaxy Blends

With improved instruments and technology, astronomical surveys reach deeper observation depth. Current lensing surveys (e.g. KiDS, DES and HSC) have a typical survey depth of $r \sim 25(5\sigma)$, $23.6(10\sigma)$, and $26(5\sigma)$ respectively while the Rubin-LSST stretches for $r \sim 27.5(5\sigma)$ in 10 years of observation. A deeper exposure means that the image of a certain size will include more objects. When the source number densities increase rapidly, there is also a greater chance of them overlapping in projection, causing a “blend”. The impact of blending is a key difficulty in large scale surveys like LSST, as it affects both of the essential measurements for gravitational lensing: shape and redshift. Of particular concerns are the “unrecognized blends”, where a source detected as a single object is in fact composed of multiple objects. Fig. 1.6 shows

¹<https://docushare.lsst.org/docushare/dsweb/Get/LPM-17>

Figure 1.6: Illustration of galaxy blends [37].

such an example on a simulated image. The left panel shows the detection pipeline recognizing one source marked in red, while the truth objects are plotted in blue. The right panel shows the spectral energy distribution (SED) of a blended source (shown in green), as a combination of a reddened spiray galaxy (shown in red) and a blue galaxy (shown in blue). The truth galaxies both have redshift of ~ 0.5 , while the best-fit template of the blended SED yields a $z = 0.995$ estimate.

Chapter 3 of this thesis presents a method to detect unrecognized blends using only broad-band magnitudes. Under the assumption that the blended galaxies have unique colors, a machine learning algorithm called the Self Organizing Map (SOM) is used to identify the unrecognized blends. This work is close to submission.

1.3.3 Blends in Galaxy Cluster Fields

Galaxy clusters are the largest gravity-bound objects in the universe. A typical galaxy cluster contains hundreds to thousands of galaxies and has a mass range of $10^{14} - 10^{15}$ solar masses. As the formation of clusters are deeply entangled with the cosmological environment, the abundance of galaxy clusters is a promising probe to the background cosmology [38]. Comparing to X-ray or radio observations that are affected by the baryonic physics in clusters, gravitational lensing probes directly the total mass of clusters and is the least biased approach for the mass estimate [38]. However, due to the increased number density in crowded cluster fields, the impact of blending is more serious than field galaxies. Chapter 4 presents a project to study the impact of blends on photo- z in cluster fields. The end product of this project is a series of jupyter

notebooks to address this issue to the Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC) of Rubin-LSST, and will be published as a DESC note. As the project is still on-going, some notebooks showing the preliminary results are shown in Chapter 4.

Chapter 2

Photometric Calibration in u -band

This chapter describes a project to calibrate u -band photometry with blue halo stars. This work has been submitted to the *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* (MNRAS¹) for peer review and publication.

2.1 Abstract

We present a new approach for the photometric calibration of u -band imaging using blue galactic halo stars. The galactic halo stars belong to an old stellar population of the Milky Way and have relatively low metallicity. The “blue tip” of the halo population — the main sequence turn-off (MSTO) stars — is known to have a relatively uniform intrinsic edge $u-g$ color with only slow spatial variation. In SDSS data, the observed variation is correlated with galactic latitude, which we attribute to contamination by higher-metallicity disk stars and fit with an empirical curve. This curve can then be used to calibrate u -band imaging if g -band imaging of matching depth is available. Our approach can be applied to single-field observations at $|b| > 30^\circ$, and removes the need for standard star observations or overlap with calibrated u -band imaging. We include in our method the calibration of g -band data with ATLAS-Refcat2. We test our approach on stars in KiDS DR 4, ATLAS DR 4, and DECam imaging from the NOIRLab Source Catalog (NSC DR2), and compare our calibration with SDSS. We find an improvement for all, reaching a zero-point precision of 0.016 mag for KiDS (compared to the original 0.033 mag), 0.020 mag for ATLAS (originally 0.027 mag), and 0.016 mag for DECam (originally 0.041 mag). Thus, this method alone reaches the goal of 0.02 mag photometric precision in u -band for the Rubin Observatory’s Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST).

¹<https://academic.oup.com/mnras>

2.2 Introduction

The near-ultraviolet wavelength regime accessible from the ground - in current facilities typically the u -band² - carries important astrophysical information, but is notoriously difficult to calibrate due to the steep cut-off in atmospheric transparency. For example, u -band observations are important to the study of stellar metallicity and stellar formation/evolution [39, 40], variable stars [41, 42], galactic archaeology [43], and composition of asteroids [44]. The u -band measurement also benefits photometric redshift estimates by being able to break low- vs. high-redshift degeneracies [36], thus is important for cosmological imaging surveys such as the upcoming Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) to be conducted at the Vera C. Rubin Observatory. With great care, u -band photometric zero-points of large contiguous sky areas can be calibrated to roughly half the precision of optical bands; the Sloan Digital Sky Survey [SDSS; 45, 46] reached 13 mmag in u -band compared to 8, 8, and 7 mmag in the gri -bands [47, 48]. The goal for Rubin-LSST is 15 mmag in the $grizy$ -bands, while the u -band may be worse but with less than a factor of 2 (table 15 of LPM-17³).

u -band calibration of pointed single-field observations with no overlapping calibrated survey data is even more difficult. While in the northern extragalactic sky, u -band images can be calibrated by comparing with SDSS, the current southern sky surveys lack in depth and precision. SkyMapper⁴ covers much of the Southern sky but is comparatively shallow. Moreover, its u -band is notably different from the other u -bands discussed here, resulting in large color terms relative to other filter sets, and accordingly large zero-point scatter when comparing to other observations [49]. The ATLAS survey [50] reaches 22.0 magnitude at 5σ in the u -band with a zeropoint precision of 0.035 mag, but only covers about 4000 deg² (DR4). The Kilo-Degree Survey⁵ [KiDS; 51] has a 5σ limiting magnitude as deep as 24.2 in the u -band with 0.035 mag zero-point precision but covers only ~ 1000 deg² as of DR4.

When no calibrated reference stars are available in the field of view (or those stars saturate), the u -band calibration becomes very challenging. Typically, exposures of other fields containing calibrated standard stars are required for the calibration, with the assumption that the atmospheric conditions do not vary between the fields of interest and the standard star fields. As the u -band

²In this introduction, we will use the term u -band generically; our analysis uses specific u -band filters, but can be easily adapted to other filters limited by the atmosphere in the NUV.

³<https://docushare.lsst.org/docushare/dsweb/Get/LPM-17>

⁴<http://skymapper.anu.edu.au/>

⁵<http://kids.strw.leidenuniv.nl/>

transmission function is largely defined by the atmosphere, this assumption becomes questionable. As a result, the traditional standard star calibration method introduces considerable intrinsic uncertainties.

One calibration approach that circumvents the need for extrapolating from standard star fields is Stellar Locus Regression [SLR; 52, 53, 54, 55]. SLR utilizes the stellar locus, namely that the colors of stars fall on a well-defined line in color-color diagrams. SLR is a very powerful calibration tool for broadband photometry of extragalactic fields, and is especially useful for single-field observations in optical bands, where it can deliver zero-points of ≤ 0.02 mag precision [54]. However, it cannot be used for u -band, since variation in stellar metallicity leads to a widening of the stellar locus due to metal absorption lines in the NUV. The imprint of metallicity on the $u-g$ color is typically 10 times larger than on the $g-r$ color [53]. It is difficult to correct for the u -band scatter in SLR because the metallicity distribution of observed stars is usually unknown. On the other hand, the strong metallicity dependence is also a feature in stellar spectral energy distribution (SED) that can be utilized to study stellar population.

We here develop an alternative way to calibrate u -band photometry of single-field observations without overlapping calibrated u -band catalogs, by isolating a population of stars with homogeneous metallicity. Namely, our method utilizes the observed $u-g$ color of halo main sequence turn off (MSTO) stars, which are F/G type stars in the galactic halo that typically have a relatively low metallicity. As they are typically farther away than the standard stars, they do not saturate in deep exposures. Based on SDSS data, Schlafly et al. [56] find that the intrinsic $u-g$ color of the very edge of the distribution — those “blue tip” stars — is roughly constant over the SDSS footprint (mostly the Northern sky) with only small spatial variation. We observe that the remaining spatial variation is strongly correlated with galactic latitude b , which can be well described by a plane-parallel model. We fit this model across on the entire SDSS footprint, and use it as the basis of a method of u -band zero-point calibration for any instrument. Assuming that the spatial relation is true in the Southern sky as well, it can be used to calibrate data sets beyond the SDSS coverage. The method requires the exposures to be deep enough to reach the halo MSTO stars ($g \approx 21$), and g -band imaging to be available as well. The latter do not need to be previously calibrated, as we provide a prescription to do so using the ATLAS-Refcat2 catalogue [57].

As a proof of principle, we here test our calibration method on KiDS, ATLAS and the NOIRLab Source Catalog [NSC, 58] stars, and compare the results with the SDSS u -band photometry. We find an improvement in the zero-point scatter in all cases, regardless of the original calibration method

(SLR for KiDS, standard stars for ATLAS and comparison with previous catalogs for NSC). The zero-point precision of u -band improves from 0.033 mag to 0.016 mag for KiDS, 0.027 mag to 0.020 mag for ATLAS, and 0.041 mag to 0.016 mag for NSC. The quoted after-calibration scatters are all based on a joint ug -bands calibration, as our method calibrates the u -band relative to the g -band. We show that a joint calibration is necessary, by examining the original g -band photometry of KiDS, ATLAS and NSC catalog and estimating their contribution to the uncertainties in the final calibrated u -band. We show that the g -band photometry can be improved by calibrating with respect to the reference catalog for the Asteroid Terrestrial-impact Last Alert System [57, ATLAS-Refcat2], and compare the calibration with SDSS and the Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System [PanSTARRS; 59]. In sum, the method presented here can be used to calibrate ug -band imaging, using only overlapping ATLAS-Refcat2 photometry. It is thus available for the full sky; however, since it is based on colors of halo stars, we limit the analysis to galactic latitudes $|b| > 30^\circ$ and with extinction $E(B-V) < 0.1$.

This paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2.3 we describe the data sets used in this work, together with the selections of the star samples and the details of catalog cross-matching. Sect. 2.4 details our method of detecting the “blue tip” $u-g$ color and the fitting of the color-latitude model. In Sect. 2.5 we present the re-calibration on KiDS, ATLAS and NSC. We discuss possible applications and summarize our work in Sect. 2.6. Quoted magnitudes are in the AB system [60].

2.3 Data Description

In this work, we will test the calibration methods (for both the u - and g -bands) using star catalogs from KiDS [51], ATLAS [50] and NSC [58]. They will be referred to as the validation sets. We use much of the large area of SDSS [45] to develop the calibration approach for u -band, and use other parts of SDSS (regions overlapping the validation sets) as the truth for validation. ATLAS-Refcat2 [57] is used for calibrating the g -band. Since the latest SDSS calibration utilizes PanSTARRS calibration [48], we also compare our g -band calibration to PanSTARRS directly. The sky coverage of the data sets used in this work is shown in Fig. 2.1. Table 2.1 summarises the usage of these data sets.

For developing the method, we strive to select stellar samples of high purity. Therefore, we use the photometric quality flags provided by SDSS in all available bands, i.e. $ugriz$. When calibrating u -band data with this method, similar care should be taken to select stellar samples with high purity, even if

Table 2.1: Overview of the datasets used in this work. We develop our u -band calibration model with SDSS and apply the method to the validation sets. SDSS is also used as the ug -bands truth catalog for the validation sets. Notice that the two SDSS catalogs are selected to not overlap each other. We also develop a g -band calibration procedure to accompany the u -band calibration, based on ATLAS-Refcat2 and using PanSTARRS as the truth for validation.

Model Construction	SDSS(u), ATLAS-Refcat2(g)
Validation Sets	KiDS, ATLAS, NSC
Truth Catalogs	SDSS(ug), PanSTARRS(g)

fewer bands are available. We expect that the single-field datasets that this method is of interest to are typically deeper than the survey data examined here, such that a robust selection of stars to this depth ($g \approx 21$) should be straightforward.

We initially keep only stars with magnitude 14-21 in all available bands and uncertainties < 0.1 , largely to illustrate how we develop this method. We later place an explicit cut of $18.5 < g < 20$ which obviates the previous cuts. We use extinction-corrected magnitudes; where those are not explicitly given in a catalog, we calculate them from Schlegel et al. [61]. Details of the sample selection for each dataset can be found in App .1.

2.3.1 SDSS data

We use stars from SDSS DR 15 [46]. We randomly select 640 non-overlapping fields of $2 \times 2 \text{ deg}^2$: in the galactic North ($b > 30^\circ$), we query 400 fields from the region $8\text{h} < \text{R.A.} < 16\text{h}$ and $-10^\circ < \text{Dec.} < 70^\circ$; in the South ($b < -30^\circ$), we select 240 fields in between $-3\text{h} < \text{R.A.} < 5\text{h}$ and $-10^\circ < \text{Dec.} < 30^\circ$. We exclude the KiDS and ATLAS regions, as well as tiles that overlap known Globular and Open Clusters.

2.3.2 KiDS data

KiDS is a 1350 deg^2 optical imaging survey designed to study weak gravitational lensing and galaxy evolution. We use the KiDS Data Release 4.1 [51] multi-band source catalogue. The original KiDS photometry is calibrated with SLR, followed by a latitude-dependent correction for u -band (similar to our approach), and a final calibration of r -band magnitudes to Gaia DR2 [63], shifting the zero-points of all bands accordingly [51]. The catalogue consists of sources detected from 1006 tiles ($\sim 1 \times 1 \text{ deg}^2$ FOV) observed with filters u, g, r , and i , all of which have low extinction $E(B-V) < 0.1$. The entire North part of

Figure 2.1: Sky coverage of the data used in this work. For each survey, we indicate the fields that we use ($1 \times 1 \text{ deg}^2$ or $2 \times 2 \text{ deg}^2$) by colored boxes: green for SDSS, blue for KiDS, red for ATLAS, and gray for NSC. SDSS fields are selected randomly from the area with $|b| > 30^\circ$ and $E(B-V) < 0.1$. The KiDS North area entirely overlaps SDSS, while KiDS South has no SDSS overlap. ATLAS tiles overlapping SDSS are shown in yellow. PanSTARRS is available for all fields at declination above -30° , and ATLAS-Refcat2 is full-sky. The star symbols indicate some known Globular Clusters (GCs) and Open Clusters (OCs), which we exclude here. The Milky Way is indicated by gray lines at $b = 30^\circ, 0^\circ, -30^\circ$. The Sagittarius Stream is indicated as orange lines at $|\beta| = 7^\circ$, where β is the latitude in the Sagittarius Coordinate System [62].

KiDS (492 tiles) overlaps SDSS, while the South part (514 tiles) is completely out of the SDSS footprint. Notice that a small portion of KiDS North has a galactic latitude lower than 30° (see Fig. 2.1), but since the extinction in that region is low, we do not exclude those tiles. We use the extinction-corrected Gaussian aperture and PSF (GAaP) magnitudes, a measurement of the flux inside a tapered aperture. The GAaP magnitudes account for PSF differences between observations in different filter bands for accurate color measurements while optimizing SNR. For stars, the GAaP magnitudes measure the total flux [64].

2.3.3 ATLAS data

ATLAS is an optical *ugriz* survey that aims to cover 4700 square degrees of the Southern Sky at high galactic latitudes to comparable depths as SDSS in the North. ATLAS utilizes the same telescope as KiDS (VST, the VLT Survey Telescope) thus they share the same set of filters. ATLAS uses the ESO nightly standard stars and compares the zero-points with APASS, the AAVSO (American Association of Variable Star Observers) Photometric All-Sky Survey⁶ [50, 65]. We download sources in ATLAS Data Release 4⁷ from two regions: the galactic North region $10\text{h} < \text{R.A.} < 16\text{h}$ and $-4^\circ < \text{Dec.} < 0^\circ$, and the galactic South with $-2.5\text{h} < \text{R.A.} < 4\text{h}$. We split the sources into 1019 tiles with an approximate tile size of $2 \times 2 \text{ deg}^2$, a larger size than KiDS in order to balance the number of stars in each tile. Most of the ATLAS regions overlapping SDSS are at the edge of SDSS, yielding fewer stars matching with SDSS. Out of all the 1019 tiles, only 152 tiles overlap a large enough SDSS area to yield > 300 stars in common). Notice that in the Galactic North region, we limit the data to $\text{Dec.} > -4^\circ$ in order to remain in the fully contiguous area of SDSS coverage, avoiding single scans at high airmass [see e.g. fig. 1 of 48].

2.3.4 NSC data

We use the DECam *ug* data from the NOIRLab⁸ Source Catalog (NSC), a collection and reduction of public imaging data taken from various facilities [58]. Only a few NSC exposures are taken with the *u*-band filter, all taken with DECam. The NSC DR2 catalogue calibrates the *u*-band imaging with SkyMapper and Gaia DR2 in the North, and GALEX, Gaia and 2MASS [66] in the South. From the NSC catalog, we select stars at lower Galactic Latitude

⁶<https://www.aavso.org/apass>

⁷<http://osa.roe.ac.uk/>

⁸<https://noirlab.edu/public/>

($|b| > 30^\circ$) and overlapping PanSTARRS (Dec. $> -30^\circ$), and assign them to individual DECam exposures according to exposure centers. Only 158 tiles have enough stars (more than 300 within $18.5 < g < 20$ and ug mag error < 0.1) and only 72 of them have enough matches with SDSS.

2.3.5 PanSTARRS data

PanSTARRS is a wide-field survey with five broadbands (*grizy*). PanSTARRS has a consistent photometric calibration of $7 \sim 12.4$ mmags across all of the Northern sky down to Dec. $> -30^\circ$ [67]. We retrieve PanSTARRS data to cover the footprint of the validation sets.

2.3.6 ATLAS-RefCat2 data

The ATLAS-Refcat2 (in the following Refcat2) is an all-sky star catalog containing nearly one billion stars which is 99% complete down to magnitude < 19 [57]. The catalog is a compilation of PanSTARRS DR1, SkyMapper DR1 [49], Tycho-2 [68], the Yale Bright Star Catalog [69], new detection from ATLAS Pathfinder and re-processed APASS images [65], in order to provide a consistent reference photometry catalog for the Asteroid Terrestrial-impact Last Alert System [ATLAS, 70]. Source photometry is converted into the PanSTARRS *griz* system and then combined with a weighted-mean to give the final Refcat2 magnitudes. The overall RMS uncertainty of Refcat2 is < 5 mmags, where in some small patches the uncertainty is < 20 mmags. We correct for the extinction with the same band coefficients as PanSTARRS.

We use Refcat2 as the g -band reference catalog instead of Gaia, because the Refcat2 g -band filter is closer to our target data sets. The Gaia $\{G, G_{BP}, G_{RP}\}$ filter system yields a more complicated color equation.

2.3.7 Catalog Cross-Matching

We match individual stars across the catalogs for two purposes:

1. to calibrate g -band magnitudes with respect to Refcat2, and
2. to compare the calibrated magnitudes (ug -bands) to the truth datasets (SDSS/PanSTARRS).

For both purposes, we need to match the validation sets to other surveys, i.e. to Refcat2 as the g -band calibrator and to SDSS/PanSTARRS as the truth. The match radius is set to 1 arcsec. Table 2.2 shows the average number of stars per tile with successful match. Notice that the number of stars with the initial selection is presented here (magnitudes = $[14, 21]$ and errors < 0.1).

Table 2.2: Average number of stars used per field. We list the typical number of matches to the other catalogs; the variations reflect different depths and field sizes. When matching ATLAS to SDSS, many fields have few matching stars because they are on the edges of SDSS, thus we adopt a larger tile size than KiDS to obtain more matched stars per field. The NSC sample is a combination of many shallow exposures and several deep exposures, so the average number of matched stars is also lower than KiDS.

	KiDS	ATLAS	NSC
tile size	$1^\circ \times 1^\circ$	$2^\circ \times 2^\circ$	$1.5^\circ \times 1.5^\circ$
minimum no. of stars detected	~ 200	~ 1000	~ 1100
maximum no. of stars detected	~ 1800	~ 14000	~ 13800
average no. of stars detected	~ 800	~ 3700	~ 3000
matched with SDSS	~ 700	~ 1400	~ 600
matched with Refcat2	~ 600	~ 3400	~ 560
matched with PanSTARRS	~ 700	~ 3500	~ 570

2.3.8 Color Equations

In order to test our method, we will compare (re-calibrated) u - and g -band magnitudes to SDSS and PanSTARRS. Since the filter transmission curves from different instruments/surveys are not identical, this invariably requires transforming one set of magnitudes into another using color-dependent equations. For KiDS and ATLAS, such transformations (based on cross-comparison to SDSS) have been published in the literature, but these do not suffice for our purposes: for KiDS, the color equations are reported only after subtracting an unspecified constant [71]; for ATLAS, the u -band transform to SDSS is specified as a linear color equation, but it is noted that a second-order fit would be preferable [72]. We initially attempt to re-derive the color transformations from overlapping survey data (App .2); however, we find systematic offsets between KiDS and ATLAS u - and g -band magnitudes, despite stemming from the same telescope and instrument. Similarly, we compare the NSC u - and g -band magnitudes with those published by the SHELA survey [73]; note that the SHELA data is also included in the NSC - with an independent data reduction - and therefore does not constitute an additional validation dataset for our main purpose), and find systematic differences. We therefore choose to not use color transformations from samples of cross-matched stars between KiDS/ATLAS/NSC and SDSS/PanSTARRS, since that would make our method dependent on assuming that one of these calibrations is correct and the other is not. For completeness, we include our own measurements of the color transforms from the cross-matched survey data in App .2. We note

that these color transformations show discrepancies with the color transformations derived from synthetic magnitudes (see below), but a full investigation of these discrepancies (shown in Fig. 4) is beyond the scope and purpose of this work.

Rather than relying on the calibration of one of the validation datasets, we opt to fit the color equations based on synthetic magnitudes, following the SDSS [74, 75] and PanSTARRS [76, 77] procedures. Synthetic magnitudes can be derived by convolving the spectra of well-calibrated spectrophotometric standard stars with the filter transmission functions of the instruments. For each star, the synthetic magnitudes yield the colors (i.e. magnitude differences, i.e. flux ratios) between different magnitudes, including between those from different instruments. By using a library of spectrophotometric standard stars that representatively samples the stellar locus, these relations can be determined as function of a specific color, i.e. the color transformation equations. The synthetic color equations are independent of the initial calibration of the validation sets, and are able to link the calibration accuracy to an absolute flux standard, in this case the AB system of SDSS. Because of their importance to photometric calibration, significant investments have been made to accurately and precisely map the spectra of sets of spectrophotometric standard stars, which puts us in a position to capitalize on this work. We therefore calculate synthetic magnitudes for all instruments involved in this work using stellar spectra from Pickles [78], XSL [The X-Shooter Spectral Library, 79, 80] and CALSPEC [81, 82]. We present the color transform equations and their determination in App .3.

2.4 Method Construction

We here construct a model for the correlation between the $u-g$ color of the “blue tip” stars and their galactic latitude. Ivezić et al. [83] showed that there are two distinct populations of MSTO stars in the Milky Way: one with a brighter magnitude ($g \lesssim 17$) and a redder $u-g$ color, while the other are fainter and bluer. Within each population, the $u-g$ color (a proxy for stellar metallicity) is nearly constant regardless of their magnitudes. The brighter, redder population stems from MSTOs in the thick galactic disk, while the fainter, bluer population is dominated by halo MSTOs which are older and have a lower metallicity. In Fig. 2.2 we replicate this finding. Ivezić et al. [83] find that the metallicity of the halo population is spatially invariant, as is also shown by other studies [e.g. 84]. This is the key assumption that we will utilize here.

We first isolate likely halo MSTO stars from the distribution of $u-g$ colors (Fig. 2.2). The first step is to isolate the population of stars approximately

Figure 2.2: 2d histogram of stars in a $4 \times 4 \text{ deg}^2$ SDSS field of g -band magnitude and $u-g$ color. The solid black box indicates the population dominated by halo MSTO stars, and the dashed black box indicates blue disk stars. Stars within the white box are preselected to be used for detecting the edge $u-g$ color (see Sect. 2.4.1 and Fig. 2.3). The g magnitude cut at 20.0 is chosen for a relatively complete sample selection. The $u-g$ pre-selection can be set by eye to include stars on both sides of the blue halo stars, and can be different for different surveys and un-calibrated instrumental magnitudes.

within the white box shown in Fig. 2.2, including stars on both sides of halo MSTOs while excluding the population of red stars. For un-calibrated data, the specific magnitude selection will be different according to the instrumental zero-point. We then fit a step-function-like model to find the edge color by counting the stars on both sides of the edge, described in Sect. 2.4.1. In SDSS data we find a dependence of the detected edge color on galactic latitude, which we attribute to contamination from disk MSTOs along the line of sight. We fit the color-latitude dependence with a plane-parallel disk model in Sect. 2.4.2. We also test the impact of spatial inhomogeneities in the halo on the relation by examining areas near the Sagittarius Stream, the largest stellar structure in the galactic halo. We find that any effect is too small for us to detect (Sect. 2.4.2). In Sect. 2.5, we show how the color-latitude relation can be used to calibrate u -band photometry, and verify the method on KiDS, ATLAS and NSC data sets.

Figure 2.3: Left: histogram of the $u-g$ colors of stars from one SDSS field (within the pre-selected magnitude and color range) and the intrinsic color distribution model (blue line; Eq. 2.2). The individual likelihood (Eq. 2.5) of each star is plotted in red points; these convolve the intrinsic model with the measurement uncertainty, effectively broadening the blue edge. Both the intrinsic model and the individual likelihood are re-scaled to match the histogram. Notice that the model is not fit to the histogram, but by evaluating the likelihood for each individual star (Eq. 2.5). The parameters used for plotting both models are taken from the best-fit convolved model (Eq. 2.5). Black vertical lines mark the Floor Interval for this field, within which the floor probability F is derived. Right: Posterior distribution of the model parameters. Notice that the intrinsic edge width σ_{int} is consistent with zero, affirming the assumption that it is small. The figures are created with functions defined in this notebook.

2.4.1 Detecting the “Blue Tip”

The goal is to detect the blue-side edge of the MSTOs’ $u-g$ color, as shown in the left panel of Fig. 2.3 where the $u-g$ distribution of MSTOs in an SDSS field is plotted. The stars included in Fig. 2.3 are pre-selected in g -band magnitude and $u-g$ color as discussed previously (the white box in Fig. 2.2). Note that the distribution extends to the redder side of the blue edge by about one magnitude, to help identify the blue edge. The pre-selection cuts are different for each survey and they are listed in Table 2.3.

Our starting point is the “blue tip” model of Schlafly et al. [56]:

$$P(x|x_0) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \text{Erf} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_{\text{int}}} \right) \right] + F. \quad (2.1)$$

Table 2.3: Data selection for the “blue tip” model. The g magnitude cuts and the $u-g$ pre-selection define the white box in Fig. 2.2, inside which the stars are used for detecting the edge color. “Floor Interval” specifies the $u-g$ range used to derive the floor probability density F in the model (equation [2.2] and [2.5]). The magnitude cut at 20.0 is chosen to compensate the completeness of some shallow fields in NSC. Color cuts and Floor Intervals are determined by eye examination and need to be adjusted changes in a few irregular fields.

	mag g cut	$u-g$ cut ($a - b$)	Floor Interval
SDSS	18.5 – 20.0	0.4 – 2.0	0.4 – 0.6
KiDS	18.5 – 20.0	0.0 – 2.0	0.0 – 0.6
ATLAS	18.5 – 20.0	0.0 – 2.0	0.0 – 0.6
NSC	18.5 – 20.0	0.5 – 2.0	0.5 – 0.8

It is a probability distribution of the $u-g$ color (denoted x) of each star in the field given the MSTO edge color x_0 . Here Erf() is the Gaussian Error function, the result of a step function convolved with a Gaussian of width σ_{int} . In Schlafly et al. [56], the only free parameter in the model is the MSTO edge color x_0 , while the intrinsic width of the edge σ_{int} and the floor probability F (number of stars per magnitude on the left side of the edge) are set to fixed values.

We make several modifications to the model:

- (i) We multiply by a Gaussian PDF centered on x_0 with width σ_p to better describe the distribution on the right side of the edge.
- (ii) We make σ_{int} a free parameter in the fit.
- (iii) The floor probability density F is calculated by counting the actual number of stars on the left side of the edge.

The model thus becomes:

$$P(x|x_0, \sigma_p, \sigma_{\text{int}}) = \frac{A}{2} \mathcal{N}(x_0, \sigma_p) \left[1 + \text{Erf} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_{\text{int}}} \right) \right] + F, \quad (2.2)$$

where A is the normalization factor for $P(x)$ to integrate to 1 over the sample range. Given the $u-g$ bounds a and b of the pre-selection, A is determined from other model parameters: the edge color x_0 , the width of the right-side Gaussian σ_p , the floor probability F , as well as a and b . Assuming that $\sigma_{\text{int}} \ll \sigma_p$, A can be calculated from:

$$A \cdot \text{Erf} \left(\frac{b - x_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_p} \right) = 2 - 2F(b - a). \quad (2.3)$$

Note that the model is robust against the arbitrariness of a and b (they are decided by eyes, see Table 2.3), since any small changes in a and b contribute only to the global normalization A and thus do not alter the probability of one star’s u - g color relative to another. Similarly, the floor probability density F , like a and b , has some arbitrariness in its determination. It is calculated by counting stars inside a pre-defined Floor Interval (FI) of the u - g color,

$$F = \left(\frac{N^{\text{FI}}}{N} \right) / \text{len}(\text{FI}), \quad (2.4)$$

where N^{FI} , N and $\text{len}(\text{FI})$ are the number of stars in the Floor Interval, the number of stars in the pre-selected sample (i.e. the white box in Fig. 2.2 and the length of the Floor Interval, respectively. Our choices for Floor Intervals for all surveys are summarized in Table 2.3.

We refer to model (2.2) as the intrinsic model. We make a further modification to account for the photometric uncertainties:

- (iv) For each star, the intrinsic model is convolved with the observed (photometric) uncertainty of the u - g color.

The convolution calculation is challenging. However, it can be substantially simplified with the assumption that the intrinsic edge width σ_{int} is small compared to both the width of the right-side Gaussian (σ_{p}) and the u - g photometry uncertainties (as we will see, σ_{int} is often consistent with zero, so this assumption holds true). Under this assumption, the convolved model (which now represents the individual likelihood of each star) becomes

$$\mathcal{L}_i^{\text{star}}(x_i|x_0, \sigma_{\text{p}}, \sigma_{\text{int}}) = \frac{A}{2} \mathcal{N}(x_0, \sigma_{\text{p}}) \left[1 + \text{Erf} \left(\frac{x_i - x_0}{\sqrt{2}\Sigma_i} \right) \right] + F, \quad (2.5)$$

where i labels each single star, and $\Sigma_i^2 = \sigma_{\text{int}}^2 + u_{\text{err},i}^2 + g_{\text{err},i}^2$ is the square sum of the intrinsic edge width and the photometric uncertainty of the u and g magnitudes. Comparing Eq. 2.5 to Eq. 2.2, we see that the convolution with the photometric uncertainty results in a broadening of the error function (i.e. the “step”), as one would have intuitively guessed. An example of the intrinsic and convolved models are shown in the left panel of Fig. 2.3 on top of the stars to which they are fit.

In sum, our model has 3 parameters: the edge color x_0 , the intrinsic edge width σ_{int} and the width of the right side Gaussian σ_{p} . A and F are not free parameters and are calculated with Eq. (2.3) and Eq. (2.4) respectively. We use flat priors on x_0 and σ_{p} , and an exponential prior $e^{-3\sigma_{\text{int}}}$ on σ_{int} to reflect our assumption that it is small and to ensure the convergence of the

chains. We use PyStan [85], a Python wrapper of Stan⁹ to perform an MCMC sampling. The posteriors of one field are shown in the right panel of Fig. 2.3. In most cases, we can only constrain an upper limit on σ_{int} which is indeed much smaller than σ_p or the $u-g$ uncertainty, typically 0.5 mags and 0.05 mags respectively.

2.4.2 Disk Contamination Model

The Color-Latitude Model

The procedures described in Sect. 2.4.1 deliver a robust edge $u-g$ color (x_0 in the model) for the halo MSTOs in each field. Schlafly et al. [56] find a slow spatial variation of the edge color across the sky, which they attribute to increasing contamination of the sample by redder disk stars. Following this interpretation, we show the measured edge color as function of galactic latitude b in both the North and the South in Fig. 2.4, and find a notable correlation.

Since dust extinction has already been accounted for, we follow Schlafly et al. and attribute this correlation to the contamination of disk stars in our halo MSTO sample. The contamination is unavoidable since the line of sight always goes through the galactic disk to reach the halo. Some of the disk stars, more distant and thus fainter ($g > 18.5$), may enter our sample selection, causing the blue tip to shift redder. Assuming the Milky Way has a flat disk, then, the number of disk stars in each exposure, and thus the amount of contamination, is roughly proportional to the path length through the disk. We model this contamination with a simple plane-parallel model (similar to airmass):

$$\hat{x}_0 = \frac{D}{|\sin b|} + x_0^{\text{halo}} \quad (2.6)$$

where \hat{x}_0 is the model prediction of the observed (contaminated) edge $u-g$ color, x_0^{halo} the intrinsic (uncontaminated) edge color of the pure halo MSTOs and D the disk contamination factor. The denominator $|\sin b|$ represents the line-of-sight length within the galactic disk, with b being the galactic latitude of the field. The detected edge color x_0 often has a Gaussian-like posterior distribution (Fig. 2.3), thus we model the measurements with a Gaussian likelihood:

$$\mathcal{L}_i^{\text{field}}(x_0^i | D, x_0^{\text{halo}}, \sigma_{\text{halo}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi(\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_{\text{halo}}^2)}} \exp \left[-\frac{(x_0^i - \hat{x}_0)^2}{2(\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_{\text{halo}}^2)} \right], \quad (2.7)$$

where i stands for each field, x_0^i is the detected edge color of the halo MSTOs

⁹<https://mc-stan.org/users/documentation/>

Figure 2.4: The correlation between the $u-g$ edge color of SDSS halo MSTOs (x_0) and galactic latitude. Left: SDSS data and best-fit disk contamination models (equation [2.6]). Each data point is the measured $u-g$ edge color of MSTOs, x_0 , in a field. The uncertainties on the data points are measured from the marginalized posterior distribution of x_0 . The separate fits in the Galactic North and South are shown with blue and orange colors respectively, with the shaded areas being 1σ and 2σ width of all curves generated from MCMC samples of (D, x_0^{halo}) and perturbed with a random Gaussian noise of width σ_{halo} , the intrinsic scatter of model (equation [2.7]). The best-fit joint model is plotted in yellow. Some outliers in the North are marked in red; these are exposures taken in two specific scans, run 4674 and 4678 (see Sect. 2.4.2) and are excluded from the fitting process due to their inconsistent photometry. Right: Posterior probability distribution of free parameters D , x_0^{halo} and σ_{halo} of the model. The dashed lines indicate constant $D+x_0$ values of the best-fit D and x_0^{halo} from the separate fits (see Table 2.4). These $D+x_0^{\text{halo}}$ values represent the observed MSTO colors with minimum contamination at $b = \pm 90^\circ$. The figures are created with this notebook.

in the field (x_0 in equation [2.5]), σ_i is the uncertainty on x_0 (the 1σ width of x_0 as shown in the right panel of Fig. 2.3) and σ_{halo} is the intrinsic scatter of the color-latitude relation.

Fitting Results

We fit the parameters D , x_0^{halo} and σ_{halo} with flat priors. To avoid *petitio principii* (using SDSS for both the calibration and the verification), we fit the model using only the regions outside of the validation sets.

Since the galactic halo is known to be much more complicated than a single-component sphere [86, 87, 88], we initially fit the Galactic North ($b > 0$) and South ($b < 0$) separately. Furthermore, Schlafly et al. [56] find a color asymmetry between the North and South (see table 4 therein).

We again use PyStan to fit the model with an MCMC and show the results in Fig. 2.4 and Table 2.4. We find some outliers in the Galactic North which are attributable to exposures taken in two specific SDSS runs¹⁰ (a contiguous period of drift scan), 4674 and 4678 (Fig. 1). We exclude those tiles from the MCMC fit, assuming that they suffer from systematic calibration issue [see also fig. 6 of 56].

We find marginal evidence for (small) differences in the color-latitude dependence between the North and South, since the D - x_0^{halo} posteriors do not overlap in the two-dimensional view (Fig. 2.4). D and x_0^{halo} are highly degenerate, and the data best constrains the combination ($D + x_0^{\text{halo}}$), corresponding to the blue edge color at $|b| = 90^\circ$ where the disk contamination is minimal. The fact that the D - x_0^{halo} posteriors do not overlap can be attributed to a slight mismatch between the blue edge colors at $|b| = 90^\circ$ in the best-fit model. The color difference (6 mmags) is in the opposite direction to Schlafly et al. [56], where the North is bluer than the South by 7.6 mmags (comparing the median colors of $40^\circ < |b| < 70^\circ$, see table 4 therein). Moreover, we note that this difference is smaller than the measured intrinsic scatter of the relation (~ 9 mmag). We also present a joint fit both the North and South in Fig. 2.4 and Table 2.4. The joint fit absorbs the small North-South difference into a slightly increased intrinsic scatter. The intrinsic scatter from the joint fit, 10.2 ± 0.4 mmags, is still smaller than the SDSS residual calibration uncertainty (per run) on the u -band [15 mmags; 48]; this is most likely due to a different tile size: in this work, we use $2 \times 2 \text{ deg}^2$ fields from SDSS, while an SDSS run consists of 6 columns, each $13'.5$ wide. Since the inferred North-South difference is quite small, and smaller than the best-fit intrinsic scatter, we continue with the model from the joint fit, describing both hemispheres with the same model

¹⁰https://www.sdss.org/dr16/imaging/imaging_basics/

Table 2.4: Maximum *a posteriori* parameters for SDSS disk contamination model (equation [2.6]) with 1σ uncertainties. Fitting all SDSS stars regardless of being in the Sagittarius Stream or not. The North and South fit yields consistent marginalized parameters. The joint fit is used for the *u*-band calibration.

	D	x_0^{halo}	σ_{halo}
Galactic North	0.048 ± 0.002	0.700 ± 0.003	0.0094 ± 0.0006
Galactic South	0.037 ± 0.003	0.705 ± 0.005	0.0088 ± 0.0009
Joint fit	0.040 ± 0.002	0.705 ± 0.003	0.0102 ± 0.0005

Table 2.5: Maximum *a posteriori* parameters for SDSS disk contamination model (equation [2.6]) with 1σ uncertainties. Separating the field stars from the Sagittarius Stream stars. The stream stars are allowed to have a different intrinsic color than that of the field stars. The fitting yields no significant difference between the two.

	D	$x_{0,\text{field}}^{\text{halo}}$	$x_{0,\text{stream}}^{\text{halo}}$	σ_{halo}
Galactic North	0.046 ± 0.003	0.702 ± 0.004	0.695 ± 0.004	0.0091 ± 0.0005
Galactic South	0.038 ± 0.004	0.703 ± 0.005	0.705 ± 0.005	0.0090 ± 0.0009
Joint fit	0.038 ± 0.002	0.709 ± 0.003	0.705 ± 0.003	0.0101 ± 0.0005

parameters, for simplicity.

The Sagittarius Stream

The Sagittarius Stream is the most dominant structure in the galactic halo, as shown in Fig. 2.1. We test whether fields within the Sagittarius Stream have a notably different *u-g* edge color by adding an additional free parameter, $x_{0,\text{stream}}^{\text{halo}}$, to the model. We keep D and σ_{halo} the same for tiles in and out of the stream, while allowing their halo colors to be different, parameterized with $x_{0,\text{field}}^{\text{halo}}$ for the field tiles, and $x_{0,\text{stream}}^{\text{halo}}$ for the tiles inside the Sagittarius Stream. All tiles in and out of the stream are fit simultaneously with the 4 parameters, using either the North/South separate model or the joint model. The stream tiles are defined to be within 7° from zero latitude of the Sagittarius Coordinate System [62]. In all models, the stream tiles show no significant color difference from the field tiles, as shown in Table 2.5.

2.5 Re-calibration of the Validation Sets

The key step to using the u -band calibration method for a specific data set is to determine the parameters D and x_0^{halo} of the color-latitude relation equation (2.6) for the instrument being used. Once these parameters, and thus the relation, are established, any new data set taken with the same instrument can be calibrated by direct comparison between the measured and predicted blue tip $u-g$ color x_0 . As the filter responses and CCD efficiency of a given instrument are generally different from SDSS, a different blue tip color x_0 will be measured. We here assume that the contamination factor D is universal among instruments with SDSS-like filters, since it is determined by the geometry of the Milky Way. The instrument-specific halo color x_0^{halo} can be derived by minimizing the u -band residual with respect to SDSS on overlapping fields. We demonstrate this process for VST (the KiDS and ATLAS data sets) and DECam (the NSC data) in Sect. 2.5.2.

As the calibration is based on the $u-g$ color, a well-calibrated g -band is necessary. Since we find inconsistencies between published color transformations from different surveys conducted with the same instruments (App .2), we choose to first re-calibrate the g -band survey data (Sect. 2.5.1).

2.5.1 The g -band calibration

KiDS calibrates the g -band by comparing to Gaia DR2 (for relative zero-points) and anchoring on SDSS [51] (for global zero-point). ATLAS uses the APASS for the g -band [50] and also ties to Gaia. NSC calibrate the g -band by comparing with PanSTARRS and ATLAS-Refcat2. We re-calibrate the g -band zero-points based entirely on Refcat2, and compare the results with SDSS. We also compare the calibration with PanSTARRS for a larger sample size beyond the SDSS footprint. The g -band calibration follows the procedures:

1. Match stars between Refcat2 and the validation sets as described in Sect. 2.3.7.
2. Convert Refcat2 g to $g_{\text{VST/DECam}}$ using equation (3) and calculate the g -band offset for each matched star.
3. Calculate the median offset for each field.
4. Adjust the g -band zeropoint by subtracting the median in each field, to yield calibrated g -band magnitudes.

The verification with SDSS/PanSTARRS follows the same routine:

Table 2.6: The median tile-offset standard deviation of the validation set comparing with other surveys, before and after our re-calibration. This table corresponds to Fig. 2.5, where the original offsets are shown in empty histograms and the calibrated offsets in blue. The standard deviations and the uncertainties in this table are derived from a boot-strap re-sampling from the corresponding distributions in Fig. 2.5.

	<i>g</i> -band std, compared to:		<i>u</i> -band std to SDSS (joint <i>ug</i> calibration)
	SDSS	PanSTARRS	
KiDS original	0.0134 ± 0.0005	0.0191 ± 0.0007	0.033 ± 0.002
KiDS calibrated	0.0110 ± 0.0007	0.00108 ± 0.00004	0.0157 ± 0.0006
ATLAS original	0.0106 ± 0.0006	0.005 ± 0.001	0.027 ± 0.001
ATLAS calibrated	0.011 ± 0.001	0.00094 ± 0.00005	0.020 ± 0.002
NSC original	0.0069 ± 0.0006	0.0096 ± 0.0004	0.041 ± 0.005
NSC calibrated	0.0074 ± 0.0006	0.00077 ± 0.00006	0.016 ± 0.001

1. Match stars between SDSS/PanSTARRS and the validation sets.
2. Convert $g_{\text{SDSS/Pan}}$ to $g_{\text{VST/DECam}}$ using equation (3).
3. Calculate the median-tile *g*-band offsets, before and after the re-calibration.

The resulting median-tile *g*-band offsets are shown in the left and middle columns of Fig. 2.5, with orange/blue color representing the original/re-calibrated data sets. We compare the measured standard deviations of the offset distributions in Table 2.6. For comparison, in Fig. 2.5 we also show (as empty histograms) the magnitude offsets between the original photometry and the validation datasets when transforming magnitudes with color equations fit directly on the cross-matched data sets (equation [1]).

Notice that the empty histograms (the original magnitudes converted into the SDSS system with color equations fit from overlapping data) are centered on zero by construction, since the constant offsets are absorbed into the color equations. The orange histograms (those converted with color equations from synthetic magnitudes), on the other hand, reveal a systematic difference between the validation sets and the SDSS AB system. After the re-calibration to Refcat-2, the orange histograms show negligible mean values with respect to both SDSS and PanSTARRS, indicating an improvement in systematic photometric accuracy.

Also notice that, after calibration, the RMS scatters with respect to PanSTARRS reduce to ≤ 1 mmag level. This is expected, since PanSTARRS is the major component of Refcat2 within its footprint. For the offsets with respect to SDSS, we find similar scatters before/after re-calibration on all data sets

Figure 2.5: The distributions of the median magnitude differences (computed per field) of the validation sets compared with reference truth catalogs. The orange histograms represent the original data release of KiDS/ATLAS/NSC, comparing to the reference data with color equations fit on the synthetic magnitudes (equation [3]). The blue histograms are the offsets after our re-calibration, also comparing to the references with equation (3). For comparison, the empty histograms show the offsets from the original data release, but with color equations fit on the cross-matched data sets (equation [1]). The empty histograms thus center on zero mean values by construction. The standard deviation of the original (orange) and re-calibrated (blue) distributions are listed in Table 2.6. Note that because the g -band re-calibration calibrates with respect to Refcat-2, which is heavily dominated by PanSTARRS, the re-calibrated g -band is in excellent agreement with PanSTARRS by construction.

(Table 2.6). The measured scatters on the VST data sets (both original and re-calibrated) are consistent with the reported scatter against SDSS: 0.014 mags for KiDS [71] and 0.013 mags for ATLAS [89]. The NSC g -band is reported to have a zero-point scatter (relative to its mean zero-point) of ~ 0.039 mags based on ~ 9000 fields [58]. We find it to be ~ 0.007 with respect to SDSS over the 72 tiles used in this work, which after the re-calibration remains at the same level. In sum, the re-calibration with Refcat2 improves the g -band zero-point accuracy, and keeps the same level of precision (comparing with SDSS), or improves it (comparing with PanSTARRS).

2.5.2 The u -band calibration

We assume that the contamination factor D is the same for all instruments of SDSS-like filters, and keep it fixed at 0.04 from the SDSS joint fit (Table 2.4). The halo color x_0^{halo} may vary for different facilities, and needs to be determined in order to use equation (2.6) for calibrating u -band zero-points based on observed edge colors. Notice that x_0^{halo} cannot be determined a priori (e.g. via a color transform from SDSS to other instruments). This is because x_0^{halo} is not the $u - g$ color of a specific star, but the edge color of a population, therefore it is difficult to define the corresponding colors (e.g. $g - i$) involved in the ug -band color equations. However, x_0^{halo} is straightforward to establish empirically by comparing with SDSS fields (which we take as truth values). Namely, because the u -band color transformation ($u_{\text{inst}} - u_{\text{SDSS}}$) between the instrument in question and SDSS depends only on g - and i -band (which are both calibrated at this point), any residual offset with SDSS can simply be negated by adjusting x_0^{halo} . In practice, we therefore simultaneously determine x_0^{halo} and calibrate the u -band photometry of the dataset in question. Technically, this procedure works on a single field overlapping SDSS, but we suggest performing it with as many tiles as possible to mitigate possible bias rooted in scatters of SDSS photometry.

Since KiDS and ATLAS are both taken with VST, we use both to determine the relation for VST:

1. For a given field, calibrate the KiDS/ATLAS g -band magnitudes with Refcat2 as in Sect. 2.5.1.
2. Detect the $(u - g)$ edge colors with the calibrated g -band, as described in Sect. 2.4.1. Notice that these colors are uncalibrated, as the u -band is still uncalibrated.
3. For each field, calculate the residual between the measured $(u - g)$ edge color and the model prediction equation (2.6), setting the contamination

factor D to 0.04, and the halo color x_0^{halo} to zero for an initial pass.

4. Calibrate the u -band magnitudes from the residuals in (iii) as the zero-points for each field. (Recall that the method calibrates the u -band zero-point by “moving” each field onto the best-fit relation, equation [2.6]).
5. Compare the calibrated u -band magnitudes with SDSS using the synthetic color transform (3), and calculate the residual median offsets per field. The halo color x_0^{halo} is the mean of the distribution of median offsets.

This procedure yields the calibrated color-latitude relation for VST:

$$(u - g)_{\text{VST}} = \frac{0.04}{|\sin b|} + 0.697. \quad (2.8)$$

The procedure for the NSC catalog is exactly the same. The resulting color-latitude equation for DECam is:

$$(u - g)_{\text{DECam}} = \frac{0.04}{|\sin b|} + 0.504. \quad (2.9)$$

With the above instrument-specific curves, new datasets taken with VST or DECam can be straightforwardly calibrated:

1. Calibrate the g -band onto the SDSS AB system (2.5.1).
2. Detect the halo MSTO edge color as described in Sect. 2.4.1.
3. Compare with equation (2.8) or (2.9) depending on instrument. Calibrate onto the curve.

The resulting u -band offset distributions are shown in the right column of Fig. 2.5. Similar to the g -band panels, the offset distributions from the original data sets are shown in orange, while the re-calibrated histograms in blue. The orange/blue histograms are offsets derived with the synthetic color equations (3), while the empty histograms are the original data sets with color equations derived from overlapping fields (equation [1]) for comparison. The standard deviation of the empty and the blue distributions are shown in corresponding entries in Table 2.6.

The original KiDS/ATLAS u -band zeropoint precision is reported for both to be ~ 0.035 mags RMS scatter relative to SDSS [see the release notes 71, 89]. We first produce our own estimate of this value from the KiDS/ATLAS data included in this work, transforming the original magnitude to SDSS using the

color transformations that we fit to overlapping data (equation [1]), i.e. the empty histograms in Fig. 2.5. We find a standard deviation of 0.033 mags for KiDS and 0.027 mags for ATLAS. The smaller scatter for ATLAS is most likely due to the larger tile size used in this work. Similarly, a global NSC u -band scatter of 0.07 mags is reported in Nidever et al. [58] while we find it to be 0.041 mags in the regions overlapping SDSS.

After the re-calibration, the standard deviation is reduced to ~ 0.016 mags for KiDS, 0.020 mags for ATLAS and 0.016 mags for NSC (these are based on the synthetic color equations [3]), i.e. the u -band precision is substantially improved for all three datasets.

2.6 Summary and Discussion

In this paper we have presented a new method for the photometric calibration of u -band imaging. The method requires no standard star comparison, nor does it require the fields to overlap with each other. This makes our method powerful even for pointed, single-field observations. It is applicable to fields outside the galactic plane ($|b| > 30^\circ$), for which both u -band and g -band imaging are available, deep enough to detect the halo MSTO population ($g \approx 21$). Based on comparing three validation datasets (KiDS, ATLAS, and NSC) with SDSS u -band photometry, we reach a competitive precision for the zero-point calibration (≤ 0.02 mag), satisfying the Rubin-LSST photometry requirement.

Our method is based empirically on the slow spatial variation of $u-g$ color of halo MSTO stars. We develop an algorithm to detect the edge $u-g$ color of halo MSTOs (Sect. 2.4.1), and observe that this color is strongly correlated with galactic latitudes. We fit a simple plane-parallel model to the correlation (Sect. 2.4.2), and use it for the u -band calibration. The model is motivated by contamination of disk stars in the halo MSTO sample. It is worth noting that the photometric calibration of the Javalambre Photometric Local Universe Survey DR2 [J-PLUS; 90, 91] shares a similar flavor to our method, despite of a different approach and motivation. J-PLUS DR2 first builds a median-metallicity stellar locus from a spectroscopic sample, then model the deviance of observed color to the locus as a function of milky way locations. A precision of 18 mmag in u -band at a magnitude limit of 21.16 is reported for the final calibration. The deviance-latitude dependence found by J-PLUS [fig. 6 of 91] is notably similar to the color-latitude relation that we utilize here, which is attributed to stellar metallicity variation rather than contamination of a halo stellar population by disk stars. We emphasize that the color-latitude relation we find is entirely empirical, and that the interpretation of the underlying physical cause of the color-latitude relation, equation (2.6), has no effect on

our method itself, other than the assumption that the relation holds in both hemispheres. In App .4 we attempt to use Gaia to reject disk stars from the sample of halo MSTO stars, but find that Gaia EDR3 is not yet deep enough to substantially reduce the disk star contamination.

Sect. 2.5.2 details how to establish the color-latitude relation for a specific instrument. Once the relation is found, it can be used to calibrate any data taken with the instrument. The magnitude transform to SDSS is also needed in the procedure, and can be derived with synthetic magnitudes as described in App .3 given the filter responses. The method can then be through the following steps:

1. For a given field, calibrate the g -band with ATLAS-Refcat2 as described in Sect. 2.5.1.
2. Detect the halo MSTO “blue tip” u - g color using model (2.5).
3. Calibrate the detected color onto the color-latitude relation (equation [2.8] for VST-Omegacam and equation [2.9] for DECam). In other words, use the residual between the detected u - g color and the color-latitude relation as the u -band zero-point.

In this work, we present calibrated color-latitude relations for Omegacam and DECam, but the method can be straightforwardly expanded to other instruments (provided that some fields overlapping SDSS are available) following the procedure discussed in Sect. 2.5.2.

We have verified the method by re-calibrating the u -band photometry of the KiDS, ATLAS and NSC datasets, and find an improved zeropoint precision (when comparing to SDSS as the truth dataset) for all of them (Sect. 2.5.2). For KiDS/ATLAS/NSC, we find RMS scatters of 0.016/0.020/0.016 mag against SDSS, compared to the RMS scatters with the original calibration of 0.033/0.027/0.041 mag.

As the method includes (re-)calibrating g -band imaging of the same field, using ATLAS-Refcat2 as the g -band reference, we also examine the re-calibrated vs. original g -band photometry of KiDS/ATLAS/NSC. We show that for all three, the re-calibration is in excellent agreement with PanSTARRS (as expected, given that ATLAS-Refcat2 relies heavily on PanSTARRS), and remains at the same precision level with respect to SDSS as the original g -band calibration.

One of the applications that could benefit from this work is photometric redshift measurements of large scale cosmological imaging surveys. For example, the KiDS-1000 cosmology is based on a nine-band photometric redshift estimate [$ugriZYJHK_s$; 92, 93], where the u -band has the largest zero-point

scatter out of the 4 optical bands (0.035, 0.014, 0.005, and 0.009 mags for *ugri* respectively; see the DR4 release note Kuijken [71]). Our re-calibration method reduces the *u*-band scatter by about factor of two, which should improve the photometric redshift estimation.

This work has potential benefits for the Rubin Observatory’s LSST. The current photometric calibration plan (Michael Wood-Vasey, private communication) is to adopt a similar pipeline as the Forward Global Calibration Method (FGCM) by Burke et al. and DES Collaboration [94]. FGCM combines auxiliary data with survey images and models the atmosphere and system throughput of all bands at any survey time and location. FGCM has delivered a stable photometric calibration of 6 – 7 mmags random error per exposure for the first three years of the Dark Energy Survey [DES; 95] in the *grizY* bands. However, since DES does not include *u*-band observations, the performance of FGCM on *u*-band, which depends sensitively on the near-UV cut-off of atmospheric transparency, is to this date unknown. Our method provides a fast calibration of the LSST *u*-band imaging which can be used as a preliminary on-the-fly calibration, an independent cross-check of FGCM, and/or be incorporated into the FGCM scheme. Moreover, the large Southern sky footprint of LSST provides complementary coverage to SDSS in the North, which will fact-check our assumption of a whole-sky color-latitude relation. Furthermore, as LSST is deeper than SDSS, it will allow us to study the magnitude dependence of the MSTO blue-tip color, and thus the stellar structure in the Milky Way halo.

Chapter 3

Color-based Galaxy Blends detection

This chapter describes my project to identify unrecognized galaxy blends with Machine Learning. This work is planned to be submitted to *MNRAS* for peer review and publication.

3.1 Abstract

We develop a new method to detect unrecognized blends based only on colors of galaxies. The method utilizes Self Organizing Map (SOM), an unsupervised neural network designed to represent a high-dimensional data set with a low-dimension (usually 2-d) map. We test the method on a combined data set of COSMOS, COSMOS HST and an assembly of spectroscopic redshift catalogs in the same area. Our preliminary results show that based on the 9-band photometry in COSMOS, the method can detect and remove 14.74% to 67.75% of the unrecognized blends at the cost of 7.50% to 48.76% of all galaxies. This also corresponds to removing 9.33% to 52.48% of the catastrophic photo-z outliers at the same time.

3.2 Introduction

Modern optical cosmology surveys face great challenges in both the sample size and complexity, due to increasing survey depth. For example, the Kilo-Degree Survey [KiDS; 51] measures $\sim 10^8$ sources at a depth of $r \sim 25$; The Dark Energy Survey [DES; 95] and the Hyper Suprime-Cam Subaru Strategic Program Survey [HSC-SSP; 28] have a limiting magnitude $r \sim 26$ to observe

$\sim 10^8$ galaxies. The Legacy Survey of Space and Time [LSST; 24] to be conducted at the Vera C. Rubin Observatory will observe $\sim 10^{10}$ galaxies at a limiting magnitude of $r \sim 27.5$ (in 10 years). When the number density of sources increases rapidly, there is also a greater chance of them overlapping in projection, causing a “blend”. Sanchez et al. [96] show that at the 10-year depth of LSST, 62% of galaxies will have at least 1% flux contributed from neighbouring sources. Fortunately, the majority of blends can be recognized by the ground detection algorithms and be de-blended with dedicated tools such as SCARLET [97]. However, Dawson et al. [98] show that there are still 14% “ambiguous blends” (also known as the unrecognized blends) for the LSST gold sample at $i \sim 25.3$, and the situation will only get worse when the observations go deeper. These unrecognized blends are sources detected as a single object from ground-based observations, but are in fact composed of and can be matched to multiple objects in a high-resolution space-based catalog (in this case, the *Hubble Space Telescope*).

The impact of blending is a key difficulty in large scale surveys like LSST. Specifically, blending affects the two essential measurements for weak lensing cosmology: shear (shape) of galaxies, and their photometric-redshift (photo-z). MacCrann et al. and DES Collaboration [99] find that blending-related effects are the dominant contribution to the mean multiplicative bias of approximately 2%. Mandelbaum [100] emphasizes that the impact of blending on photometric redshift estimation is particularly difficult to determine, since the spectroscopic redshift selection for samples used for training and calibrating photo-z may result in them having different unrecognized blend rates than the general galaxy population. Cunha et al. [32] also show that, without carefully matching the redshift distribution between the weak lensing sample and the calibration spec-z sample, 2% wrong (spectroscopic) redshifts can cause $\sim 15\%$ error in the dark energy equation of state w for DES (see table 2 therein). More recently, based on an emulated mock catalog, Nourbakhsh et al. [101] observe a ~ 0.02 decrease in the derived structure growth parameter $S_8 = \sigma_8(\Omega_m/0.3)^{0.5}$ due to unrecognized blends. In comparison, the current S_8 tension between local and early-universe measurements is around 0.066, or $2 \sim 3\sigma$.

We develop a new method to detect unrecognized blends at the catalog level using only broad-band photometry. This method utilizes an unsupervised artificial neural network called the Self Organizing Map [SOM; 102, 103, 104], a machine learning algorithm designed to represent a high-dimensional data set with a low-dimension (usually 2-d) map. We test the method on the COSMOS data set [105, 106] and find that, based on selected 9-band photometry of COSMOS, this method can detect and remove 14.74% to 67.75% of the unrecognized blends at the cost of 7.50% to 48.76% of all sources, depending on

the desired purity of the resulting sample. This also corresponds to removing 9.33% to 52.48% of the catastrophic photo-z outliers at the same time.

This paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 3.3 we describe the data sets used in this work. In Sect. 3.4 we briefly introduce the basic SOM algorithm, and describe in details our methodology of detecting unrecognized blends with SOM. Sect. 3.5 shows our preliminary results, and Sect. 3.6 summarizes this work.

3.3 Data Description

We use the COSMOS data set [Sect. 3.3.1; 105, 106] as the base catalog for this work. It is a combined catalog of data from several ground-based facilities. We match the COSMOS data to the HST catalog of the same region [Sect. 3.3.2; 107, 108] to mark the unrecognized blends for the training and validation of our SOM-blending algorithm. We also match the COSMOS data to an assembled spectroscopic redshift catalog in the COSMOS region (Sect. 3.3.3) to study the impact of blends on photo-z. The following sections detail our selection on the above data sets, and Sect. 3.3.4 describes how we match between catalogs to define unrecognized blends.

3.3.1 The COSMOS Data Set

The COSMOS data set [105, 106] contains precise photometric redshifts based on 30-band photometry for more than half a million objects over the 2 deg² COSMOS field at a 3σ depth of $i^+ < 26.2$. In this work, we utilize 9 band photometry data in COSMOS (u -band from CFHT, $BVri^+z^{++}$ -bands from Subaru, and YJH -bands from UltraVISTA) to mimic the LSST observation with Euclid synergies. A series of cuts are applied to select sources with high-fidelity photometry:

1. **FLAG_COSMOS=1 & FLAG_HJMCC=0 & FLAG_PETER=0.**

Sources that satisfy these cuts are kept. The first two flags mark sources within the COSMOS area that also have UltraVISTA coverage. The last flag removes saturated sources and bad areas in optical bands.

2. **b_FLAGS < 4.**

SExtractor photometry flags. We keep sources with **b_FLAGS = 0, 1 and 2**, which corresponds to isolated sources, sources with bright neighbors, and (recognized) blends, respectively. Here **b** stands for all of the $uBVri^+z^{++}YJH$ bands; sources that satisfy this cut in all bands are kept.

3. $b_IMAFLAGS_ISO = 0$.
Sources with the saturation flags of 0 in all bands are kept.
4. $FLUX_RADIUS > 0$.
Spurious sources with negative flux radius are removed.
5. $ip_FLUX_APER3/FLUX_RADIUS^2 < 0.002$.
Sources with low surface brightness are removed.

In addition, we remove sources that are outside of the HST coverage. We further select the “base COSMOS sample”, made of 138849 high S/N sources that satisfy:

- a. $TYPE = 0$.
Morphology classification based on NIR or 3.6 μm observation. Only galaxies are kept.
- b. $ip_MAG_AUTO < 24.5$.
We assume the *Euclid* depth of $i^+ \sim 24.5$.
- c. $ZPDF > 0$.
The COSMOS 30 band photo-z estimated with galaxy SED templates, measured at the median of the likelihood distributions. Only sources with positive photo-z measurement are used for training.

Out of the 138849 base COSMOS sample, we mark $FLAG_ISO=1$ for 60392 sources that are labeled as isolated in all bands (see item 2 above). We refer to these sources as the “Non-deblended sample”, while the rest 78457 sources are called the “Deblended sample”. Notice that the Non-deblended sample is based on ground source detections only.

Note that we do not cut on flux errors, nor do we exclude non-detections in any bands. We adopt the Lupton *asinh* magnitude [109], or “Luptitudes”, a magnitude system designed with well behavior at low or even negative fluxes (See APP .5 for how we calculated Luptitudes for the base COSMOS sample). All of the 138849 base sample sources with derived Luptitudes can be directly mapped onto the SOM for a blend classification, once the SOM is trained. However, not all of them can be used for training the SOM, since some might have un-physical colors due to blending. We match to the HST data set to mark their blendedness.

3.3.2 The HST Data Set

We use the COSMOS HST/ACS data set [hereafter the HST data set; 107, 108] as the truth for blends. The HST data set is obtained with the *Hubble Space*

Telescope in the F814W filter, covering a field that is 1.64 deg² in the COSMOS area at a 5 σ depth of 27.2. Some cuts are also applied on this data set:

1. keep `0 < mag_best < 26.5`.
We keep sources that are up to 2 mags fainter than the base COSMOS sample (`ip_MAG_AUTO < 24.5`) to allow for blending with fainter sources.
2. keep `0 < flux_radius < 10/0.049`
We remove spurious sources with negative flux radii, as well as diffuse sources larger than 10" (`flux_radius` is in units of pixels, and the HST ACS pixel scale is 0.049" /pix).
3. remove `mu_class = 3`.
Fake detections with `mu_class = 3` are removed. We keep galaxies (`mu_class = 1`) and point sources (`mu_class = 2`).

We get 719935 sources after the above cuts. We then calculate the effective size (as observed by Subaru) of all sources by convolving the `flux_radius` with the ground-based PSF:

$$\text{flux_radius_eff}^2 = (0.049 * \text{flux_radius})^2 + \Delta_{\text{PSF}}^2, \quad (3.1)$$

where

$$\Delta_{\text{PSF}}^2 = (3.328 * 0.2)^2 - (2.28 * 0.049)^2 \quad (3.2)$$

is the square difference of the Subaru PSF and the HST PSF in arcseconds. Here the Subaru pixel scale is 0.2" /pix, and again the HST ACS pixel ratio is 0.049" /pix. The PSF sizes (in pixels) for both instruments (3.328 for Subaru and 2.28 for HST) are estimated as the mode of the flux radius distribution of stars.

3.3.3 Spectroscopy Data Sets

We assemble the truth redshift catalog from a range of spectroscopy data sets covering the COSMOS field. They are:

1. zCOSMOS [110, 111]: zCOSMOS is a large-redshift survey in the COSMOS field conducted with the VIMOS spectrograph on the Very Large Telescope (VLT). The survey is designed to characterize the environments of/produce diagnostic information on the COSMOS galaxies and active galactic nuclei. We retrieve the zCOSMOS DR3 catalog which contains

20689 objects, and apply cuts to select high quality redshift measurements. Following the data release document¹, we keep the Confidence Class (cc) flag of:

- 4.x and 3.x: (very) secure redshift measurements.
- 9.5: one-line redshifts that are consistent with photometric redshifts at $|z_{\text{spec}} - z_{\text{phot}}|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) < 0.04$.
- 2.5: Probable redshifts that are consistent with photometric redshifts at $|z_{\text{spec}} - z_{\text{phot}}|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) < 0.04$.

The selected sample contains 15867 sources.

2. DEIMOS [112, 113]: The COSMOS DEIMOS Catalog consists of 10718 objects in the COSMOS field, observed through multi-slit spectroscopy with the Deep Imaging Multi-Object Spectrograph (DEIMOS) on the Keck II telescope. We keep sources with a quality flag $Q = 2$ or 1.5 , representing reliable spectroscopic identification or sources with $|z_{\text{spec}} - z_{\text{phot}}|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) < 0.1$, respectively. We also remove unphysical sources with $z_{\text{spec}} > 10$. This results in 8339 sources from DEIMOS.
3. C3R2 [114, 115, 116]: The Complete Calibration of the Color-Redshift Relation (C3R2) is a spectroscopic survey at depth $i \sim 24.5$. C3R2 aims to fill out the galaxy color space with spectroscopic redshifts, to provide a firm foundation for photometric-redshift calibration for upcoming weak lensing cosmology surveys. The C3R2 catalogs (DR1+DR2+DR3) consist of ~ 5000 spectroscopic redshift measurements from Keck and VLT, of which 2767 sources are within the COSMOS region. We keep 2451 of those with **flag** = 4, which have highly certain redshift estimates based on multiple line detections.
4. VUDS [117, 118]: The VIMOS Ultra Deep Survey (VUDS) is a spectroscopic redshift survey of ~ 10000 very faint galaxies to study the major phase of galaxy assembly. VUDS covers 3 separate fields: COSMOS, ECDFS and VVDS-02h, providing an additional 384 sources in the COSMOS field. We keep only 144 sources with **zflags** = 3 or 4, which have moderate to high S/N with several absorption and/or emission lines, and strong cross-correlation signal with good to excellent continuum match to templates.

¹https://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/data/COSMOS/spectra/z-cosmos/zCOSMOS_DR3.pdf

Figure 3.1: Illustration of mis-identified blends if the matching is only performed in one go. Case 1: The ground detection matches a space detection with no other sources around (1-1 match). This is a “pure” source. Case 2: The ground detection matches to 2 space sources (1-2 match). This is an unrecognized blend. Case 3: Two ground-detections are closeby but de-blended, and each of them can be matched to 2 space detections within certain distance. They can be mistaken as unrecognized blends if we only match between the two catalogs in one run. We use a two-step matching algorithm to avoid such situation.

We combine all catalogs into one, and check for duplicated sources by matching their coordinates. We require the duplicated sources to agree within $z < 0.01$ among different catalogs. Sources with larger than 0.01 redshift difference are discarded. Finally, we obtain a spectroscopic redshift catalog of 22459 sources within the COSMOS field, which we refer to as the “spec-z sample”.

3.3.4 Catalog Matching

We match the base COSMOS catalog to the HST data to mark blended sources. An apparent approach is to count the number of matches for each ground source: those who match to only one HST source are clean, and those who match to multiple HST sources are blended. However, this simple approach fails when two close-by but cleanly deblended ground sources are matched to two close-by space detections and are both mistaken as blended objects, as shown in Fig. 3.1. In order to avoid such situations, we follow a similar

approach as in Dawson et al. [98] to cross-match the catalogs with a two-step matching algorithm:

1. **Primary Match:** A Primary Match is the closest HST object within $2''$ of a COSMOS object.
2. **Additional Match:** An Additional Match is any HST object that is non-Primary, and satisfies:
 - $\Theta/(\sigma_C + \sigma_H) < 1.5''$. Here Θ is the angular separation between the COSMOS object and its Additional Match, σ_C is the flux radius of the COSMOS galaxy in arcseconds (`FLUX_RADIUS`), and σ_H is the effective flux radius of the Additional Match convolved to ground PSF (`flux_radius_eff`, equation [3.1]).
 - $\Delta(\text{magnitude I}) < 2$. We allow the galaxies to blend with fainter sources (including stars) down to about 1/6 in flux.

We think of the COSMOS galaxies to be “pure” (up to the HST-ACS resolution) when they have only a Primary Match, and those who have at least one Additional Match(es) are marked as unrecognized blends. We find that more than 99% of COSMOS galaxies have a Primary Match, and around 17% of them have Additional Match(es) thus are unrecognized blends. We will refer to this cross-matched COSMOSxHST sample as the “labeled sample”, meaning the unrecognized blends are labeled for training and testing.

We then match the labeled sample to the spec-z sample where we simply match their coordinates within $1''$. Only 17935 spectra out of the 22459 objects are matched to the labeled sample, with the 4524 unmatched ones lying in the outskirts of the COSMOS footprint (no UltraVISTA coverage; see item 1 of section 3.3.1) or in the surrounding areas of very bright sources, where the photometry on the Subaru images are severely affected that we reject the nearby sources from the base cosmos sample (item 2 of section 3.3.1).

Some summary statistics of the final sample are listed in Table 3.1. For clarity, we re-iterate our definitions of the columns:

Deblended (Deb): Sources marked as blended in any of the $uBVri^+z^{++}YJH$ bands of COSMOS, but with fluxes successfully recovered.

Non-Deblended (Non-Deb): Sources isolated (not blended) in all of the $uBVri^+z^{++}YJH$ bands. The “purest” sample defined with ground-based observations.

Pure: Sources with only a Primary Match to the HST catalog. They are isolated clean sources up to the HST resolution.

Figure 3.2: Magnitude distribution of the base COSMOS catalog and the matched spec-z sample. The magnitudes of the spec-z sample come from HST-ACS/F814W filter or I -band measurements of the Subaru Telescope. For the base COSMOS sample, the derived Luptitudes are plotted. The spec-z sources above ~ 22.5 are mostly contribution from the C3R2 catalog.

Un-recognized Blends (Unrec): Sources with a Primary Match and at least one Additional Match. Certainly blended sources, but not recognized as a blend by the ground-based detection.

Notice that the base COSMOS sample are roughly divided equally into the Deblended and Non-Deblended categories. Both categories consist of about 83% pure sources and 17% unrecognized blends, labeled by matching to HST. This indicates that the ground detection based on galaxy morphology alone do not carry information about the unrecognized blends. In this work, however, we will show that the situation can be improved by adding the color information. Also notice that the Deblended sample has more spectrum matches than the Non-Deblended sample, which is expected since the deblended galaxies tend to be bigger (brighter) and are thus preferred by the spectroscopic surveys. The magnitude distribution of the matched catalogs is shown in Fig. 3.2.

We define the photometric redshift outliers (photo-z outliers; for the subsample with a spectrum match) to be the galaxies with $|z_{C30} - z_{\text{spec}}| > 0.15(1 + z_{\text{spec}})$, where z_{C30} is the COSMOS 30-band photometric redshift and z_{spec} is the spectroscopic redshift. Notice that the Non-Deblended sample have a lower outlier fraction than the Deblended sample. This is expected, since the flux reconstruction of the blended sources may not be perfect. The pure sample consist of both the Deblended sources and the Non-Deblended galaxies, thus its outlier rate is in between the two.

Table 3.1: Summary of the base COSMOS sample matched to the HST data set and the spectroscopy data set. The five columns are the Total (all of the base COSMOS sample), the Deblended sample, the Non-Deblended sample, the Pure sample and the Unrecognized blends, respectively, as described in Sect. 3.3.4.

	Total	Deb	Non-Deb	Pure	Unrec
# Sources	138849	78457	60392	116471	22378
Pure Fraction	83.0%	83.1%	82.8%	100%	0%
# Spectra Match	17935	12592	5343	16542	1393
Photo-z Outliers	480	399	81	383	97
Outlier Fraction	2.68%	3.17%	1.52%	2.32%	6.96%

3.4 Methods

Our key assumption is that the (unrecognized) blended galaxies have different colors from the isolated sources, which can be identified with Machine Learning. In this work, we utilize a self-organizing map (SOM) algorithm for this purpose. SOM is a type of unsupervised artificial neural network (ANN) designed to represent a high dimensional data set with a low-dimension (usually 2-d) map. It has become a popular photometric-redshift algorithm and is used in many studies [102, 103, 104, 114, 115, 119, 120, 121, 122]. We refer the readers to the cited literature [especially 103] for more details of the SOM algorithm, and here we briefly summarize the general algorithm and the specific configurations of our SOM in section 3.4.1. The details of our SOM-blending detection method is presented in section 3.4.2.

3.4.1 The SOM Configurations

A SOM consists of a fixed number (N) of grids of an arbitrary shape: rectangle, hexagon, triangle, etc. The grids define SOM “cells”, each associated with a weight vector ω_k , $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ which has the same dimension as the features of data. The weight vectors are randomly initialized, and the training process of the SOM is the training of the weight vectors.

The training takes one galaxy at each step, randomly drawn from the training sample of size N_T . The cells compete for the galaxy, resulting in a winner whose weight vector is the closest to the feature vector of the galaxy. The galaxy then “lands on” the winner cell, making an impact to the weight vectors of the winner and its close neighbors. These cells then shift their weights towards the feature vector of the galaxy, in such a way that a closer neighbor gets a larger shift. The process is repeated a set number of times

with replaceable sampling of galaxies from the training set. To make the map eventually converge, later galaxies will have a smaller impact on the cells. The decreasing rate of impact over iterations (the learning rate function) and the decay rate over distances on neighbors (the neighborhood function) are two sets of configuration parameters of SOM.

We define our map on a unit sphere tiled up with equal-area cells [healpix²; 123, 124]. We adopt a healpix of resolution index 5, which has 12288 cells in total where each cell is approximately $2 \times 2 \text{ deg}^2$. This results in an order of 10 galaxies per cell on average for the base COSMOS sample. Following Carrasco Kind and Brunner [103], we update the weight vectors in the training iteration t with

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathbf{k}}(t+1) = \boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathbf{k}}(t) + \alpha(t)H_{b,k}(t)[\mathbf{x}(t) - \boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathbf{k}}(t)], \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is the feature vector of the galaxy drawn at step t , and $\alpha(t)$ is the learning-rate factor defined with a starting value α_s and an ending value α_e :

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_s \left(\frac{\alpha_e}{\alpha_s} \right)^{t/N_T}, \quad (3.4)$$

and $H_{b,k}(t)$ is the neighborhood function:

$$H_{b,k}(t) = \exp \left[-D_{b,k}^2 / \sigma^2(t) \right]. \quad (3.5)$$

Here $D_{b,k}$ is generally the Euclidean distance between the k -th cell and the winner cell (b for best-match) in pixel units, but in our set-up, it is the angular distance between the cells in radians. The neighborhood function contains a width parameter $\sigma(t)$, also designed to provide a decaying behavior over iterations, such that early-iteration galaxies will affect farther cells on the map than later ones. It is defined as

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0} \right)^{t/N_T}, \quad (3.6)$$

with an initial value σ_0 the size of the entire map and an ending value σ_f comparable to the size of a single cell. Our SOM parameters are listed in Table 3.2.

3.4.2 Identification of Blends with SOM

After the training process, new samples can be mapped onto the SOM in the same way as the training sample (galaxies landing on their best match “winner”

²<http://healpix.sourceforge.net>

Table 3.2: Parameter values of the SOM configuration in this work. The α parameters are dimensionless scale factors, and the σ parameters are in radians.

α_s	α_e	σ_0	σ_f
0.9	0.5	π	0.036

cells), but they now do not alter the cell weights. The SOM is then used as a classifier where each cell is an individual class that spans a small sub-space in the higher dimensional feature space of sources. We seek to identify the sub-spaces where the (unrecognized) blended galaxies tend to appear.

For the purpose of cross-validation, we split the labeled sample into three parts:

The training sample: A random half of the Pure sample, but not including any sources with a spectrum match. This is because we have a limited number of spectrum which we reserve for the validation purpose. To avoid unwanted selection, however, we do not simply exclude the spectrum matches from the training sample. Instead, we swap the sources with galaxies in the other half pure sample with similar properties and without a spectrum match. Specifically, we swap with a source with $\sum_i |\Delta b_i| < 10$, where $b_i \in \{u, B, V, r, i^+, z^{++}, Y, J, H, z_{C30}\}$. On average, this means that the source has less than 1 magnitude difference in each band and in the photometric redshift.

The identification sample: A random half of the unrecognized blends. The sample is also spectrum-free under the same source-swap approach with the other half unrecognized blends. We map this sample onto the trained SOM, and mark the SOM cells with high occupation of unrecognized blends. They are referred to as the **blending cells**.

The validation sample: The other half pure sample and the other half unrecognized blends. This sample contains all the spectrum matches. We map the validation sample onto the SOM, recognize and remove from the sample the sources in the blending cells, and re-quantify the blends fraction and photo- z outliers.

We use all 8 colors of the 9 bands and 1 magnitude (i^+) from the base COSMOS sample. The colors and magnitude are re-scaled to center on 0 and to have a standard deviation of 1, so that they contribute equally to the competition of cells. The distance between a cell k and a source is calculated with

$$D_k^2 = \sum_i \frac{(F_i - \omega_{k,i})^2}{\sigma_i^2 + 1}, \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.3: An example of SOM used in this work. The SOM is trained with the training sample described in Sect. 3.4.2, and the weight vectors are scaled to match the original colors of the training sample for illustration. One color ($r - i^+$) of the 9 components of the weight vectors is shown.

where \mathbf{F} is the feature vector of the source (8 colors and 1 magnitude, whose components are indexed by i), σ_i is the uncertainty in the features (propagated from the magnitude uncertainties and also re-scaled by the same amount as with the features). We adopt the χ^2 distance D_k with an intrinsic uncertainty of 1. In some rare cases where one or two features are missing from a source (non-detection in a band), the distance is calculated with only the available features, and boosted proportionally to account for the missing features. The winner cell for this source is the one with minimum distance D_k .

The SOM weights are initialized randomly between $[-1,1]$. A trained SOM is shown in Fig. 3.3 as an example. The figure shows the $r - i^+$ component of the SOM weight vectors, which is scaled to match the original color of the sources (for the illustration purpose only). The SOM shown here is from one realization out of five used in this work.

3.5 Results

We train the SOM with the training sample described in Sect. 3.4.2, and map the identification sample onto the SOM. We then identify N blending cells as the top N cells with highest number ratio of unrecognized blends over the pure galaxies, as shown in the left panel of Fig. 3.4. Notice that the blending cells are evenly distributed over the entire map. This is expected, as blending happens to galaxies of all types and colors.

Next, we map the validation sample onto the SOM. As the validation sam-

Figure 3.4: Left: galaxy number of the unrecognized blends from the identification sample mapped onto each cell. We define the top N cells with the highest number as the blending cells. Right: (Normalized) distribution of distances between galaxies in the validation sample and their best-match cells. The distances are calculated with the 9 re-scaled features (8 colors plus i^+ band magnitude) of galaxies using equation (3.7). The unrecognized blends population have a larger mean distance than the pure sample, indicating a different color distribution.

ple contains both the pure galaxies and unrecognized blends, we could immediately compare the “goodness” of their mapping to the SOM. Specifically, we examine the distance between a galaxy and its best match cell as defined in equation (3.7). The distance distributions for the two sub-samples in the validation sample are shown in the right panel of Fig. 3.4. The figure clearly shows that the unrecognized blends are typically more distant to their best match cells, confirming our assumption that they have different colors than the pure sample.

We then identify the galaxies that land on the blending cells. These galaxies are then removed from the validation sample, and they will be referred to as the **removed sample**. Correspondingly, the rest of the validation sample will be called the **rest sample**. We re-quantify the blending and photometric outlier rate of the removed sample in Sect. 3.5.1 and the rest sample in Sect. 3.5.2.

3.5.1 The Removed Sample

We remove galaxies that are in top 500, 1000, 1500, 3000, or 5000 blending cells from the validation sample. As a comparison, we also (separately) remove sources in the same number of cells, but the cells are chosen randomly from the SOM. Some statistics of the removed galaxies are shown in the upper panels (a to d) of Fig. 3.5 and Table 3.3. We repeat the process for 5 different realizations

Figure 3.5: Main results of this work. Removing potentially blended sources from the validation sample and re-quantifying the blends/photo-z. The Top panels show the statistics of the galaxies being removed. a): the number ratio between the blended galaxies in the removed sample over all the blended galaxies in the validation sample. b): the blends in removed sample over all the removed sample. c): the photo-z outliers in the removed sample over all the photo-z outliers in the validation sample. d): the removed outliers over all the removed sample. The red points show the above quantities at top N blending cells, while the blue points show the same quantities in each panel but with removing N random cells. The lines connect the results from the same SOM realization (we use 5 realization in total). The lower panels (e - h) also show the same quantities, but for the rest of the validation sample after removing N cells. Corresponding results are also shown in Table 3.3.

of SOM, which results in 5 sets of data points in the figure. Table 3.3 records the averaged results from the 5 realizations.

Firstly, we ask how much blends are removed out of all the blended sources in the validation sample. Panel a) shows the fraction of the unrecognized blends in the removed sample over all the unrecognized blends in the validation sample. The fraction goes from 14.74% to 67.75% when removing top 500 to 5000 blending cells, corresponding to removing 7.50% to 48.76% of the validation sample at the same time. In comparison, when removing 500 to 5000 random cells, the fraction goes from 4.09% to 40.80% at the cost of 4.02% to 40.83% of the total population.

Secondly, we consider the accuracy of using the blending cells to identify the blended sources. Panel b) shows the fraction of the unrecognized blends in the removed sample over all the removed sources. As shown in the panel/table, the top 500 blending cells contain 5169 galaxies, out of which 1647 are unrecognized blends, resulting in a high blending fraction of $\sim 31.86\%$. In comparison, a random 500 cells yields only $\sim 16.51\%$ blends fraction. This suggests that the

Table 3.3: Main results of this work. Removing potentially blended sources from the validation sample and re-quantifying the blends/photo-z. The upper table shows the statistics for the removed sample in top N blending cells: number of cells removed from the SOM, corresponding number of sources removed from the validation sample, and the blending/photo-z outlier fractions. The lower panel shows a comparison case where N random cells are used. The columns are: cells – number of cells to remove; gal – number of galaxies in those cells, removed from the validation sample; f_{gal} – fraction of galaxies removed from the validation sample; bl – number of unrecognized blends in the removed sample; $f_{\text{bl}}^{\text{bl}}$ – fraction of unrecognized blends in the removed sample over all of the unrecognized blends in the validation sample; $f_{\text{rm}}^{\text{bl}}$ – fraction of unrecognized blends in the removed sample over all the removed sample; pz – the number of photo-z outlier; $f_{\text{pz}}^{\text{pz}}$ – fraction of photo-z outliers in the removed sample over all removed sample; $f_{\text{rm}}^{\text{pz}}$ – fraction of photo-z outliers in the removed sample over all the removed sample. All numbers are averaged over the 5 SOM realizations in this work, and the results for each realization are also plotted in Fig. 3.5.

Top N Blending Cells, Removed Sample								
cells	gal	$\%f_{\text{gal}}$	bl	$\%f_{\text{bl}}^{\text{bl}}$	$\%f_{\text{rm}}^{\text{bl}}$	pz	$\%f_{\text{pz}}^{\text{pz}}$	$\%f_{\text{rm}}^{\text{pz}}$
500	5169	7.50	1647	14.74	31.86	44	9.33	10.32
1000	9163	13.29	2744	24.56	29.95	77	16.18	9.40
2000	16100	23.36	4378	39.18	27.19	131	27.52	8.12
3000	22263	32.30	5586	49.99	25.09	175	36.89	6.79
5000	33606	48.76	7571	67.75	22.53	249	52.48	5.23
N Random Cells, Removed Sample								
cells	gal	$\%f_{\text{gal}}$	bl	$\%f_{\text{bl}}^{\text{bl}}$	$\%f_{\text{rm}}^{\text{bl}}$	pz	$\%f_{\text{pz}}^{\text{pz}}$	$\%f_{\text{rm}}^{\text{pz}}$
500	2769	4.02	457	4.09	16.51	19	4.12	2.95
1000	5616	8.15	916	8.20	16.32	40	8.40	2.69
2000	11274	16.36	1833	16.41	16.26	76	16.13	2.68
3000	16685	24.21	2719	24.33	16.30	116	24.45	2.74
5000	28146	40.83	4559	40.80	16.20	204	43.03	2.76

SOM blending cells are efficient in finding unrecognized blends. Moving to the other extreme, even when we remove as many as top 5000 cells to dilute the detection, we still find a larger blending fraction than the random selection (22.53% vs. 16.20%).

Next, we examine similar quantities for the photo-z outliers. Panel c) shows the fraction of the removed outliers over all the outliers, and panel d) shows the fraction of the removed outliers over all removed sources. We observe a similar trend here: the top- N algorithm can remove more outliers than a random selection, and with a higher accuracy.

3.5.2 The Rest Sample

We then turn our attention to the rest of the validation sample after removing galaxies, shown in the lower panels (e - h) of Fig. 2.5 and Table 3.4.

Panel e) shows the fraction of unrecognized blends in the rest sample over all the unrecognized blends. By definition, it is complimentary to the data points in panel a). We conclude that the the top- N procedure removes more blends than a random selection, leaving a cleaner rest sample after removing. Similarly, panel f) shows the fraction of the unrecognized blends in the rest sample over all the rest sample. Notice that the ratio is lower than a random selection immediately at 500 cells, and keeps getting even lower with more cells removed. This again indicates that the removal of blends is efficient and the rest sample is relatively clean.

Panels g) and h) show the similar statistics of photo-z outliers for the rest sample. Although not significant, we observe that the blending cells are still better at removing the outliers than a random selection.

3.6 Summary And Discussion

We present a color-based method to detect unrecognized blends. The method uses a machine learning algorithm: the Self-Organizing Map [SOM; 102, 103, 104] as a classifier to identify potential blends. SOM is itself un-supervised, but to identify the SOM cells where potential blends tend to gather, a training set with accurate blending information is needed.

We test the method on the COSMOS data set [105, 106], where the higher-resolution HST catalog is also available [107, 108] as the truth for blends. Following Dawson et al. [98], we match the HST catalog to the COSMOS data with a 2-step matching algorithm designed to detect unrecognized blends (Sect. 3.3.4). We find 17.0% unrecognized blends for the COSMOS data set at $i^+ < 24.5$. Interestingly, we also find similar fractions of 16.9% and 17.2%

Table 3.4: Main results of this work. Similar to Table 3.3 but for the rest sample. The upper table shows the statistics for the rest sample after removing sources in top N blending cells, while the lower table shows a comparison case where N random cells are removed. The column definitions are similar to Table 3.3. All numbers are averaged over the 5 SOM realizations in this work, and the results for each realization are also plotted in Fig. 3.5.

Top N Blending Cells, Rest Sample								
cells	gal	$\%f_{\text{gal}}$	bl	$\%f_{\text{bl}}^{\text{bl}}$	$\%f_{\text{rest}}^{\text{bl}}$	pz	$\%f_{\text{pz}}^{\text{pz}}$	$\%f_{\text{rest}}^{\text{pz}}$
500	63682	92.50	9604	85.26	14.95	432	90.67	2.48
1000	59688	86.71	8507	75.44	14.11	399	83.82	2.34
2000	52751	76.64	6873	60.82	12.87	345	72.48	2.13
3000	46588	67.70	5665	50.01	11.98	301	63.11	1.97
5000	35245	51.24	3680	32.25	10.20	227	47.52	1.73
N Random Cells, Rest Sample								
cells	gal	$\%f_{\text{gal}}$	bl	$\%f_{\text{bl}}^{\text{bl}}$	$\%f_{\text{rest}}^{\text{bl}}$	pz	$\%f_{\text{pz}}^{\text{pz}}$	$\%f_{\text{rest}}^{\text{pz}}$
500	66082	95.98	10794	95.91	16.20	457	95.88	2.65
1000	63235	91.85	10335	91.80	16.21	436	91.60	2.66
2000	57577	83.64	9418	83.59	16.21	400	83.87	2.66
3000	52166	75.79	8532	75.67	16.19	360	75.55	2.64
5000	40705	59.17	6692	59.20	16.22	272	56.97	2.59

unrecognized blends in the De-blended sample and the Non-Deblended sample respectively, defined by the blending flags in the COSMOS data from ground detection (see Sect. 3.3.4 for more details). This indicates that the ground morphology measurements are in-sensitive to unrecognized blends.

We also assemble a spectroscopic redshift catalog from several source catalogs: zCOSMOS [110, 111], DEIMOS [112, 113], C3R2 [114, 115, 116], and VUDS [117, 118]. The assembled spec-z catalog is also matched to the COSMOS data to qualify the photometric redshift estimates. Especially, we examine the photo-z outliers defined as $|z_{C30} - z_{\text{spec}}| > 0.15(1 + z_{\text{spec}})$. We find that the unrecognized blends sample has a significantly higher photo-z outlier rate (6.96%) comparing to other categories: 3.17% for the De-blended, 1.52% for the Non-deblended and 2.32% for the pure sample.

We then split all the combined data sets into three sub-samples (Sect. 3.4.2): the training sample to train the SOM; the identification sample to map onto the SOM and identify “blending cells” – the SOM pixels where unrecognized blends tend to gather; and the validation sample, also mapped onto the SOM to test the detection of unrecognized blends with the blending cells. The sources mapped onto the blending cells are then removed from the validation sample to re-quantify the blends. We find that the process can remove 14.74% to 67.75% of the unrecognized blends at the cost of 7.50% to 48.76% of all sources in the validation sample. In the removed sample, the unrecognized blends fraction is 31.86% to 22.53% (lower when removing more cells), indicating an efficient removal of the blended sources. After the removal of sources, the rest of the validation sample has 14.95% to 10.20% unrecognized blends, significantly lower comparing to the fraction of 17.0% in the base COSMOS sample.

The same process is also used to re-quantify the photo-z outliers for the sub-sample with spectrum matches. We find similar trend as for the unrecognized blends, and the removal of photo-z outliers with blending cells again outperforms a random cell selection. However, the difference is not as significant as for the unrecognized blends. This is expected, as the blending cells are designed to detect unrecognized blends which is only mildly correlated with photo-z outliers (recall that only 6.96% of unrecognized blends are photo-z outliers). It is of great interest to identify “outliers cells” for the photo-z outlier detection in parallel to the blending cells in SOM. However, due to the limited number of spectroscopic sources, it is difficult to perform such a study here. We look forward to such a study based on simulated catalogs (e.g. DESC – Data Challenge 2 [DC2; 125]) in the future.

Chapter 4

Cluster Blends on Photo-z

This chapter describes my project to quantify the impact of blends on photo-z in cluster fields. This work will be published as a DESC note¹.

4.1 Introduction

Galaxy clusters are among the largest astrophysical objects in the Universe. They contain a few hundreds up to several thousands of galaxies, typically of mass range $10^{14} \sim 10^{15}$ solar mass. The formation of galaxy clusters is closely linked to the matter distribution in the universe, therefore, even a moderately precise measurement of the cluster abundance can lead to competitive cosmological constraints. Furthermore, the abundance of clusters also depends on the expansion history of the universe as well as the structure growth rate. This dual sensitivity makes galaxy cluster studies complicated yet particularly interesting.

Typically, galaxies only make up $\sim 1\%$ of the total mass of a cluster. However, galaxies are the main source of light in clusters. In optical bands, only the galaxies are visible. Intergalactic gas (intracluster medium, ICM) contributes another 9% to the total mass. As the ICM is typically very hot due to the deep potential well in the clusters, they emit X-ray radiation. Also due to the high temperature in ICM, photons from the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) can be scattered by high-energy electrons in galaxy clusters through inverse Compton scattering, in which the low-energy CMB photons receive an average energy boost that causes the spectral distortion of CMB (the Sunyaev–Zeldovich effect). Finally, the rest of the mass is in the form of dark matter. The dark matter component is not directly observable. However,

¹<https://lsstdesc.org/pages/publications.html>

gravitational distortion due to the large total mass of a cluster can be measured at nearby background galaxies, providing another probe to the cluster mass. Comparing to X-ray or the SZ detections, gravitational lensing provides the least biased mass estimates.

Due to the over-density of galaxies in clusters, there is a greater chance for the galaxies to be blended (either with cluster member galaxies or with foreground/background sources). This project aims to address this issue, and study the impact of blends on photometric redshifts in the cluster fields. The goal of this project is to produce a series of jupyter notebooks to demonstrate this topic. The notebooks are to be presented at collaboration meetings of the Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC), and to be published along with a DESC note.

4.2 Quick Example

This project is based on the Data Challenge 2 [DC2; 125] simulations of DESC. It is the second data challenge carried out in preparation for analysis of LSST at Rubin Observatory. Two catalog products are used in this project: the truth catalog, based on which image simulations are made; the object catalog, where the actual LSST pipeline was run on the simulated images to produce realistic source detections.

In this quick example, one massive cluster is identified from the truth catalog, and is matched to the object catalog to identify the blends. In comparison, a patch of sky that contains only field galaxies is also analyzed in the same way. Fig. 4.1 shows the footprint of data used in this example. Each data point is a galaxy in the truth catalog, whose color represents its dark matter halo mass. The black data points all have a halo mass of $\sim 10^{15}$ solar masses, therefore they are all cluster member galaxies surrounded by the same dark matter halo (the halo of the cluster). The rest green/white points are galaxies with smaller halo mass. These are galaxies surrounded by their own sub-halos and they do not belong to any galaxy cluster. Two patches of sky are selected to represent a typical cluster region and a field galaxy region, as shown in the red/green box in Fig. 4.1. The green box is larger in size to compensate the lower number density of sources. Then, all sources in the detection catalog that reside within the boxes are matched to the truth catalog for a blend identification, following the two-round matching algorithm explained in the Sect. 3.3.4. We then compare the photometric redshift estimates with the true redshift for the two patches, as shown in Fig. 4.2. The summary statistics are shown in Table 4.1. As a conclusion, in this quick example, we can already see that the cluster patch has more blended sources than the field patch, and the

Figure 4.1: Truth catalog footprint of the subset in DC2 simulation used in this work. The color scale shows halo mass of each galaxy.

Table 4.1: Matching between the detection catalog and the truth catalog to identify unrecognized blends.

	total Sources	unrec-blends/total	Pz-outlier/BL
Field Patch	1494	4.7%	16%
Cluster Patch	1416	7.7%	23%

blended sources in the cluster patch tend to have more photometric outliers. The jupyter notebook for the plots is attached in App .6.

4.3 Future Plans

In astronomy, when matching between two catalogs, the most commonly used algorithm is to match sources by angular distances. There is a general concern in the application of such algorithms to the detection of blends, as the shapes and sizes of galaxies should also be considered. Fig. 4.3 shows such a situation, where a detected source (shown in red) is matched to two truth sources (shown in blue) within a certain distance thus it is regarded as a blend. However, if we consider the sizes and shapes of the sources, it is obvious that the two sources are well separated (the secondary match is missing from detection, though). Therefore, it is beneficial to add the shape information in the matching algo-

Figure 4.2: Comparing photometric redshifts to the truth redshifts in DC2 simulation for the cluster and field patch.

rithm. The next step of this project is to implement such an algorithm for matching ellipses. In future studies, this algorithm will be applied to the DC2 catalogs for a comparison with the distance-only matching, and to quantify the impact on blends/photo-z. A demonstration jupyter notebook is attached in App .7.

The final goal of this project is to quantify the impact of blends on photo-z in cluster fields. It will be a similar analysis as in Sect. 4.2, but applied to a catalog of all galaxy clusters in DC2 simulation with realistic cluster finding pipelines. My collaborators in the DESC cluster working group has been working to deliver the cluster detection on DC2 [the red-sequence matched-filter Probabilistic Percolation, RedMapper; the Wavelet Z Photometric, WaZP 126, 127]. The cluster working group has also been collaborating with the photometric redshift working group in DESC to produce realistic photo-z estimates on clusters. These data products will be utilized for this project.

Figure 4.3: Illustration of matching galaxy blends by shapes.

Chapter 5

Summary and Future Plans

Weak gravitational lensing is a powerful probe for structure growth, and thus is an essential tool for testing cosmological models beyond Λ CDM. Weak lensing requires two basic measurements: shape (shear) of galaxies, and redshift of them. Due to the sheer amount of sources needed and planned for lensing surveys, the redshift measurements are only accessible through multi-band photometry (photo-z). This thesis consists of three projects motivated by the photo-z requirements of Rubin-LSST. However, the projects have applications beyond photo-z or Rubin data analysis.

5.1 Project 1: u -band photometry

u -band is the bluest optical band accessible from ground. u -band measurements are important to photo-z estimation, as it is able to break the high- and low- redshift degeneracy through the Lyman- α feature of galaxy spectral energy distribution (SED). However, u -band is usually the most difficult band to calibrate due to the steep cut-off in atmospheric transmission.

In this project, we propose a new method to calibrate the u -band imaging. This method utilizes the main sequence turn offs (MSTOs) in the stellar halo of the Milky Way. Upon validation on a set of deep u -band imaging data sets, we find that this method delivers a photometric precision of ≤ 0.02 for the u -band. Thus this method satisfies the LSST designed photometry requirement.

This method will be applied to the Rubin-LSST commissioning data for another in-depth test, and has the chance to be eventually incorporated into the photometry pipeline of LSST. On the other hand, in addition to data calibration, some tools developed for the u -band project can also be used for interesting science. For example, as the LSST detection limit is significantly deeper than previous surveys, it will enable unprecedented exploration of the

Milky Way stellar halo. By measuring the magnitude dependence of the colors of MSTOs, one can trace the metallicity gradient deep into the stellar halo, allowing the study of star formation history and halo evolution. Previous work [128] shows that the inner halo is dominated by stars that are likely remnants of a dwarf galaxy accreted onto the Milky Way (the Gaia-Enceladus-Sausage). It is then of great interest to explore the properties of stars in the outer halo, and seek their origin.

5.2 Project 2 and 3: Galaxy Blends

Blending of galaxies is a major difficulty for weak lensing, as it impacts both the shape measurements and the redshift estimation. Of particular concern are the unrecognized blends, where two or more sources are too close to be individually identified in ground-based data.

In project 2, we develop a method to detect unrecognized blends with a machine learning algorithm (Self Organizing Map; SOM) based only on the broad-band magnitudes from ground observations. We assemble a test data set mimicking the Rubin + Euclid observation, based on which we test the detection algorithm. We find that the method can detect and remove 14.74% to 67.75% of the unrecognized blends at the cost of 7.50% to 48.76% of all sources, depending on the desired purity of the resulting sample.

In project 3, we aim to demonstrate that the blending situation is worse in galaxy clusters, where the number density of galaxies is typically higher than field galaxies. As a quick example, we identify a cluster patch and a field patch on a set of simulation data (the Data Challenge 2 from DESC), and perform a similar analysis as in project 2 to qualify the blending situation. We find a higher blending rate for the cluster patch (7.7% vs. 4.7%), and a higher photo-z outlier rate for the blended sources in the cluster (23% vs. 16%).

Looking forward, some more efforts are needed to finish project 3, and there are plenty of possible projects to conduct based on project 2 and 3:

1. to extend the analysis of cluster blending to the Rubin commissioning data;
2. to test deblending algorithms/pipeline on DC2 and the Rubin commissioning data;
3. to try different novel machine learning techniques for the blends detection;
4. to study the impact of the un-recognized blends on cosmology inference.

In addition to the DC2 simulation, the Rubin commissioning data provides opportunities to study the galaxy blends. The Rubin Observatory is now in an

exciting phase of integration and commissioning and will become operational in 2024. The commissioning observation will target the COSMOS field and some cluster fields which already have HST coverage, making it possible to test (de)blending in realistic imaging. I am part of a commissioning working group that plans to stress-test the Rubin deblender [scarlet 97] during commissioning. This work will ensure that the deblender be adjusted to work well in both the general field and in dense regions such as clusters, and that possible critical failure modes be fixed early. As an extension of my project 3, it will be interesting to study the impact of blends on photometric redshift on this data set in addition to DC2 simulations. I will also work with our collaborators to produce the first Rubin weak lensing mass map for galaxy clusters. On the other hand, Carrasco Kind and Brunner [129] have shown that prediction trees and random forests are powerful methods for predicting photometric redshift and are robust in identifying outliers. It is therefore interesting to study the usage of a boosted random forest for the blends detection in parallel with project 2. Other methods like Support-Vector Machines and neural network are possible considerations too.

Bibliography

- [1] A. Friedmann. Über die Krümmung des Raumes. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 10:377–386, January 1922. doi: 10.1007/BF01332580.
- [2] F. Zwicky. On the Masses of Nebulae and of Clusters of Nebulae. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 86:217, October 1937. doi: 10.1086/143864.
- [3] Vera C Rubin, W Kent Ford Jr, and Norbert Thonnard. Rotational properties of 21 sc galaxies with a large range of luminosities and radii, from ngc 4605/r= 4kpc/to ugc 2885/r= 122 kpc. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 238:471–487, 1980.
- [4] D. Walsh, R. F. Carswell, and R. J. Weymann. 0957+561 A, B: twin quasistellar objects or gravitational lens? *Nature*, 279:381–384, May 1979. doi: 10.1038/279381a0.
- [5] H. C. van de Hulst, E. Raimond, and H. van Woerden. Rotation and density distribution of the Andromeda nebula derived from observations of the 21-cm line. *Bulletin of the Astronomical Institutes of the Netherlands*, 14:1, November 1957.
- [6] J. H. Oort. Some Problems Concerning the Structure and Dynamics of the Galactic System and the Elliptical Nebulae NGC 3115 and 4494. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 91:273, April 1940. doi: 10.1086/144167.
- [7] Douglas Clowe, Anthony Gonzalez, and Maxim Markevitch. Weak-Lensing Mass Reconstruction of the Interacting Cluster 1E 0657-558: Direct Evidence for the Existence of Dark Matter. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 604(2):596–603, April 2004. doi: 10.1086/381970.
- [8] M. Markevitch, A. H. Gonzalez, D. Clowe, A. Vikhlinin, W. Forman, C. Jones, S. Murray, and W. Tucker. Direct Constraints on the Dark Matter Self-Interaction Cross Section from the Merging Galaxy Cluster 1E 0657-56. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 606(2):819–824, May 2004. doi: 10.1086/383178.

- [9] Planck Collaboration et al. Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters. *A&A*, 641:A6, September 2020. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201833910.
- [10] E. P. Hubble. Extragalactic nebulae. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 64: 321–369, December 1926. doi: 10.1086/143018.
- [11] Edwin Hubble. A Relation between Distance and Radial Velocity among Extra-Galactic Nebulae. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science*, 15(3):168–173, March 1929. doi: 10.1073/pnas.15.3.168.
- [12] Adam G. Riess, Alexei V. Filippenko, Peter Challis, Alejandro Clocchiatti, Alan Diercks, Peter M. Garnavich, Ron L. Gilliland, Craig J. Hogan, Saurabh Jha, Robert P. Kirshner, B. Leibundgut, M. M. Phillips, David Reiss, Brian P. Schmidt, Robert A. Schommer, R. Chris Smith, J. Spyromilio, Christopher Stubbs, Nicholas B. Suntzeff, and John Tonry. Observational Evidence from Supernovae for an Accelerating Universe and a Cosmological Constant. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 116(3):1009–1038, September 1998. doi: 10.1086/300499.
- [13] S. Perlmutter, G. Aldering, G. Goldhaber, R. A. Knop, P. Nugent, P. G. Castro, S. Deustua, S. Fabbro, A. Goobar, D. E. Groom, I. M. Hook, A. G. Kim, M. Y. Kim, J. C. Lee, N. J. Nunes, R. Pain, C. R. Pennyacker, R. Quimby, C. Lidman, R. S. Ellis, M. Irwin, R. G. McMahon, P. Ruiz-Lapuente, N. Walton, B. Schaefer, B. J. Boyle, A. V. Filippenko, T. Matheson, A. S. Fruchter, N. Panagia, H. J. M. Newberg, W. J. Couch, and The Supernova Cosmology Project. Measurements of Ω and Λ from 42 High-Redshift Supernovae. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 517(2):565–586, June 1999. doi: 10.1086/307221.
- [14] C. Krishnan, R. Mohayaee, E. Ó. Colgáin, M. M. Sheikh-Jabbari, and L. Yin. Does Hubble tension signal a breakdown in FLRW cosmology? *Classical and Quantum Gravity*, 38(18):184001, September 2021. doi: 10.1088/1361-6382/ac1a81.
- [15] Elcio Abdalla et al. Cosmology Intertwined: A Review of the Particle Physics, Astrophysics, and Cosmology Associated with the Cosmological Tensions and Anomalies. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:2203.06142, March 2022.
- [16] W. J. G. de Blok. The Core-Cusp Problem. *Advances in Astronomy*, 2010:789293, January 2010. doi: 10.1155/2010/789293.

- [17] G. Gentile, P. Salucci, U. Klein, D. Vergani, and P. Kalberla. The cored distribution of dark matter in spiral galaxies. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 351(3):903–922, July 2004. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2966.2004.07836.x.
- [18] Anatoly Klypin, Andrey V. Kravtsov, Octavio Valenzuela, and Francisco Prada. Where Are the Missing Galactic Satellites? *The Astrophysical Journal*, 522(1):82–92, September 1999. doi: 10.1086/307643.
- [19] Marcel S. Pawlowski, Benoit Famaey, Helmut Jerjen, David Merritt, Pavel Kroupa, Jörg Dabringhausen, Fabian Lüghausen, Duncan A. Forbes, Gerhard Hensler, François Hammer, Mathieu Puech, Sylvain Fouquet, Hector Flores, and Yanbin Yang. Co-orbiting satellite galaxy structures are still in conflict with the distribution of primordial dwarf galaxies. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 442(3):2362–2380, August 2014. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stu1005.
- [20] Adam G. Riess, Wenlong Yuan, Lucas M. Macri, Dan Scolnic, Dillon Brout, Stefano Casertano, David O. Jones, Yukei Murakami, Louise Breuval, Thomas G. Brink, Alexei V. Filippenko, Samantha Hoffmann, Saurabh W. Jha, W. D’arcy Kenworthy, John Mackenty, Benjamin E. Stahl, and Weikang Zheng. A Comprehensive Measurement of the Local Value of the Hubble Constant with 1 km/s/Mpc Uncertainty from the Hubble Space Telescope and the SH0ES Team. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:2112.04510, December 2021.
- [21] Wendy L. Freedman, Barry F. Madore, Dylan Hatt, Taylor J. Hoyt, In Sung Jang, Rachael L. Beaton, Christopher R. Burns, Myung Gyoon Lee, Andrew J. Monson, Jillian R. Neeley, M. M. Phillips, Jeffrey A. Rich, and Mark Seibert. The Carnegie-Chicago Hubble Program. VIII. An Independent Determination of the Hubble Constant Based on the Tip of the Red Giant Branch. *ApJ*, 882(1):34, September 2019. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/ab2f73.
- [22] Catherine Heymans, Tilman Tröster, Marika Asgari, Chris Blake, Hendrik Hildebrandt, Benjamin Joachimi, Konrad Kuijken, Chieh-An Lin, Ariel G. Sánchez, Jan Luca van den Busch, Angus H. Wright, Alexandra Amon, Maciej Bilicki, Jelte de Jong, Martin Crocce, Andrej Dvornik, Thomas Erben, Maria Cristina Fortuna, Fedor Getman, Benjamin Giblin, Karl Glazebrook, Henk Hoekstra, Shahab Joudaki, Arun Kannawadi, Fabian Köhlinger, Chris Lidman, Lance Miller, Nicola R. Napolitano, David Parkinson, Peter Schneider, HuanYuan Shan, Edwin A. Valentijn, Gijs Verdoes Kleijn, and Christian Wolf. KiDS-1000

- Cosmology: Multi-probe weak gravitational lensing and spectroscopic galaxy clustering constraints. *A&A*, 646:A140, February 2021. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/202039063.
- [23] Scott Dodelson, Katrin Heitmann, Chris Hirata, Klaus Honscheid, Aaron Roodman, Uroš Seljak, Anže Slosar, and Mark Trodden. Cosmic Visions Dark Energy: Science. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1604.07626, April 2016.
- [24] Ivezić et al. LSST: From Science Drivers to Reference Design and Anticipated Data Products. *ApJ*, 873(2):111, March 2019. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/ab042c.
- [25] M. Bartelmann and P. Schneider. Weak gravitational lensing. *Phys. Rep.*, 340(4-5):291–472, January 2001. doi: 10.1016/S0370-1573(00)00082-X.
- [26] Jelte T. A. de Jong, Gijs A. Verdoes Kleijn, Konrad H. Kuijken, and Edwin A. Valentijn. The Kilo-Degree Survey. *Experimental Astronomy*, 35(1-2):25–44, January 2013. doi: 10.1007/s10686-012-9306-1.
- [27] The Dark Energy Survey Collaboration. The Dark Energy Survey. *arXiv e-prints*, art. astro-ph/0510346, October 2005.
- [28] Hiroaki Aihara et al. The Hyper Suprime-Cam SSP Survey: Overview and survey design. *PASJ*, 70:S4, January 2018. doi: 10.1093/pasj/psx066.
- [29] R. Laureijs et al. Euclid Definition Study Report. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1110.3193, October 2011.
- [30] D. Spergel et al. Wide-Field Infrared Survey Telescope-Astrophysics Focused Telescope Assets WFIRST-AFTA 2015 Report. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1503.03757, March 2015.
- [31] Sarah Bridle et al. Handbook for the GREAT08 Challenge: An image analysis competition for cosmological lensing. *Annals of Applied Statistics*, 3:6–37, January 2009. doi: 10.1214/08-AOAS222.
- [32] Carlos E. Cunha, Dragan Huterer, Huan Lin, Michael T. Busha, and Risa H. Wechsler. Spectroscopic failures in photometric redshift calibration: cosmological biases and survey requirements. *MNRAS*, 444(1):129–146, October 2014. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stu1424.

- [33] H. Hildebrandt et al. KiDS+VIKING-450: Cosmic shear tomography with optical+infrared data. *A&A*, 633:A69, January 2020. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201834878.
- [34] Regression: Photometric redshifts of galaxies. <https://ogrisel.github.io/scikit-learn.org/sklearn-tutorial/tutorial/astronomy/regression.html>, 2011. Accessed: 2022-04-28.
- [35] J. B. Oke and J. E. Gunn. Secondary standard stars for absolute spectrophotometry. *ApJ*, 266:713–717, March 1983. doi: 10.1086/160817.
- [36] Charles C. Steidel, Mauro Giavalisco, Max Pettini, Mark Dickinson, and Kurt L. Adelberger. Spectroscopic Confirmation of a Population of Normal Star-forming Galaxies at Redshifts $Z > 3$. *ApJ*, 462:L17, May 1996. doi: 10.1086/310029.
- [37] S. Schmidt. DC2-era PZ/Blending Assessment Project(s). Presented at the 2019 DESC meeting: Berkeley, 2019.
- [38] Steven W. Allen, August E. Evrard, and Adam B. Mantz. Cosmological Parameters from Observations of Galaxy Clusters. *ARA&A*, 49(1):409–470, September 2011. doi: 10.1146/annurev-astro-081710-102514.
- [39] Deokkeun An, Timothy C. Beers, Jennifer A. Johnson, Marc H. Pinsonneault, Young Sun Lee, Jo Bovy, Željko Ivezić, Daniela Carollo, and Matthew Newby. THE STELLAR METALLICITY DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION OF THE GALACTIC HALO FROM SDSS PHOTOMETRY. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 763(1):65, jan 2013. doi: 10.1088/0004-637x/763/1/65. URL <https://doi.org/10.1088%2F0004-637x%2F763%2F1%2F65>.
- [40] Matthew Prescott, Ivan K. Baldry, and Phil A. James. Evolution of the u-band luminosity function from redshift 1.2 to 0. *MNRAS*, 397(1): 90–102, July 2009. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.14859.x.
- [41] Ž. Ivezić, R. H. Lupton, S. Anderson, L. Eyer, J. E. Gunn, M. Jurić, G. R. Knapp, G. Miknaitis, J. E. Gunn, C. M. Rockosi, D. Schlegel, M. A. Strauss, C. Stubbs, and D. E. Vanden Berk. Variability Studies with SDSS. *Mem. Soc. Astron. Italiana*, 74:978, January 2003.
- [42] Tian-Wen Cao, Ming Yang, Hong Wu, Tian-Meng Zhang, Jian-Rong Shi, Hao-Tong Zhang, Fan Yang, Jing-Kun Zhao, Xu Zhou, Zhou Fan, Zhao-Ji Jiang, Jun Ma, Jia-Li Wang, Zhen-Yu Wu, Hu Zou, Zhi-Min Zhou,

- Jun-Dan Nie, A. Li Luo, Xue-Bing Wu, and Yong-Heng Zhao. Spectral identification of the u-band variable sources in two LAMOST fields. *Ap&SS*, 361(9):293, September 2016. doi: 10.1007/s10509-016-2883-0.
- [43] Marcin Sawicki, Stephane Arnouts, Jiasheng Huang, Jean Coupon, Anneya Golob, Stephen Gwyn, Sebastien Foucaud, Thibaud Moutard, Ikuru Iwata, Chengze Liu, Lingjian Chen, Guillaume Desprez, Yuichi Harikane, Yoshiaki Ono, Michael A. Strauss, Masayuki Tanaka, Nathalie Thibert, Michael Balogh, Kevin Bundy, Scott Chapman, James E. Gunn, Bau-Ching Hsieh, Olivier Ilbert, Yipeng Jing, Olivier LeFèvre, Cheng Li, Yuichi Matsuda, Satoshi Miyazaki, Tohru Nagao, Atsushi J. Nishizawa, Masami Ouchi, Kazuhiro Shimasaku, John Silverman, Sylvain de la Torre, Laurence Tresse, Wei-Hao Wang, Chris J. Willott, Toru Yamada, Xiaohu Yang, and Howard K. C. Yee. The CFHT large area U-band deep survey (CLAUDS). *MNRAS*, 489(4):5202–5217, Nov 2019. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stz2522.
- [44] David Jewitt, Nuno Peixinho, and Henry H. Hsieh. U-Band Photometry of Kuiper Belt Objects. *AJ*, 134(5):2046–2053, Nov 2007. doi: 10.1086/522787.
- [45] M. R. Blanton, M. A. Bershad, B. Abolfathi, F. D. Albareti, C. Allende Prieto, A. Almeida, J. Alonso-García, F. Anders, S. F. Anderson, B. Andrews, and et al. Sloan Digital Sky Survey IV: Mapping the Milky Way, Nearby Galaxies, and the Distant Universe. *AJ*, 154:28, July 2017. doi: 10.3847/1538-3881/aa7567.
- [46] D. S. Aguado et al. The Fifteenth Data Release of the Sloan Digital Sky Surveys: First Release of MaNGA-derived Quantities, Data Visualization Tools, and Stellar Library. *ApJS*, 240(2):23, February 2019. doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/aaf651.
- [47] N. Padmanabhan, D. J. Schlegel, D. P. Finkbeiner, J. C. Barentine, M. R. Blanton, H. J. Brewington, J. E. Gunn, M. Harvanek, D. W. Hogg, Ž. Ivezić, D. Johnston, S. M. Kent, S. J. Kleinman, G. R. Knapp, J. Krzesinski, D. Long, E. H. Nielsen, Jr., A. Nitta, C. Loomis, R. H. Lupton, S. Roweis, S. A. Snedden, M. A. Strauss, and D. L. Tucker. An Improved Photometric Calibration of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey Imaging Data. *ApJ*, 674:1217–1233, February 2008. doi: 10.1086/524677.
- [48] D. P. Finkbeiner, E. F. Schlafly, D. J. Schlegel, N. Padmanabhan, M. Jurić, W. S. Burgett, K. C. Chambers, L. Denneau, P. W. Draper, H. Flewelling, K. W. Hodapp, N. Kaiser, E. A. Magnier, N. Metcalfe,

- J. S. Morgan, P. A. Price, C. W. Stubbs, and J. L. Tonry. Hypercalibration: A Pan-STARRS1-based Recalibration of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey Photometry. *ApJ*, 822:66, May 2016. doi: 10.3847/0004-637X/822/2/66.
- [49] C. Wolf, C. A. Onken, L. C. Luvaul, B. P. Schmidt, M. S. Bessell, S.-W. Chang, G. S. Da Costa, D. Mackey, T. Martin-Jones, S. J. Murphy, T. Preston, R. A. Scalzo, L. Shao, J. Smillie, P. Tisserand, M. C. White, and F. Yuan. SkyMapper Southern Survey: First Data Release (DR1). *PASA*, 35:e010, February 2018. doi: 10.1017/pasa.2018.5.
- [50] T. Shanks, N. Metcalfe, B. Chehade, J. R. Findlay, M. J. Irwin, E. Gonzalez-Solares, J. R. Lewis, A. K. Yoldas, R. G. Mann, M. A. Read, E. T. W. Sutorius, and S. Voutsinas. The VLT Survey Telescope ATLAS. *MNRAS*, 451:4238–4252, August 2015. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stv1130.
- [51] K. Kuijken, C. Heymans, A. Dvornik, H. Hildebrandt, J. T. A. de Jong, A. H. Wright, T. Erben, M. Bilicki, B. Giblin, H.-Y. Shan, F. Getman, A. Grado, H. Hoekstra, L. Miller, N. Napolitano, M. Paolilo, M. Radovich, P. Schneider, W. Sutherland, M. Tewes, C. Tortora, E. A. Valentijn, and G. A. Verdoes Kleijn. The fourth data release of the Kilo-Degree Survey: ugri imaging and nine-band optical-IR photometry over 1000 square degrees. *arXiv 1902.11265*, February 2019.
- [52] K. R. Covey, Ž. Ivezić, D. Schlegel, D. Finkbeiner, N. Padmanabhan, R. H. Lupton, M. A. Agüeros, J. J. Bochanski, S. L. Hawley, A. A. West, A. Seth, A. Kimball, S. M. Gogarten, M. Claire, D. Haggard, N. Kaib, D. P. Schneider, and B. Sesar. Stellar SEDs from 0.3 to 2.5 μm : Tracing the Stellar Locus and Searching for Color Outliers in the SDSS and 2MASS. *AJ*, 134:2398–2417, December 2007. doi: 10.1086/522052.
- [53] F. W. High, C. W. Stubbs, A. Rest, B. Stalder, and P. Challis. Stellar Locus Regression: Accurate Color Calibration and the Real-Time Determination of Galaxy Cluster Photometric Redshifts. *AJ*, 138:110–129, July 2009. doi: 10.1088/0004-6256/138/1/110.
- [54] P. L. Kelly, A. von der Linden, D. E. Applegate, M. T. Allen, S. W. Allen, P. R. Burchat, D. L. Burke, H. Ebeling, P. Capak, O. Czoske, D. Donovan, A. Mantz, and R. G. Morris. Weighing the Giants - II. Improved calibration of photometry from stellar colours and accurate photometric redshifts. *MNRAS*, 439:28–47, March 2014. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stt1946.

- [55] I. Sevilla-Noarbe et al. and DES Collaboration. Dark Energy Survey Year 3 Results: Photometric Data Set for Cosmology. *ApJS*, 254(2):24, June 2021. doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/abeb66.
- [56] E. F. Schlafly, D. P. Finkbeiner, D. J. Schlegel, M. Jurić, Ž. Ivezić, R. R. Gibson, G. R. Knapp, and B. A. Weaver. The Blue Tip of the Stellar Locus: Measuring Reddening with the Sloan Digital Sky Survey. *ApJ*, 725:1175–1191, December 2010. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/725/1/1175.
- [57] J. L. Tonry, L. Denneau, H. Flewelling, A. N. Heinze, C. A. Onken, S. J. Smartt, B. Stalder, H. J. Weiland, and C. Wolf. The ATLAS All-Sky Stellar Reference Catalog. *ApJ*, 867(2):105, November 2018. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/aae386.
- [58] David L. Nidever, Arjun Dey, Katie Fasbender, Stéphanie Juneau, Aaron M. Meisner, Joseph Wishart, Adam Scott, Kyle Matt, Robert Nikutta, and Ragadeepika Pucha. Second Data Release of the All-sky NOIRLab Source Catalog. *AJ*, 161(4):192, April 2021. doi: 10.3847/1538-3881/abd6e1.
- [59] K. C. Chambers et al. The Pan-STARRS1 Surveys. *ArXiv e-prints*, December 2016.
- [60] J. B. Oke and J. E. Gunn. Secondary standard stars for absolute spectrophotometry. *ApJ*, 266:713–717, March 1983. doi: 10.1086/160817.
- [61] D. J. Schlegel, D. P. Finkbeiner, and M. Davis. Maps of Dust Infrared Emission for Use in Estimation of Reddening and Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation Foregrounds. *ApJ*, 500:525–553, June 1998. doi: 10.1086/305772.
- [62] Steven R. Majewski, M. F. Skrutskie, Martin D. Weinberg, and James C. Ostheimer. A Two Micron All Sky Survey View of the Sagittarius Dwarf Galaxy. I. Morphology of the Sagittarius Core and Tidal Arms. *ApJ*, 599(2):1082–1115, Dec 2003. doi: 10.1086/379504.
- [63] Gaia Collaboration. The Gaia mission. *A&A*, 595:A1, November 2016. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201629272.
- [64] K. Kuijken, C. Heymans, H. Hildebrandt, R. Nakajima, T. Erben, J. T. A. de Jong, M. Viola, A. Choi, H. Hoekstra, L. Miller, E. van Uitert, A. Amon, C. Blake, M. Brouwer, A. Buddendiek, I. F. Conti, M. Eriksen, A. Grado, J. Harnois-Déraps, E. Helmich, R. Herbonnet, N. Irisarri, T. Kitching, D. Klaes, F. La Barbera, N. Napolitano, M. Radovich,

- P. Schneider, C. Sifón, G. Sikkema, P. Simon, A. Tudorica, E. Valentijn, G. Verdoes Kleijn, and L. van Waerbeke. Gravitational lensing analysis of the Kilo-Degree Survey. *MNRAS*, 454:3500–3532, December 2015. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stv2140.
- [65] A. A. Henden, M. Templeton, D. Terrell, T. C. Smith, S. Levine, and D. Welch. VizieR Online Data Catalog: AAVSO Photometric All Sky Survey (APASS) DR9 (Henden+, 2016). *VizieR Online Data Catalog*, 2336, January 2016.
- [66] M. F. Skrutskie, R. M. Cutri, R. Stiening, M. D. Weinberg, S. Schneider, J. M. Carpenter, C. Beichman, R. Capps, T. Chester, J. Elias, J. Huchra, J. Liebert, C. Lonsdale, D. G. Monet, S. Price, P. Seitzer, T. Jarrett, J. D. Kirkpatrick, J. E. Gizis, E. Howard, T. Evans, J. Fowler, L. Fullmer, R. Hurt, R. Light, E. L. Kopan, K. A. Marsh, H. L. McCallon, R. Tam, S. Van Dyk, and S. Wheelock. The Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS). *AJ*, 131:1163–1183, February 2006. doi: 10.1086/498708.
- [67] Eugene. A. Magnier, Edward. F. Schlafly, Douglas P. Finkbeiner, J. L. Tonry, B. Goldman, S. Röser, E. Schilbach, S. Casertano, K. C. Chambers, H. A. Flewelling, M. E. Huber, P. A. Price, W. E. Sweeney, C. Z. Waters, L. Denneau, P. W. Draper, K. W. Hodapp, R. Jedicke, N. Kaiser, R. P. Kudritzki, N. Metcalfe, C. W. Stubbs, and R. J. Wainscoat. Pan-STARRS Photometric and Astrometric Calibration. *ApJS*, 251(1):6, November 2020. doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/abb82a.
- [68] E. Høg, C. Fabricius, V. V. Makarov, S. Urban, T. Corbin, G. Wycoff, U. Bastian, P. Schwekendiek, and A. Wicenec. The Tycho-2 catalogue of the 2.5 million brightest stars. *A&A*, 355:L27–L30, March 2000.
- [69] D. Hoffleit and Jr. Warren, W. H. VizieR Online Data Catalog: Bright Star Catalogue, 5th Revised Ed. (Hoffleit+, 1991). *VizieR Online Data Catalog*, art. V/50, November 1995.
- [70] J. L. Tonry, L. Denneau, A. N. Heinze, B. Stalder, K. W. Smith, S. J. Smartt, C. W. Stubbs, H. J. Weiland, and A. Rest. ATLAS: A High-cadence All-sky Survey System. *PASP*, 130(988):064505, June 2018. doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/aabadf.
- [71] Konrad Kuijken. *ESO Phase 3 Data Release Description*, May 2020. Available at <http://www.eso.org/rm/api/v1/public/releaseDescriptions/151>.

- [72] Nigel Metcalfe. Vst atlas dr4 release description, 2020. URL <http://astro.dur.ac.uk/Cosmology/vstatlas/index.php?go=dr4>.
- [73] Isak G. B. Wold, Lalitwadee Kawinwanichakij, Matthew L. Stevans, Steven L. Finkelstein, Casey Papovich, Yaswant Devarakonda, Robin Ciardullo, John Feldmeier, Jonathan Florez, Eric Gawiser, Caryl Gronwall, Shardha Jogee, Jennifer L. Marshall, Sydney Sherman, Heath V. Shipley, Rachel S. Somerville, Francisco Valdes, and Gregory R. Zeimann. The Spitzer-HETDEX Exploratory Large Area Survey. II. The Dark Energy Camera and Spitzer/IRAC Multiwavelength Catalog. *ApJS*, 240(1):5, January 2019. doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/aace85.
- [74] M. Fukugita, T. Ichikawa, J. E. Gunn, M. Doi, K. Shimasaku, and D. P. Schneider. The Sloan Digital Sky Survey Photometric System. *AJ*, 111:1748, April 1996. doi: 10.1086/117915.
- [75] R. C. Bohlin, M. E. Dickinson, and D. Calzetti. Spectrophotometric Standards from the Far-Ultraviolet to the Near-Infrared: STIS and NICMOS Fluxes. *AJ*, 122(4):2118–2128, October 2001. doi: 10.1086/323137.
- [76] J. L. Tonry, C. W. Stubbs, K. R. Lykke, P. Doherty, I. S. Shivvers, W. S. Burgett, K. C. Chambers, K. W. Hodapp, N. Kaiser, R. P. Kudritzki, E. A. Magnier, J. S. Morgan, P. A. Price, and R. J. Wainscoat. The Pan-STARRS1 Photometric System. *ApJ*, 750(2):99, May 2012. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/750/2/99.
- [77] D. Scolnic, S. Casertano, A. Riess, A. Rest, E. Schlafly, R. J. Foley, D. Finkbeiner, C. Tang, W. S. Burgett, K. C. Chambers, P. W. Draper, H. Flewelling, K. W. Hodapp, M. E. Huber, N. Kaiser, R. P. Kudritzki, E. A. Magnier, N. Metcalfe, and C. W. Stubbs. Supercal: Cross-calibration of Multiple Photometric Systems to Improve Cosmological Measurements with Type Ia Supernovae. *ApJ*, 815(2):117, December 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/815/2/117.
- [78] A. J. Pickles. A Stellar Spectral Flux Library: 1150-25000 Å. *PASP*, 110(749):863–878, July 1998. doi: 10.1086/316197.
- [79] Yan-Ping Chen, S. C. Trager, R. F. Peletier, A. Lançon, A. Vazdekis, Ph. Prugniel, D. R. Silva, and A. Gonneau. The X-shooter Spectral Library (XSL). I. DR1: Near-ultraviolet through optical spectra from the first year of the survey. *A&A*, 565:A117, May 2014. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201322505.

- [80] A. Gonneau, M. Lyubenova, A. Lançon, S. C. Trager, R. F. Peletier, A. Arentsen, Y. P. Chen, P. R. T. Coelho, M. Dries, J. Falcón-Barroso, P. Prugniel, P. Sánchez-Blázquez, A. Vazdekis, and K. Verro. The X-shooter Spectral Library (XSL): Data release 2. *A&A*, 634:A133, February 2020. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201936825.
- [81] Ralph C. Bohlin, Karl D. Gordon, and P. E. Tremblay. Techniques and Review of Absolute Flux Calibration from the Ultraviolet to the Mid-Infrared. *PASP*, 126(942):711, August 2014. doi: 10.1086/677655.
- [82] Ralph C. Bohlin, Ivan Hubeny, and Thomas Rauch. New Grids of Pure-hydrogen White Dwarf NLTE Model Atmospheres and the HST/STIS Flux Calibration. *AJ*, 160(1):21, July 2020. doi: 10.3847/1538-3881/ab94b4.
- [83] Ž. Ivezić, B. Sesar, M. Jurić, N. Bond, J. Dalcanton, C. M. Rockosi, B. Yanny, H. J. Newberg, T. C. Beers, C. Allende Prieto, R. Wilhelm, Y. S. Lee, T. Sivarani, J. E. Norris, C. A. L. Bailer-Jones, P. Re Fiorentin, D. Schlegel, A. Uomoto, R. H. Lupton, G. R. Knapp, J. E. Gunn, K. R. Covey, J. Allyn Smith, G. Miknaitis, M. Doi, M. Tanaka, M. Fukugita, S. Kent, D. Finkbeiner, J. A. Munn, J. R. Pier, T. Quinn, S. Hawley, S. Anderson, F. Kiuchi, A. Chen, J. Bushong, H. Sohi, D. Haggard, A. Kimball, J. Barentine, H. Brewington, M. Harvanek, S. Kleinman, J. Krzesinski, D. Long, A. Nitta, S. Snedden, B. Lee, H. Harris, J. Brinkmann, D. P. Schneider, and D. G. York. The Milky Way Tomography with SDSS. II. Stellar Metallicity. *ApJ*, 684:287–325, September 2008. doi: 10.1086/589678.
- [84] Rodrigo A. Ibata et al. Chemical Mapping of the Milky Way with The Canada-France Imaging Survey: A Non-parametric Metallicity-Distance Decomposition of the Galaxy. *ApJ*, 848(2):129, October 2017. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/aa8562.
- [85] Allen Riddell, Ari Hartikainen, and Matthew Carter. *pystan* (3.0.0). PyPI, March 2021.
- [86] Amina Helmi, Carine Babusiaux, Helmer H. Koppelman, Davide Massari, Jovan Veljanoski, and Anthony G. A. Brown. The merger that led to the formation of the Milky Way’s inner stellar halo and thick disk. *Nature*, 563(7729):85–88, Oct 2018. doi: 10.1038/s41586-018-0625-x.
- [87] Vasily Belokurov, Jason L. Sanders, Azadeh Fattahi, Martin C. Smith, Alis J. Deason, N. Wyn Evans, and Robert J. J. Grand. The Biggest Splash. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1909.04679, Sep 2019.

- [88] Robyn E. Sanderson, Johanna Hartke, and Amina Helmi. Modeling the Gravitational Potential of a Cosmological Dark Matter Halo with Stellar Streams. *ApJ*, 836(2):234, Feb 2017. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/aa5eb4.
- [89] T. Shanks. *ESO Phase 3 Data Release Description*, May 2019. Available at <http://www.eso.org/rm/api/v1/public/releaseDescriptions/131>.
- [90] A. J. Cenarro et al. J-PLUS: The Javalambre Photometric Local Universe Survey. *A&A*, 622:A176, February 2019. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201833036.
- [91] C. López-Sanjuan, H. Yuan, H. Vázquez Ramió, J. Varela, D. Cristóbal-Hornillos, P. E. Tremblay, A. Marín-Franch, A. J. Cenarro, A. Ederoclite, E. J. Alfaro, A. Alvarez-Candal, S. Daflon, A. Hernán-Caballero, C. Hernández-Monteagudo, F. M. Jiménez-Esteban, V. M. Placco, E. Tempel, J. Alcaniz, R. E. Angulo, R. A. Dupke, M. Moles, and Jr Sodre, L. J-PLUS: Systematic impact of metallicity on photometric calibration with the stellar locus. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:2101.12407, January 2021.
- [92] Catherine Heymans, Tilman Troster, Marika Asgari, Chris Blake, Hendrik Hildebrandt, Benjamin Joachimi, Konrad Kuijken, Chieh-An Lin, Ariel G. Sanchez, Jan Luca van den Busch, Angus H. Wright, Alexandra Amon, Maciej Bilicki, Jelte de Jong, Martin Crocce, Andrej Dvornik, Thomas Erben, Maria Cristina Fortuna, Fedor Getman, Benjamin Giblin, Karl Glazebrook, Henk Hoekstra, Shahab Joudaki, Arun Kannawadi, Fabian Kohlner, Chris Lidman, Lance Miller, Nicola R. Napolitano, David Parkinson, Peter Schneider, HuanYuan Shan, Edwin A. Valentijn, Gijs Verdoes Kleijn, and Christian Wolf. KiDS-1000 Cosmology: Multi-probe weak gravitational lensing and spectroscopic galaxy clustering constraints. *A&A*, 646:A140, February 2021. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/202039063.
- [93] H. Hildebrandt, J. L. van den Busch, A. H. Wright, C. Blake, B. Joachimi, K. Kuijken, T. Troster, M. Asgari, M. Bilicki, J. T. A. de Jong, A. Dvornik, T. Erben, F. Getman, B. Giblin, C. Heymans, A. Kannawadi, C. A. Lin, and H. Y. Shan. KiDS-1000 catalogue: Redshift distributions and their calibration. *A&A*, 647:A124, March 2021. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/202039018.
- [94] D. L. Burke et al. and DES Collaboration. Forward Global Photometric

- Calibration of the Dark Energy Survey. *AJ*, 155(1):41, January 2018. doi: 10.3847/1538-3881/aa9f22.
- [95] Dark Energy Survey Collaboration. The Dark Energy Survey: more than dark energy - an overview. *MNRAS*, 460(2):1270–1299, August 2016. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stw641.
- [96] Javier Sanchez, Ismael Mendoza, David P. Kirkby, Patricia R. Burchat, and LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration. Effects of overlapping sources on cosmic shear estimation: Statistical sensitivity and pixel-noise bias. *J. Cosmology Astropart. Phys.*, 2021(7):043, July 2021. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2021/07/043.
- [97] P. Melchior, F. Moolekamp, M. Jerdee, R. Armstrong, A. L. Sun, J. Bosch, and R. Lupton. SCARLET: Source separation in multi-band images by Constrained Matrix Factorization. *Astronomy and Computing*, 24:129, July 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.ascom.2018.07.001.
- [98] William A. Dawson, Michael D. Schneider, J. Anthony Tyson, and M. James Jee. The Ellipticity Distribution of Ambiguously Blended Objects. *ApJ*, 816(1):11, January 2016. doi: 10.3847/0004-637X/816/1/11.
- [99] N. MacCrann et al. and DES Collaboration. Dark Energy Survey Y3 results: blending shear and redshift biases in image simulations. *MNRAS*, 509(3):3371–3394, January 2022. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stab2870.
- [100] Rachel Mandelbaum. Weak Lensing for Precision Cosmology. *ARA&A*, 56:393–433, September 2018. doi: 10.1146/annurev-astro-081817-051928.
- [101] Erfan Nourbakhsh, J. Anthony Tyson, Samuel J. Schmidt, and The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration. Galaxy blending effects in deep imaging cosmic shear probes of cosmology. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:2112.07659, December 2021.
- [102] Teuvo Kohonen. The self-organizing map. *Neurocomputing*, 21(1):1–6, 1998. ISSN 0925-2312. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-2312\(98\)00030-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-2312(98)00030-7). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925231298000307>.
- [103] Matias Carrasco Kind and Robert J. Brunner. SOMz: photometric redshift PDFs with self-organizing maps and random atlas. *MNRAS*, 438(4):3409–3421, March 2014. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stt2456.

- [104] Daniel Masters, Peter Capak, Daniel Stern, Olivier Ilbert, Mara Salvato, Samuel Schmidt, Giuseppe Longo, Jason Rhodes, Stephane Paltani, Bahram Mobasher, Henk Hoekstra, Hendrik Hildebrandt, Jean Coupon, Charles Steinhardt, Josh Speagle, Andreas Faisst, Adam Kalinich, Mark Brodwin, Massimo Brescia, and Stefano Cavuoti. Mapping the Galaxy Color-Redshift Relation: Optimal Photometric Redshift Calibration Strategies for Cosmology Surveys. *ApJ*, 813(1):53, November 2015. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/813/1/53.
- [105] C. Laigle, H. J. McCracken, O. Ilbert, B. C. Hsieh, I. Davidzon, P. Capak, G. Hasinger, J. D. Silverman, C. Pichon, J. Coupon, H. Aussel, D. Le Borgne, K. Caputi, P. Cassata, Y. Y. Chang, F. Civano, J. Dunlop, J. Fynbo, J. S. Kartaltepe, A. Koekemoer, O. Le Fèvre, E. Le Floch, A. Leauthaud, S. Lilly, L. Lin, S. Marchesi, B. Milvang-Jensen, M. Salvato, D. B. Sanders, N. Scoville, V. Smolcic, M. Stockmann, Y. Taniguchi, L. Tasca, S. Toft, Mattia Vaccari, and J. Zabl. The COSMOS2015 Catalog: Exploring the $1 < z < 6$ Universe with Half a Million Galaxies. *ApJS*, 224(2):24, June 2016. doi: 10.3847/0067-0049/224/2/24.
- [106] P. Capak, H. Aussel, M. Ajiki, H. J. McCracken, B. Mobasher, N. Scoville, P. Shopbell, Y. Taniguchi, D. Thompson, S. Tribiano, S. Sasaki, A. W. Blain, M. Brusa, C. Carilli, A. Comastri, C. M. Carollo, P. Cassata, J. Colbert, R. S. Ellis, M. Elvis, M. Giavalisco, W. Green, L. Guzzo, G. Hasinger, O. Ilbert, C. Impey, K. Jahnke, J. Kartaltepe, J. P. Kneib, J. Koda, A. Koekemoer, Y. Komiyama, A. Leauthaud, O. Le Fèvre, S. Lilly, C. Liu, R. Massey, S. Miyazaki, T. Murayama, T. Nagao, J. A. Peacock, A. Pickles, C. Porciani, A. Renzini, J. Rhodes, M. Rich, M. Salvato, D. B. Sanders, C. Scarlata, D. Schiminovich, E. Schinnerer, M. Scodreggio, K. Sheth, Y. Shioya, L. A. M. Tasca, J. E. Taylor, L. Yan, and G. Zamorani. The First Release COSMOS Optical and Near-IR Data and Catalog. *ApJS*, 172(1):99–116, September 2007. doi: 10.1086/519081.
- [107] A. M. Koekemoer, H. Aussel, D. Calzetti, P. Capak, M. Giavalisco, J. P. Kneib, A. Leauthaud, O. Le Fèvre, H. J. McCracken, R. Massey, B. Mobasher, J. Rhodes, N. Scoville, and P. L. Shopbell. The COSMOS Survey: Hubble Space Telescope Advanced Camera for Surveys Observations and Data Processing. *ApJS*, 172(1):196–202, September 2007. doi: 10.1086/520086.
- [108] N. Scoville, R. G. Abraham, H. Aussel, J. E. Barnes, A. Benson, A. W.

- Blain, D. Calzetti, A. Comastri, P. Capak, C. Carilli, J. E. Carlstrom, C. M. Carollo, J. Colbert, E. Daddi, R. S. Ellis, M. Elvis, S. P. Ewald, M. Fall, A. Franceschini, M. Giavalisco, W. Green, R. E. Griffiths, L. Guzzo, G. Hasinger, C. Impey, J. P. Kneib, J. Koda, A. Koekemoer, O. Lefevre, S. Lilly, C. T. Liu, H. J. McCracken, R. Massey, Y. Mellier, S. Miyazaki, B. Mobasher, J. Mould, C. Norman, A. Refregier, A. Renzini, J. Rhodes, M. Rich, D. B. Sanders, D. Schiminovich, E. Schinnerer, M. Scodggio, K. Sheth, P. L. Shopbell, Y. Taniguchi, N. D. Tyson, C. M. Urry, L. Van Waerbeke, P. Vettolani, S. D. M. White, and L. Yan. COSMOS: Hubble Space Telescope Observations. *ApJS*, 172(1):38–45, September 2007. doi: 10.1086/516580.
- [109] Robert H. Lupton, James E. Gunn, and Alexander S. Szalay. A Modified Magnitude System that Produces Well-Behaved Magnitudes, Colors, and Errors Even for Low Signal-to-Noise Ratio Measurements. *AJ*, 118(3): 1406–1410, September 1999. doi: 10.1086/301004.
- [110] Simon J. Lilly et al. The zCOSMOS 10k-Bright Spectroscopic Sample. *ApJS*, 184(2):218–229, October 2009. doi: 10.1088/0067-0049/184/2/218.
- [111] C. Knobel et al. The zCOSMOS 20k Group Catalog. *ApJ*, 753(2):121, July 2012. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/753/2/121.
- [112] G. Hasinger, P. Capak, M. Salvato, A. J. Barger, L. L. Cowie, A. Faisst, S. Hemmati, Y. Kakazu, J. Kartaltepe, D. Masters, B. Mobasher, H. Nayyeri, D. Sanders, N. Z. Scoville, H. Suh, C. Steinhardt, and Fengwei Yang. The DEIMOS 10K Spectroscopic Survey Catalog of the COSMOS Field. *ApJ*, 858(2):77, May 2018. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/aabacf.
- [113] Ryan P. Mallery, Bahram Mobasher, Peter Capak, Yuko Kakazu, Dan Masters, Olivier Ilbert, Shoubaneh Hemmati, Claudia Scarlata, Mara Salvato, Henry McCracken, Olivier LeFevre, and Nick Scoville. Ly α Emission from High-redshift Sources in COSMOS. *ApJ*, 760(2):128, December 2012. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/760/2/128.
- [114] Daniel C. Masters, Daniel K. Stern, Judith G. Cohen, Peter L. Capak, Jason D. Rhodes, Francisco J. Castander, and Stéphane Paltani. The Complete Calibration of the Color-Redshift Relation (C3R2) Survey: Survey Overview and Data Release 1. *ApJ*, 841(2):111, June 2017. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/aa6f08.

- [115] Daniel C. Masters, Daniel K. Stern, Judith G. Cohen, Peter L. Capak, S. Adam Stanford, Nina Hernitschek, Audrey Galametz, Iary Davidson, Jason D. Rhodes, Dave Sanders, Bahram Mobasher, Francisco Castander, Kerianne Pruett, and Sotiria Fotopoulou. The Complete Calibration of the Color-Redshift Relation (C3R2) Survey: Analysis and Data Release 2. *ApJ*, 877(2):81, June 2019. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/ab184d.
- [116] S. A. Stanford et al. Euclid Preparation. XIV. The Complete Calibration of the Color-Redshift Relation (C3R2) Survey: Data Release 3. *ApJS*, 256(1):9, September 2021. doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/ac0833.
- [117] O. Le Fèvre et al. The VIMOS Ultra-Deep Survey: $\sim 10\,000$ galaxies with spectroscopic redshifts to study galaxy assembly at early epochs $2 < z < 6$. *A&A*, 576:A79, April 2015. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201423829.
- [118] L. A. M. Tasca, O. Le Fèvre, B. Ribeiro, R. Thomas, C. Moreau, P. Casata, B. Garilli, V. Le Brun, B. C. Lemaux, D. Maccagni, L. Pentericci, D. Schaerer, E. Vanzella, G. Zamorani, E. Zucca, R. Amorin, S. Bardelli, L. P. Cassarà, M. Castellano, A. Cimatti, O. Cucciati, A. Durkalec, A. Fontana, M. Giavalisco, A. Grazian, N. P. Hathi, O. Ilbert, S. Paltani, J. Pforr, M. Scodreggio, V. Sommariva, M. Talia, L. Tresse, D. Vergani, P. Capak, S. Charlot, T. Contini, S. de la Torre, J. Dunlop, S. Fotopoulou, L. Guaita, A. Koekemoer, C. López-Sanjuan, Y. Mellier, M. Salvato, N. Scoville, Y. Taniguchi, and P. W. Wang. The VIMOS Ultra Deep Survey first data release: Spectra and spectroscopic redshifts of 698 objects up to $z_{spec} < 6$ in CANDELS. *A&A*, 600:A110, April 2017. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201527963.
- [119] T. Kohonen. The self-organizing map. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 78(9):1464–1480, 1990. doi: 10.1109/5.58325.
- [120] James E. Geach. Unsupervised self-organized mapping: a versatile empirical tool for object selection, classification and redshift estimation in large surveys. *MNRAS*, 419(3):2633–2645, January 2012. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19913.x.
- [121] R. Buchs et al. and DES Collaboration. Phenotypic redshifts with self-organizing maps: A novel method to characterize redshift distributions of source galaxies for weak lensing. *MNRAS*, 489(1):820–841, October 2019. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stz2162.
- [122] Angus H. Wright, Hendrik Hildebrandt, Jan Luca van den Busch, and Catherine Heymans. Photometric redshift calibration with self-

- organising maps. *A&A*, 637:A100, May 2020. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201936782.
- [123] K. M. Górski, E. Hivon, A. J. Banday, B. D. Wandelt, F. K. Hansen, M. Reinecke, and M. Bartelmann. HEALPix: A Framework for High-Resolution Discretization and Fast Analysis of Data Distributed on the Sphere. *ApJ*, 622:759–771, April 2005. doi: 10.1086/427976.
- [124] Andrea Zonca, Leo Singer, Daniel Lenz, Martin Reinecke, Cyrille Rosset, Eric Hivon, and Krzysztof Gorski. healpy: equal area pixelization and spherical harmonics transforms for data on the sphere in python. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 4(35):1298, March 2019. doi: 10.21105/joss.01298. URL <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01298>.
- [125] LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (LSST DESC). The LSST DESC DC2 Simulated Sky Survey. *ApJS*, 253(1):31, March 2021. doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/abd62c.
- [126] E. S. Rykoff, E. Rozo, M. T. Busha, C. E. Cunha, A. Finoguenov, A. Evrard, J. Hao, B. P. Koester, A. Leauthaud, B. Nord, M. Pierre, R. Reddick, T. Sadibekova, E. S. Sheldon, and R. H. Wechsler. redMaP-Per. I. Algorithm and SDSS DR8 Catalog. *ApJ*, 785(2):104, April 2014. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/785/2/104.
- [127] M. Aguena, C. Benoist, L. N. da Costa, R. L. C. Ogando, J. Gschwend, H. B. Sampaio-Santos, M. Lima, M. A. G. Maia, S. Allam, S. Avila, D. Bacon, E. Bertin, S. Bhargava, D. Brooks, A. Carnero Rosell, M. Carrasco Kind, J. Carretero, M. Costanzi, J. De Vicente, S. Desai, H. T. Diehl, P. Doel, S. Everett, A. E. Evrard, I. Ferrero, A. Ferté, B. Flaugher, P. Fosalba, J. Frieman, J. García-Bellido, P. Giles, R. A. Gruendl, G. Gutierrez, S. R. Hinton, D. L. Hollowood, K. Honscheid, D. J. James, T. Jeltema, K. Kuehn, N. Kuropatkin, O. Lahav, P. Melchior, R. Miquel, R. Morgan, A. Palmese, F. Paz-Chinchón, A. A. Plazas, A. K. Romer, E. Sanchez, B. Santiago, M. Schubnell, S. Serrano, I. Sevilla-Noarbe, M. Smith, M. Soares-Santos, E. Suchyta, G. Tarle, C. To, D. L. Tucker, and R. D. Wilkinson. The WaZP galaxy cluster sample of the dark energy survey year 1. *MNRAS*, 502(3):4435–4456, April 2021. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stab264.
- [128] Alis J. Deason, Vasily Belokurov, Sergey E. Koposov, and Lachlan Lancaster. Apocenter Pile-up: Origin of the Stellar Halo Density Break. *ApJ*, 862(1):L1, July 2018. doi: 10.3847/2041-8213/aad0ee.

- [129] Matias Carrasco Kind and Robert J. Brunner. TPZ: photometric redshift PDFs and ancillary information by using prediction trees and random forests. *MNRAS*, 432(2):1483–1501, June 2013. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stt574.
- [130] R. H. Lupton, J. E. Gunn, and A. S. Szalay. A Modified Magnitude System that Produces Well-Behaved Magnitudes, Colors, and Errors Even for Low Signal-to-Noise Ratio Measurements. *AJ*, 118:1406–1410, September 1999. doi: 10.1086/301004.
- [131] M. B. Taylor. STILTS - A Package for Command-Line Processing of Tabular Data. In C. Gabriel, C. Arviset, D. Ponz, and S. Enrique, editors, *Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XV*, volume 351 of *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*, page 666, July 2006.
- [132] A. Katherina Vivas, Abhijit Saha, Knut Olsen, Robert Blum, Edward W. Olszewski, Jennifer Claver, Francisco Valdes, Tim Axelrod, Catherine Kaleida, Andrea Kunder, Gautham Narayan, Thomas Matheson, and Alistair Walker. Absolute Magnitudes and Colors of RR Lyrae Stars in DECam Passbands from Photometry of the Globular Cluster M5. *AJ*, 154(3):85, September 2017. doi: 10.3847/1538-3881/aa7fed.
- [133] H. A. Flewelling, E. A. Magnier, K. C. Chambers, J. N. Heasley, C. Holmberg, M. E. Huber, W. Sweeney, C. Z. Waters, A. Calamida, S. Casertano, X. Chen, D. Farrow, G. Hasinger, R. Henderson, K. S. Long, N. Metcalfe, G. Narayan, M. A. Nieto-Santisteban, P. Norberg, A. Rest, R. P. Saglia, A. Szalay, A. R. Thakar, J. L. Tonry, J. Valenti, S. Werner, R. White, L. Denneau, P. W. Draper, K. W. Hodapp, R. Jedicke, N. Kaiser, R. P. Kudritzki, P. A. Price, R. J. Wainscoat, S. Chastel, B. McLean, M. Postman, and B. Shiao. The Pan-STARRS1 Database and Data Products. *ApJS*, 251(1):7, November 2020. doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/abb82d.
- [134] Daniel J. Farrow, Shaun Cole, N. Metcalfe, P. W. Draper, Peder Norberg, Sébastien Foucaud, W. S. Burgett, K. C. Chambers, N. Kaiser, R. P. Kudritzki, E. A. Magnier, P. A. Price, J. L. Tonry, and C. Waters. Pan-STARRS1: Galaxy clustering in the Small Area Survey 2. *MNRAS*, 437(1):748–770, January 2014. doi: 10.1093/mnras/stt1933.
- [135] Gregory M. Green, Edward Schlafly, Catherine Zucker, Joshua S. Speagle, and Douglas Finkbeiner. A 3D Dust Map Based on Gaia,

Pan-STARRS 1, and 2MASS. *ApJ*, 887(1):93, December 2019. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/ab5362.

- [136] Edward F. Schlafly and Douglas P. Finkbeiner. Measuring Reddening with Sloan Digital Sky Survey Stellar Spectra and Recalibrating SFD. *ApJ*, 737(2):103, August 2011. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/737/2/103.
- [137] Gaia Collaboration. Gaia Early Data Release 3. Summary of the contents and survey properties. *A&A*, 649:A1, May 2021. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/202039657.

.1 Detailed Data Acquisition

In this section, we provide detailed data queries and selections for the data sets used in this work, as briefly introduced in Sect. 2.3. We also show the selections for SHELA data [73], a DECam data set that is included in NSC but with an independent calibration. SHELA is not used in any of the calibration work, but only to compare its photometry with NSC.

.1.1 SDSS data

We download SDSS data from the SkyServer¹ via a python package `urllib`. SDSS photometry is given in `luptitudes`², as introduced by Lupton et al. [130]. To be consistent with the validation set, we take the SDSS PSF flux density and derive the (Pogson) AB magnitudes [60] and the errors. Let `X` stand for all of the `u`, `g`, `r`, `i` and `z` bands. we calculate

$$\begin{aligned} X_{\text{SDSS}} &= 22.5 - 2.5 \log_{10}(\text{psfFlux}_X) - \text{extinction}_X \\ X_{\text{err}_{\text{SDSS}}} &= 1.085 / \text{sqrt}(\text{psfFluxIvar}_X) / \text{psfFlux}_X. \end{aligned}$$

where `XSDSS`, `XerrSDSS` are the X-band magnitude and the error, `psfFluxX` and `psfFluxIvarX` are the X-band PSF flux density and the inverse variance, and `extinctionX` is the X-band extinction. The flux density is measured in the units of nanomaggies³ which corresponds to a zero-point of 22.5 in magnitude. In addition, the SDSS `u`-band magnitude differs from a perfect AB magnitude by 0.04⁴, so we subtract 0.04 from the magnitude. Similarly, we add 0.02 mags to the `z`-band. We use only the clean photometry identified from SDSS by setting the flag

$$\text{stars.clean} = 1,$$

and we keep only the sources with magnitude of

$$14 < X_{\text{SDSS}} < 21,$$

and the magnitude error < 0.1 in all bands,

$$X_{\text{err}_{\text{SDSS}}} < 0.1.$$

¹<http://skyserver.sdss.org/dr15/en/tools/search/sql.aspx>

²<https://www.sdss.org/dr15/algorithms/magnitudes/#asinh>

³<https://www.sdss.org/dr15/help/glossary/#N>

⁴<https://www.sdss.org/dr13/algorithms/fluxcal/#SDSStoAB>

An example query is as follows:

```

select ra,dec,l,b,\
-2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_u) + 22.5
- extinction_u - 0.04 as psfPogCorr_u,
-2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_g) + 22.5 \
- extinction_g + 0.00 as psfPogCorr_g,
-2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_r) + 22.5 \
- extinction_r + 0.00 as psfPogCorr_r,
-2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_i) + 22.5 \
- extinction_i + 0.00 as psfPogCorr_i,
-2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_z) + 22.5 \
- extinction_z + 0.02 as psfPogCorr_z,
1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_u)/psfFlux_u as psfPogErr_u,
1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_g)/psfFlux_g as psfPogErr_g,
1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_r)/psfFlux_r as psfPogErr_r,
1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_i)/psfFlux_i as psfPogErr_i,
1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_z)/psfFlux_z as psfPogErr_z
from star as s where ra between 0
and 1 and dec between 0 and 1
and s.clean=1
and -2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_u) + 22.5
- extinction_u - 0.04 between 14 and 21
and -2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_g) + 22.5 \
- extinction_g between 14 and 21
and -2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_r) + 22.5 \
- extinction_r between 14 and 21
and -2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_i) + 22.5 \
- extinction_i between 14 and 21
and -2.5*LOG10(psfFlux_z) + 22.5 \
- extinction_z + 0.02 between 14 and 21
and 1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_u)/psfFlux_u < 0.1
and 1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_g)/psfFlux_g < 0.1
and 1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_r)/psfFlux_r < 0.1
and 1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_i)/psfFlux_i < 0.1
and 1.085/SQRT(psfFluxIvar_z)/psfFlux_z < 0.1

```

Notice that some outliers are found in the left panel of Fig. 2.4. Most of them are exposures taken in two specific SDSS runs (4674 and 4678, see Fig. 1). They are excluded from the MCMC fitting.

Figure 1: Sky footprint of some SDSS data used in this work. Each square is a $2 \times 2^\circ$ tile. The red tiles are outliers in the color-latitude relation (Fig. 2.4). They are excluded from the fitting of model (2.6).

.1.2 KiDS data

Kids data are batch-downloaded with the bash script provided on the KiDS Data Release 4 website⁵. We use the KiDS Multi-band catalog (DR4.1 update), and select stars in each tile with high-fidelity photometry by the following criteria: (X stands for all of the *ugri*-bands:

1. **Flag = 0**
Flag is the *r*-band photometric flag from SExtractor⁶. The value 0 means the source detected has good photometric property (not over-exposed, truncated nor blended with nearby sources).
2. **SG2DPHOT = 5**
This is the star-galaxy classification based on *r*-band photometry. The value 5 means the source is a high confidence star candidate.
3. **FLAG_GAaP_X = 0**
The GAaP photometry flag. It is set to 100 when no GAaP flux is measured, otherwise 0 [64].

⁵<https://kids.strw.leidenuniv.nl/DR4/access.php>

⁶<https://www.astromatic.net/software/sextractor>

4. $14 < \text{MAG_GAaP_X} < 21$
We keep sources with magnitude within the range, and
5. $\text{MAGERR_GAaP_X} < 0.1$
magnitude errors smaller than 0.1.

.1.3 ATLAS data

We obtain the ATLAS data via the Freeform Query on the OmegaCAM Science Archive (OSA) website⁷. We apply the following selection criteria per star on ATLAS data (X stands for all of the *ugriz*-bands):

1. $\text{XClass} = -1$
 XClass is the most probable morphological classification in each band with -1=stellar, +1=non-stellar, 0=noise and -2=borderline stellar.
2. $14 < \text{XAperMag3} < 21$
ATLAS has many bright stars that are not needed for our purpose so we exclude them. Note that ATLAS doesn't offer PSF magnitudes. We use XAperMag3 as suggested by Shanks et al. [50].
3. $\text{XAperMag3Err} < 0.1$
We keep only sources with small magnitude errors.

The the extinction is corrected with

$$\text{MAG_X} = \text{XAperMag3} - aX.$$

An example query is shown below:

```
select ra, dec, l, b,
uAperMag3 - aU as u, gAperMag3 - aG as g,
rAperMag3 - aR as r, iAperMag3 - aI as i,
zAperMag3 - aZ as z,
uAperMag3Err as uerr, gAperMag3Err as gerr,
rAperMag3Err as rerr, iAperMag3Err as ierr,
zAperMag3Err as zerr,
from atlasSource where ra between 0 and 62
and uClass=-1 and gClass=-1 and rClass=-1
and iClass=-1 and zClass=-1
and uAperMag3Err < 0.1 and gAperMag3Err < 0.1
and rAperMag3Err < 0.1 and iAperMag3Err < 0.1
```

⁷<http://osa.roe.ac.uk/>

```

and zAperMag3Err < 0.1
and uAperMag3 between 14 and 21
and gAperMag3 between 14 and 21
and rAperMag3 between 14 and 21
and iAperMag3 between 14 and 21
and zAperMag3 between 14 and 21

```

.1.4 NSC data

Since the NSC catalog has limited sources, we use only the *ug*-bands selection to maximize the amount of data. We apply the following cuts:

1. $14 < (\text{umag}, \text{gmag}) < 21$
We keep sources with both magnitudes within the range.
2. $(\text{uerr}, \text{gerr}) < 0.1$
The uncertainty cut on both magnitudes.
3. `flags = 0`
The photometry flags.
4. $1'' < \text{fwhm} < 1.6''$
We select stars with the object size, and
5. `class_star > 0.95`
the star classifier by SExtractor.

We query all stars from `nsc_dr2.object` using STILTS [131], a tool set for STIL (the Starlink Tables Infrastructure Library) via the Table Access Protocol (TAP⁸). Stars are binned according to exposure centers found in `nsc_dr2.exposure`. The bash command that queries all NSC stars for this work is shown below:

```

stilts tapquery \
tapurl='http://datalab.noao.edu/tap' \
adql="SELECT id, ra, dec, glon, glat, \
umag, urms, uerr, gmag, grms, gerr, \
fwhm, class_star, ebv \
FROM nsc_dr2.object where (glat > 30 or glat < -30)
and dec > -30 and flags=0 \
and umag > 14 and umag < 21 and uerr < 0.1 \
and gmag > 14 and gmag < 21 and gerr < 0.1 \
and fwhm>1 and fwhm<1.6 and class_star>0.95" \
out=raw.fits

```

⁸<https://www.ivoa.net/documents/TAP/>

and the bash command for querying the exposure centers is below:

```
stilts tapquery \  
tapurl='http://datalab.noao.edu/tap' \  
adql="SELECT ra, dec, glon, glat, mjd, \  
exposure, exptime, airmass, nmeas, \  
zptype, zpterm, depth10sig \  
FROM nsc_dr2.exposure where filter='u' and \  
(glat > 27 or glat < -27) and dec > -29.7" \  
out=center.fits
```

We correct the reddening with extinction coefficients found in Vivas et al. [132].

.1.5 PanSTARRS data

We use CasJobs to query all PanSTARRS objects that cover as much as possible the KiDS, ATLAS and NSC footprint from table `MeanObject`, and cross-match with table `ObjectThin` for the selection cuts. The cuts are (`X` stands for all of the g , r , i and z bands):

1. $14 < X\text{MeanPSFMag} < 21$
For stars, we use `MeanPSFMag`, the mean PSF magnitude that has the lowest noise [133]⁹. We keep stars in this range for all bands.
2. $-0.2 < i\text{MeanPSFMag} - i\text{MeanKronMag} < 0.05$
We keep objects whose i -band PSF magnitude and Kron Magnitude show moderate differences. This cut serves as an efficient star-galaxy separation [134]¹⁰.
3. $X\text{MeanPSFMagErr} < 0.1$
We keep sources with small magnitude errors.
4. $nX > 0$
 nX is the number of single epoch detections in filter X . We require the object to be detected at least once in each filter.

An example query is shown below:

⁹<https://outerspace.stsci.edu/display/PANSTARRS/PS1+FAQ+-+Frequently+asked+questions#PS1FAQ-Frequentlyaskedquestions-WhichmagnitudesshouldIuse?>

¹⁰<https://outerspace.stsci.edu/display/PANSTARRS/How+to+separate+stars+and+galaxies>

```

select o.raMean as ra, o.decMean as dec,
m.gMeanPSFMag, m.rMeanPSFMag, m.iMeanPSFMag,
m.zMeanPSFMag, m.gMeanPSFMagErr, m.rMeanPSFMagErr,
m.iMeanPSFMagErr, m.zMeanPSFMagErr
into my_database
from fGetObjFromRectEq(322, -30, 360, -9 ) nb
inner join ObjectThin o
on o.objid=nb.objid and o.nDetections>1
and ng > 0 and nr > 0 and ni > 0 and nz > 0
inner join MeanObject m on o.objid=m.objid
and m.gMeanPSFMag > 14 and m.rMeanPSFMag > 14
and m.iMeanPSFMag > 14 and m.zMeanPSFMag > 14
and m.gMeanPSFMag < 21 and m.rMeanPSFMag < 21
and m.iMeanPSFMag < 21 and m.zMeanPSFMag < 21
and m.gMeanPSFMagErr < 0.1 and m.rMeanPSFMagErr < 0.1
and m.iMeanPSFMagErr < 0.1 and m.zMeanPSFMagErr < 0.1
and iMeanPSFMag - iMeanKronMag > -0.2
and iMeanPSFMag - iMeanKronMag < 0.05

```

We correct the extinction with band coefficients found in Green et al. [135].

.1.6 ATLAS-Refcat2 data

We use CasJobs to query from the table `refcat`, with the same general cuts on the magnitudes ($X=griz$)

$$14 < X < 21, \quad \text{and} \quad dX < 0.1$$

where dX is the magnitude uncertainty. We use the SFD extinction map with PanSTARRS band coefficients to correct for reddening. A simple example query:

```

select RA, DEC, g, r, i, z, Ag,
dg, dr, di, dz into my_database from refcat2
where RA between 150 and 233.5
and DEC between -20 and -10
and g > 14 and g < 21 and r > 14 and r < 21
and i > 14 and i < 21 and z > 14 and z < 21
and dg < 0.1 and dr < 0.1 and di < 0.1 and dz < 0.1

```

.1.7 SHELA data

The entire DECam-SHELA catalog is provided as supplementary data for Wold et al. [73]¹¹. We keep sources with the internal and external flags (SExtractor-based) of 0 in all bands (*ugriz*), and calculate the magnitudes and uncertainties from the flux measurements. The fluxes are calibrated and provided in the physical units of μJy , corresponding to a magnitude zero-point of 23.9. The stars are selected by the FWHM size: $r0.5 < 1$ arcsec. We again keep sources with magnitude $14 < X < 21$ and uncertainties $dX < 0.1$, with X standing for all *ugriz*-bands.

.2 Color Equations from Photometry

For completeness, we fit the color equations between the validation sets (KiDS/ATLAS/SDSS) and the reference catalogs (SDSS/PanSTARRS/Refcat2) on the cross-matched samples, and show that some inconsistencies can be found between the data sets. Notice that the fitted color equations in this section are not used in the calibration procedure due to the inconsistencies, though they are used for simple comparison purposes to form the “empty” histograms in Fig. 2.5.

We first bin all the matched stars in the reference *g-i* color (SDSS, Refcat2 or PanSTARRS). For the SDSS-matched samples, this covers: The entire KiDS North, part of ATLAS (both in the North and the South, see the yellow region in Fig. 2.1), and tiles of NSC that fall in the SDSS region. For the PanSTARRS-matched samples, this consists of all the data above D.E.C. $> -30^\circ$: KiDS North and half of KiDS South, most of ATLAS and all of NSC (the NSC sample is selected to have D.E.C. $> -30^\circ$). For Refcat2, this includes all the data sets. We bin the matched samples with an adaptive bin width to include 10000 stars in each bin. We then bootstrap the stars to estimate the median magnitude difference with uncertainty in each bin, to which we fit polynomials as a function of the median reference *g-i* color of each bin. The best-fit polynomials are shown in Fig. 2.

We use 2nd order color terms for the SDSS *u*-band, and a linear regression for all the *g*-bands. For the DECam *u*-band we use a 3rd order polynomial. In each case, the order of the polynomial is chosen to best describe the bulk

¹¹<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/1538-4365/aeee85/data>

Figure 2: Estimating the color transformation equation on the original photometry of KiDS/ATLAS/NSC. Data points are plotted with offsets (each set is 0.5 higher than the one below it) for illustration. Notice that these color equations are not used in the calibration procedure. Yellow dots are the median magnitude differences (with uncertainties) in each bin, obtained from bootstrap resampling. The color equations are fit to the yellow dots. A 2nd order polynomial is used for the u -band transform for KiDS/ATLAS, a 3rd order for DECam u -band, and 1st order for all the g -bands. The color transforms are given in equation (1), and the fitting ranges are listed in Table 1.

shape of the stars in Fig. 2. We find the following color terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{\text{KiDS}} - u_{\text{SDSS}} &= 0.069x_S^2 - 0.149x_S + 0.114, \\
 u_{\text{ATLAS}} - u_{\text{SDSS}} &= 0.074x_S^2 - 0.148x_S + 0.077, \\
 u_{\text{NSC}} - u_{\text{SDSS}} &= 0.483x_S^3 - 1.341x_S^2 + 1.168x_S - 0.22, \\
 g_{\text{KiDS}} - g_{\text{SDSS}} &= -0.035x_S + 0.038, \\
 g_{\text{ATLAS}} - g_{\text{SDSS}} &= -0.024x_S + 0.015, \\
 g_{\text{NSC}} - g_{\text{SDSS}} &= -0.067x_S - 0.041, \\
 g_{\text{KiDS}} - g_{\text{Ref}} &= 0.073x_R + 0.054, \\
 g_{\text{ATLAS}} - g_{\text{Ref}} &= 0.085x_R + 0.026, \\
 g_{\text{NSC}} - g_{\text{Ref}} &= 0.044x_R - 0.027, \\
 g_{\text{KiDS}} - g_{\text{Pan}} &= 0.071x_P + 0.055, \\
 g_{\text{ATLAS}} - g_{\text{Pan}} &= 0.083x_P + 0.027, \\
 g_{\text{NSC}} - g_{\text{Pan}} &= 0.042x_P - 0.025,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Table 1: Color ranges of equations (1) and (3). For (1), The VST entries apply to both KiDS and ATLAS. The bounds are selected to capture the bulk of the population by rejecting $\sim 5\%$ stars on both the blue and red sides from Fig. 2.

	color range
SDSS to KiDS	$0.3 < (g - i)_{\text{SDSS}} < 1.5$
SDSS to ATLAS	$0.3 < (g - i)_{\text{SDSS}} < 1.7$
SDSS to NSC	$0.3 < (g - i)_{\text{SDSS}} < 1.2$
PanSTARRS to VST/NSC	$0.3 < (g - i)_{\text{Pan}} < 1.5$
Refcat2 to VST/NSC	$0.3 < (g - i)_{\text{Ref}} < 1.5$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_S &= g_{\text{SDSS}} - i_{\text{SDSS}}, \\
 x_R &= g_{\text{Ref}} - i_{\text{Ref}}, \\
 x_P &= g_{\text{Pan}} - i_{\text{Pan}}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

We capture only the bulk of the stellar population by rejecting approximately 5% of stars on both the blue and red sides, leading to the color ranges listed in Table 1.

Notice that although KiDS and ATLAS are taken with the same telescope (VST) under the same set of filters, we find it necessary to fit the color equations separately. We return to this in App .3, but note that a direct comparison of measured KiDS/ATLAS u - and g -band magnitudes in the South (where the two surveys overlap) yields a u -band median offset of 0.035 mags and a g -band offset of 0.018 mags; the distribution is shown in Fig. 3. The tile difference is calculated on the $1 \times 1 \text{ deg}^2$ KiDS tiles matched with ATLAS stars, with the cuts in previous sections applied. The large difference in some tiles in the u -band is likely due to the different zero-point calibration adopted by the two surveys. Fig. 3 also shows the spatial distribution of offsets; which suggests a slight spatial variation with galactic latitude (recall that the KiDS u -band calibration also includes latitude-dependent correction). Similarly, we find substantial median offsets between the SHELA [73] and the NSC photometry of the SHELA dataset, shown in the right panels of Fig. 3. The median difference for all stars is found to be -0.26 in the u -band and 0.13 in the g -band. As noted before, SHELA is not part of our validation sets because the data are entirely included in the NSC catalog (albeit with a different photometric calibration to the SHELA data reduction).

These inconsistencies also show up in the constant terms in the color transform equations (1), making them dependent on the original calibration of the validation set. Therefore, we opt to derive the color terms with synthetic magnitudes, as shown in App. .3.

Figure 3: Upper Left: Median tile difference distribution between KiDS and ATLAS ug bands. The $1 \times 1 \text{ deg}^2$ KiDS tiles are matched with ATLAS. The median offset for the South tiles is -0.035 in the u band, and -0.018 in the g band. In the North, KiDS has only a few tiles that overlap ATLAS. They show similar median offsets, but in opposite sign to the South in both bands (KiDS fainter than ATLAS). Upper right: photometry difference between SHELA and NSC. Due to the low number of exposures, this panel shows the magnitude difference of stars. The overall median difference for all stars is -0.26 in the u band, and 0.13 in the g band. Lower: The spatial distribution of the histograms. The dashed lines indicate Galactic latitudes of $[-85^\circ, -75^\circ, -65^\circ, -55^\circ]$ from inner-most to outside on the left panel, and $[-60^\circ, -62^\circ, -64^\circ]$ from top to down on the right. Only the South tiles are shown for KiDS. We find no particular spatial pattern in all cases. Notice that the color-bars have different scales.

.3 Color Equations from Synthetic Magnitudes

We use synthetic magnitudes to derive magnitude transform for all instruments involved in this work. We first assemble a library of stellar spectra that cover the *ugi* band region:

1. The X-Shooter Spectral Library [XLS; 79, 80], containing 813 observations of 666 stars over the wavelength range 3000 – 25000 Å at a resolution $R \sim 10000$. The spectra were corrected for instrument transmission and telluric absorption, as well as wavelength-dependent flux losses. A comparison with other libraries (the MILES library, the combined IRTF and Extended IRTF) shows an accuracy to better than $< 1\%$ in the synthesized broad-band colors [80].
2. The CALSPEC spectra library [81, 82], consisting of the stellar spectra that are the spectrophotometric flux standards of the HST photometric system. All spectra were obtained with the Space Telescope Imaging Spectrograph (STIS) installed on HST that covers 1140 – 10200 Å (though some spectra are truncate in the *u*-band region). Some sources also have infrared coverages from the NICMOS grism and the WFC3 grisms on HST.
3. The Pickles spectra library [78], a library of 131 flux calibrated spectra, covering all normal spectral types and luminosity classes, and a variety of metallicity abundance. The wavelength coverage is 1150 – 25000 Å with a resolution of $R = 500$. The Pickles library contains sources where the atmospheric absorption features are not corrected, but simply set to zero. We note that this effect is minimal in the calculation of the synthetic magnitudes. Moreover, as the Pickles library only contribute a small amount to the total spectra used in this work, the effect is negligible.

All of the 131 spectra from Pickles are used. The coordinate information of stars is missing in the Pickles library, so the extinction is not corrected. Since the Pickles stars are much brighter than the XSL/CALSPEC sources, and are thus much closer, the extinction causes only minor reddening that can be ignored. Sources with low extinction $E(B-V) < 0.1$ are selected from the XSL and the CALSPEC library. They are de-reddened according to the Fitzpatrick reddening laws following equation (A1) of Schlafly and Finkbeiner [136]. Since some of the XSL sources have large flux uncertainties, we propagate those uncertainties into the magnitude uncertainties, and select only those with $u_{\text{err}}, g_{\text{err}} < 0.002$. 606 XSL sources pass the selection. In addition, 91 CALSPEC sources with complete wavelength coverage in the *ugi* bands are selected. This yields a total of 828 spectra.

Figure 4: Magnitude transform fitted on synthetic magnitudes. A total of 828 spectra from Pickles, XSL and CALSPEC are used for the fitting. An iterative 3σ clipping is applied in the fitting process, with rejected source marked as red. The fitted color equations are shown in solid yellow curves, and can be found in equation (3). For comparison, the magnitude equations fitted on actual survey data (see App .2 for details) are also plotted in dashed lines.

We obtain the filter transmission curves (including atmospheric transmission and system throughput) from the Filter Profile Service maintained by the Spanish Virtual Observatory¹², and use these to compute synthetic broad-band magnitudes for all datasets in question, and fit for the color equations (shown in Fig. 4). The best-fit color equations are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{\text{VST}} - u_{\text{SDSS}} &= 0.031x_S^2 - 0.08x_S - 0.012, \\
 u_{\text{DECam}} - u_{\text{SDSS}} &= -0.28x_S^2 + 0.197x_S - 0.315, \\
 g_{\text{VST}} - g_{\text{SDSS}} &= -0.024x_S - 0.007, \\
 g_{\text{DECam}} - g_{\text{SDSS}} &= -0.079x_S - 0.006, \\
 g_{\text{VST}} - g_{\text{Pan}} &= 0.094x_P + 0.005, \\
 g_{\text{DECam}} - g_{\text{Pan}} &= 0.031x_P + 0.006.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where

$$x_S = g_{\text{SDSS}} - i_{\text{SDSS}} \quad \text{and} \quad x_P = g_{\text{Pan}} - i_{\text{Pan}}. \tag{4}$$

The color ranges over which we fit (and thus the range these equations apply to) follows the bulk of photometry data in the validation sets, and are listed in Table 1.

For comparison, the color equations derived from the actual survey data

¹²<http://svo2.cab.inta-csic.es/theory/fps/>

(equation 2) are also shown in Fig. 4 in dashed lines. We find that all of them show (large) offsets to the synthetic magnitudes, but also that the color transforms determined from different survey data / calibration on the same instruments (i.e. KiDS vs. ATLAS on VST, and NSC. vs. SHELA on DECam) differ noticeably. This is likely the root cause of the inconsistencies we find in App .2.

For the above reasons, we choose to use color equations (3) for the recalibration of the validation sets. This results in 1). an independent calibration regardless of the initial photometry of the validation sets, and 2). an accurate calibration that aligns with the SDSS/PanSTARRS AB system.

.4 Gaia parallax and proper motion

We attribute the variation of the observed $u - g$ edge color in halo MSTO stars with galactic latitude to contamination from stars in the galactic disk. The Gaia satellite, currently in Early Data Release 3 [EDR3; 63, 137], offers high precision parallax and proper motion measurements, providing a possible way of rejecting disk stars based on their Gaia distance / motion measurements. We here test the usage of Gaia information to reduce the contamination.

todo: you query this info for specific stars? or fields? We retrieve data from the Gaia Archive¹³ for RA, DEC, parallax and proper motion. For each star, the total proper motion uncertainty is calculated using

$$\text{pm_err} = \frac{1}{\text{pm}} \sqrt{\text{pmra}^2 * \text{pmra_error}^2 + \text{pmdec}^2 * \text{pmdec_error}^2}$$

where `pmra`, `pmra_error` are the proper motion in right ascension direction and its uncertainty, and `pmdec`, `pmdec_error` those in the declination direction. We reject stars with parallax cut tailored for a plane-parallel disk model:

$$\text{parallax} - \text{parallax_error} > |\sin b|,$$

i.e. removing stars within the disk at 1-sigma confidence, assuming that the disk is 1 kpc thick. In addition, we place a proper motion cut, following the assumption that fast-moving stars are likely to be nearby and therefore in the disk:

$$\text{pm} - \text{pm_err} > 10 \text{ mas/year.}$$

Stars that satisfy either threshold are rejected. We keep stars that don't have a Gaia counter-part or are lacking both the parallax and the proper motion

¹³<https://gea.esac.esa.int/archive/>

Figure 5: Stars rejected by Gaia from a $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ deg}^2$ DECam field. The blue histogram shows all the DECam stars within our selection (the “white box” selection of Fig. 2.2). The empty histogram is the remaining stars after the parallax and proper motion cut of Gaia. The full model (2.5) is fitted on both histograms, and the resulting parameters are used for plotting the intrinsic model (2.2) in this Figure. No significant change in the blue tip color x_0 is observed after the Gaia cuts.

measurements.

We examine three fields from different surveys in the validation sets at different galactic latitude, listed in Table 2. The blue tip color x_0 is measured before and after the Gaia cuts. We perform the same test for stars in the SDSS fields that overlap the three selected fields. In all cases, the Gaia cuts reject about 20 – 25% of stars in our selection, but barely alter the blue tip colors. A DECam field is shown in Fig. 5 as an example. As a conclusion, Gaia EDR3 is not deep enough into the disk for rejecting the disk stars. We look forward to future Gaia data release for this purpose.

Table 2: Testing the impact of Gaia cuts on the blue tip color. The blue tip colors of three fields at different galactic latitudes and from different surveys are listed, measured both without the Gaia cuts, and with the Gaia cuts. We repeat the test for the samples of SDSS stars overlapping these three fields. The last two rows list the shift in the measured edge color when applying the Gaia cuts - no significant change in the blue tip color is observed in all 6 cases.

Survey	ATLAS	KiDS	DECam
Ra, Dec	60.14, -12.06	181.03, 1.49	187.49, 12.56
Galactic Latitude	-43.29	61.96	74.57
# White Box Stars	214	236	473
# Stars Gaia Rejected	37	51	115
x_0 w/o Gaia cuts	0.79 ± 0.02	0.80 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.01
x_0 w/ Gaia cuts	0.79 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.01
x_0 SDSS w/o cuts	0.76 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.01
x_0 SDSS w/ cuts	0.75 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.01
Δx_0	0.00 ± 0.03	0.01 ± 0.03	0.00 ± 0.01
Δx_0 SDSS	0.01 ± 0.03	0.00 ± 0.01	0.00 ± 0.01

.5 Calculating the Luptitudes

Following Lupton et al. [109], we calculate the asinh magnitudes (Luptitudes) for the base COSMOS sample with

$$m = -a \left[\sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{f/f_0}{2b} \right) + \ln b \right], \quad (5)$$

where $a = 2.5 \log_{10} e$ is a constant, and f is the flux of each source normalized by $f_0 = 3631 \times 10^6 \mu\text{Jy}$, the reference flux of an object at magnitude 0. The “softening parameter” b sets the small scale at which the magnitude responds linearly to the normalized flux. Lupton et al. [109] suggest setting b to be the normalized flux of an object with a signal-to-noise ratio of about one. In our practice, we set b to be the median normalized flux of sources with $0.9 < \text{S.N.R} < 1.1$, which are listed in Table 3. The magnitude uncertainties are calculated with:

$$m_{\text{err}} = \frac{a \cdot f_{\text{err}}/f_0}{\sqrt{4b^2 + (f/f_0)^2}}. \quad (6)$$

Table 3: Softening parameters to calculate the asinh magnitudes for the COSMOS data set.

Filter	$b[10^{-11}]$	Zero-Flux Magnitude	
		$m(f/f_0 = 0)$	$m(f/f_0 = 10b)$
<i>u</i>	1.12	27.39	24.88
<i>B</i>	0.45	28.38	25.87
<i>V</i>	0.85	27.67	25.16
<i>r</i>	0.77	27.79	25.28
<i>i</i> ⁺	1.19	27.31	24.80
<i>z</i> ⁺⁺	2.10	26.70	24.19
<i>Y</i>	3.85	26.03	23.52
<i>J</i>	4.17	25.95	23.44
<i>H</i>	5.93	25.57	23.06

.6 Jupyter Notebook: Quick Example

bl_promo_talk

April 29, 2022

0.1 Goals

1. Identify halo members from the truth catalog
2. Match truth and object catalogs for DC2 Run 2.2i
3. Identify blends, examine their photo-zs

Last Verified to Run: 2022-04-29

Notes: - Follow this [step-by-step guide](#) if you don't know how to run this notebook. - If you need more information about the Generic Catalog Reader (GCR), see [this diagram](#) and [more examples](#).

```
[1]: import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import matplotlib.patches as patches
import healpy as hp
%matplotlib inline
```

```
[2]: from astropy.coordinates import SkyCoord
from astropy.table import Table
from GCR import GCRQuery
import FoFCatalogMatching
import GRCatalogs
import fitsio
```

```
[3]: truth_cat = GRCatalogs.load_catalog('cosmoDC2_v1.1.4_small')
```

```
[4]: #sorted(truth_cat.list_all_quantities())
```

1 load the truth catalogs

1.1 load the cluster catalog, find one massive cluster, define its surrounding.

```
[9]: ### use the BCGs (is_central) to represent each cluster.
### only 1 cluster in this simulation has halo mass > 1.3e15,
### whose surrounding coordinates are defined below.

cluster_data = truth_cat.get_quantities(['ra', 'dec', 'halo_mass', 'halo_id',
↪ 'redshift', 'size_true', 'size_minor_true',
```

```

        'ellipticity_1_true',
        ↪'ellipticity_2_true', 'shear_1', 'shear_2'],
        filters=['is_central', 'halo_mass > 1.3e15'])

```

```
[15]: print(cluster_data['ra'].data, cluster_data['dec'].data)
```

```
[61.38091043] [-39.9951343]
```

1.1.1 define the cluster block

```
[7]: ## halo_id = 935700155279
     ## red_shift = 0.75
     max_ra = 61.47
     min_ra = 61.30
     max_dec = -39.92
     min_dec = -40.08
     pos_filters = [f'ra >= {min_ra}', f'ra <={max_ra}', f'dec >= {min_dec}', f'dec
     ↪<= {max_dec}']

     cluster_filters = pos_filters + ['mag_r < 25.5']

```

```
[11]: cluster_galaxy_data = truth_cat.get_quantities(['galaxy_id', 'ra', 'dec',
     ↪'size_true', 'size_minor_true', \
     ↪'position_angle_true',
     ↪'redshift', 'mag_r', 'mag_i', \
     ↪'ellipticity_1_true',
     ↪'ellipticity_2_true', 'shear_1', 'shear_2',
     ↪'halo_id', 'halo_mass'],
     ↪filters=cluster_filters)

```

```
[27]: cluster_data = Table(cluster_data)

     for i, cluster in enumerate(cluster_data):
         members = GCRQuery('halo_id == {}'.format(cluster['halo_id'])).
         ↪filter(cluster_galaxy_data)
         plt.figure(figsize=(7,7))

         plt.scatter(members['ra'], members['dec'], s=10, label='Galaxy Members
         ↪[{}].format(len(members['ra']))))
         plt.plot(cluster['ra'], cluster['dec'], 'xr', label='Cluster Center')

         plt.legend(loc='best', frameon=False, fontsize=14)
         plt.xlabel(r'ra [deg]', fontsize=16)
         plt.ylabel(r'dec [deg]', fontsize=16)
         plt.title('Mass: {:.2e} h^-1 Msun'.format(cluster['halo_mass']),
         ↪fontsize=14)

```

```
plt.show()
```


1.2 define the cluster + field block for comparison

```
[29]: max_ra = 61.88
min_ra = 60.88
max_dec = -39.5
min_dec = -40.5
pos_filters = [f'ra >= {min_ra}', f'ra <={max_ra}', f'dec >= {min_dec}', f'dec <
↳ <={max_dec}']
block_filters = pos_filters + ['mag_r < 25.5' ]
```

```
[30]: block_galaxy_data = truth_cat.get_quantities(['galaxy_id', 'ra', 'dec', '
↳ size_true', 'size_minor_true', \
```

```

    ↪ 'redshift', 'mag_r', 'mag_i', \
    ↪ filters=block_filters)
    ↪ 'position_angle_true', \
    ↪ 'halo_id', 'halo_mass'], \

```

```

[34]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(9,6))
ax = plt.subplot(111, xlim=(61.145,61.445), ylim=(-40.1,-39.85))
ax.set_xlabel('RA', fontsize=14)
ax.set_ylabel('DEC', fontsize=14)

sc = ax.scatter(block_galaxy_data['ra'], block_galaxy_data['dec'], \
    ↪ cmap='Greens', \
    ↪ s=5, \
    ↪ c=np.log10(np.abs(block_galaxy_data['halo_mass'])))

cbar = plt.colorbar(sc, ax=ax)
cbar.set_label(label=r'$\log_{10}(M_{\mathrm{halo}})$', size=14)

# Create a Rectangle patch
rect1 = patches.Rectangle((61.152, -40.08), 0.14, 0.2, linewidth=1, \
    ↪ edgecolor='b', facecolor='none')
rect2 = patches.Rectangle((61.30, -40.06), 0.14, 0.14, linewidth=1, \
    ↪ edgecolor='r', facecolor='none')

# Add the patch to the Axes
ax.add_patch(rect1)
ax.add_patch(rect2)

ax.plot(0,0,'b', lw=1, label='Field Patch')
ax.plot(0,0,'r', lw=1, label='Cluster Patch')

#q=plt.scatter(field_galaxy_data['ra'][halo_mask], \
    ↪ field_galaxy_data['dec'][halo_mask])

ax.legend(prop={'size':14}, loc='upper right')
plt.xticks(fontsize=12)
plt.yticks(fontsize=12)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('truth.png')

```


1.3 take galaxies in the defined patches above

```
[35]: raf, decf = 61.15, -40.08
      rac, decr = 61.30, -40.06
```

```
[37]: ra, dec = block_galaxy_data['ra'], block_galaxy_data['dec']
```

```
[38]: mask_f = (ra > raf) & (ra < raf + 0.14) & (dec > decf) & (dec < decf + 0.20)
      mask_c = (ra > rac) & (ra < rac + 0.14) & (dec > decr) & (dec < decr + 0.14)
```

```
[39]: field = Table(block_galaxy_data)[mask_f]
      cluster = Table(block_galaxy_data)[mask_c]
```

```
[40]: print(len(field), len(cluster))
```

3372 3160

1.4 load the stars

```
[41]: stars_cat = fitsio.read('/global/cfs/projectdirs/lstt/groups/SSim/DC2/
      ↪all_stars_DC2_run2.1i.fits.gz')
```

```
[43]: ## filters for stars
maskf_stars = (stars_cat['ra'] >= raf) & (stars_cat['ra'] <= raf+0.14) & \
             (stars_cat['decl'] >= decf) & (stars_cat['decl'] <= decf+0.2) \
             & (stars_cat['rmag'] < 25.5)

maskc_stars = (stars_cat['ra'] >= rac) & (stars_cat['ra'] <= rac+0.14) & \
             (stars_cat['decl'] >= decc) & (stars_cat['decl'] <= decc+0.14) \
             & (stars_cat['rmag'] < 25.5)

[44]: stars_catf = stars_cat[maskf_stars] # Filter out the stars that are out of the
      ↪footprint
stars_catc = stars_cat[maskc_stars] # Filter out the stars that are out of the
      ↪footprint
```

1.5 merge galaxies and stars

```
[46]: total_fgalaxies = len(field)
total_cgalaxies = len(cluster)

total_fobjs = len(stars_catf)+total_fgalaxies # Total length of the output
      ↪catalog
total_cobjs = len(stars_catc)+total_cgalaxies # Total length of the output
      ↪catalog

truth_fdata_all = dict()
truth_cdata_all = dict()

quantities = ['galaxy_id', 'ra', 'dec', 'mag_i', 'mag_r', 'redshift']
out_qty = ['id', 'ra', 'dec', 'mag_i', 'mag_r', 'redshift']
star_qty = ['simobjid', 'ra', 'decl', 'imag', 'rmag', 'redshift']
out_dtype = [np.long, np.float, np.float, np.float, np.float, np.float]

[48]: # Allocate the columns of the dictionary
for i, dtype in enumerate(out_dtype):
    truth_fdata_all[out_qty[i]] = np.zeros(total_fobjs, dtype=dtype)
    truth_cdata_all[out_qty[i]] = np.zeros(total_cobjs, dtype=dtype)
    truth_fdata_all[out_qty[i]][:total_fgalaxies] = field[quantities[i]]
    truth_cdata_all[out_qty[i]][:total_cgalaxies] = cluster[quantities[i]]
    if 'redshift' not in star_qty[i]:
        truth_fdata_all[out_qty[i]][total_fgalaxies:] = stars_catf[star_qty[i]]
        ↪# We add the info from stars and put all stars at redshift=0
        truth_cdata_all[out_qty[i]][total_cgalaxies:] = stars_catc[star_qty[i]]
        ↪# We add the info from stars and put all stars at redshift=0
    else:
        truth_fdata_all[out_qty[i]][total_fgalaxies:] = 0
        truth_cdata_all[out_qty[i]][total_cgalaxies:] = 0
```

```
truth_fdata_all['star'] = np.zeros(total_fobjs, dtype=np.bool)
truth_cdata_all['star'] = np.zeros(total_cobjs, dtype=np.bool)
truth_fdata_all['star'][total_fgalaxies:] = True
truth_cdata_all['star'][total_cgalaxies:] = True
```

1.6 plot the final truth catalogs, ready to match

```
[50]: plt.figure(figsize=(8,6))
ax = plt.subplot(111)
ax.set_xlabel('RA', fontsize=16)
ax.set_ylabel('DEC', fontsize=16)

ax.scatter(truth_fdata_all['ra'][total_fgalaxies:],
           ↪truth_fdata_all['dec'][total_fgalaxies:], s=5, c='b', label='stars')
ax.scatter(truth_fdata_all['ra'][:total_fgalaxies], truth_fdata_all['dec'][:
           ↪total_fgalaxies], s=1, c='C1', label='galaxies')

ax.scatter(truth_cdata_all['ra'][total_cgalaxies:],
           ↪truth_cdata_all['dec'][total_cgalaxies:], s=5, c='b')
ax.scatter(truth_cdata_all['ra'][:total_cgalaxies], truth_cdata_all['dec'][:
           ↪total_cgalaxies], s=1, c='C1')

ax.legend(prop={'size':16})
ax.axis('equal')
plt.xticks(fontsize=12)
plt.yticks(fontsize=12)
plt.tight_layout()
```


2 load the object (detection) catalog

```
[51]: object_cat = GCRCatalogs.load_catalog('dc2_object_run2.2i_dr3_with_photoz')
```

```
[52]: sorted(q for q in object_cat.list_all_quantities() if q.startswith('photoz_'))
```

```
[52]: ['photoz_mean',
       'photoz_median',
       'photoz_mode',
       'photoz_mode_ml',
       'photoz_mode_ml_red_chi2',
       'photoz_odds',
       'photoz_pdf']
```

```
[53]: #sorted(object_cat.list_all_quantities() )
```

```
[54]: ## filters for the object catalog
cuts = [
    GCRQuery('extendedness > 0'),    # Extended objects
```

```

    GCRQuery((np.isfinite, 'mag_i')), # Select objects that have i-band
    ↪magnitudes
    GCRQuery('clean'),             # The source has no flagged pixels
    ↪(interpolated, saturated, edge, clipped...)
                                   # and was not skipped by the deblender
    GCRQuery('mag_r_cModel < 24.5') # cModel imag brighter than 24.5
]

```

```

[55]: posf_filters = [f'ra >= {raf}', f'ra <={raf+0.14}', f'dec >= {decf}', f'dec <=
    ↪{decf+0.2}']
    posc_filters = [f'ra >= {rac}', f'ra <={rac+0.14}', f'dec >= {decc}', f'dec <=
    ↪{decc+0.14}']

    objectf_filters = posf_filters + cuts
    objectc_filters = posc_filters + cuts

```

```

[56]: # Load ra and dec from object, using both of the filters we just defined.
    object_fdata = object_cat.get_quantities(['ra', 'dec', 'mag_i_cModel',
    ↪'mag_r_cModel', \
                                           'photoz_mode', 'blendedness'],
    filters=objectf_filters, \
    native_filters=['tract == 3447'])

```

```

/opt/lsst/software/stack/python/miniconda3-4.7.10/envs/lsst-
scipipe-4d7b902/lib/python3.7/site-packages/GCRCatalogs/dc2_dm_catalog.py:43:
RuntimeWarning: divide by zero encountered in log10
    return -2.5 * np.log10(flux) + AB_mag_zp_wrt_nanoJansky
/opt/lsst/software/stack/python/miniconda3-4.7.10/envs/lsst-
scipipe-4d7b902/lib/python3.7/site-packages/GCRCatalogs/dc2_dm_catalog.py:43:
RuntimeWarning: invalid value encountered in log10
    return -2.5 * np.log10(flux) + AB_mag_zp_wrt_nanoJansky

```

```

[57]: object_cdata = object_cat.get_quantities(['ra', 'dec', 'mag_i_cModel',
    ↪'mag_r_cModel', \
                                           'photoz_mode', 'blendedness'],
    filters=objectc_filters, \
    native_filters=['tract == 3447'])

```

```

[58]: print(len(object_fdata['ra']), len(object_cdata['ra']))

```

```

1494 1416

```

```

[59]: plt.figure(figsize=(8,6))
    ax = plt.subplot(111)
    ax.set_xlabel('RA', fontsize=14)
    ax.set_ylabel('DEC', fontsize=14)

```

```

ax.scatter(truth_fdata_all['ra'], truth_fdata_all['dec'], s=1, c='g',
          ↪label='truth')
ax.scatter(truth_cdata_all['ra'], truth_cdata_all['dec'], s=1, c='g')

ax.scatter(object_fdata['ra'], object_fdata['dec'], s=1, c='C1', label='object')
ax.scatter(object_cdata['ra'], object_cdata['dec'], s=1, c='C1')
ax.legend(prop={'size':14})
ax.axis('equal')
plt.xticks(fontsize=12)
plt.yticks(fontsize=12)
plt.savefig('obj.png')

```


3 match the detection to truth

```

[60]: # now we can really do the matching!
      # FoFCatalogMatching.match takes a dictionary of catalogs to match, a
      ↪friends-of-friends linking length.
      # Because our "catalog" is not an astropy table or pandas dataframe,
      # `len(truth_coord)` won't give the actual length of the table
      # so we need to specify `catalog_len_getter` so that the code knows how to get
      ↪the length of the catalog.

```

```

resultsf = FoFCatalogMatching.match(
    catalog_dict={'truth': truth_fdata_all, 'object': object_fdata},
    linking_lengths=1.0, # Linking length of 1 arcsecond, you can play around
    ↪with the values!
    catalog_len_getter=lambda x: len(x['ra']),
)

```

```

[61]: resultsc = FoFCatalogMatching.match(
    catalog_dict={'truth': truth_cdata_all, 'object': object_cdata},
    linking_lengths=1.0, # Linking length of 1 arcsecond, you can play around
    ↪with the values!
    catalog_len_getter=lambda x: len(x['ra']),
)

```

3.1 count the number of truth and object objects for *each matching group*: 1-1 matching, 1-2, 2-1, etc

```

[63]: # instead of looping over groups, we can do this in a smart (and very fast) way

# first we need to know which rows are from the truth catalog and which are
    ↪from the object
truth_maskf = resultsf['catalog_key'] == 'truth'
truth_maskc = resultsc['catalog_key'] == 'truth'
object_maskf = ~truth_maskf
object_maskc = ~truth_maskc

# then np.bincount will give up the number of id occurrences (like histogram
    ↪but with integer input)
n_fgroups = resultsf['group_id'].max() + 1
n_cgroups = resultsc['group_id'].max() + 1

n_truthf = np.bincount(resultsf['group_id'][truth_maskf], minlength=n_fgroups)
n_truthc = np.bincount(resultsc['group_id'][truth_maskc], minlength=n_cgroups)
n_fobject = np.bincount(resultsf['group_id'][object_maskf], minlength=n_fgroups)
n_cobject = np.bincount(resultsc['group_id'][object_maskc], minlength=n_cgroups)

# now n_truth and n_object are the number of truth/object objects in each group
# we want to make a 2d histogram of (n_truth, n_object).
n_maxf = max(n_truthf.max(), n_fobject.max()) + 1
n_maxc = max(n_truthc.max(), n_cobject.max()) + 1

```

3.2 number of galaxies in each matching groups

```
[85]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(14,6))

ax1 = fig.add_subplot(121)
ax2 = fig.add_subplot(122)

ax1.set_xlabel('Number of truth objects', fontsize=14)
ax1.set_ylabel('Number of object objects', fontsize=14)

ax2.set_xlabel('Number of truth objects', fontsize=14)
ax2.set_ylabel('Number of object objects', fontsize=14)

hist_1d_f = np.bincount(n_fobject * n_maxf + n_truthf, minlength=n_maxf*n_maxf)
hist_2d_f = hist_1d_f.reshape(n_maxf, n_maxf)

hist_1d_c = np.bincount(n_cobject * n_maxc + n_truthc, minlength=n_maxc*n_maxc)
hist_2d_c = hist_1d_c.reshape(n_maxc, n_maxc)

imf = ax1.imshow(np.log10(hist_2d_f+1), extent=(-0.5, n_maxf-0.5, -0.5,
↔n_maxf-0.5), origin='lower')
cabr = plt.colorbar(imf, ax=ax1, label=r'$\log(N + 1)$')

imc = ax2.imshow(np.log10(hist_2d_c+1), extent=(-0.5, n_maxc-0.5, -0.5,
↔n_maxc-0.5), origin='lower')
cabrc = plt.colorbar(imc, ax=ax2, label=r'$\log(N + 1)$')

h = ax1.set_title('Field Galaxies', fontsize=16)
h = ax2.set_title('Cluster Galaxies', fontsize=16)

plt.tight_layout()
```


3.3 inspect the photo-z statistics for each groups

```
[70]: # for the field galaxies
one_to_one_group_maskf = np.in1d(resultsf['group_id'], np.flatnonzero((n_truthf_
↳ == 1) & (n_fobject == 1)))
two_to_one_group_maskf = np.in1d(resultsf['group_id'], np.flatnonzero((n_truthf_
↳ > 1) & (n_fobject == 1)))

truth_idxf_11 = resultsf['row_index'][one_to_one_group_maskf & truth_maskf]
object_idxf_11 = resultsf['row_index'][one_to_one_group_maskf & object_maskf]

truth_idxf_21 = resultsf['row_index'][two_to_one_group_maskf & truth_maskf]
object_idxf_21 = resultsf['row_index'][two_to_one_group_maskf & object_maskf]
group_idf_21 = resultsf['group_id'][two_to_one_group_maskf & object_maskf]

# for the cluster galaxies
one_to_one_group_maskc = np.in1d(resultsc['group_id'], np.flatnonzero((n_truthc_
↳ == 1) & (n_cobject == 1)))
two_to_one_group_maskc = np.in1d(resultsc['group_id'], np.flatnonzero((n_truthc_
↳ > 1) & (n_cobject == 1)))

truth_idxc_11 = resultsc['row_index'][one_to_one_group_maskc & truth_maskc]
object_idxc_11 = resultsc['row_index'][one_to_one_group_maskc & object_maskc]

truth_idxc_21 = resultsc['row_index'][two_to_one_group_maskc & truth_maskc]
object_idxc_21 = resultsc['row_index'][two_to_one_group_maskc & object_maskc]
group_idc_21 = resultsc['group_id'][two_to_one_group_maskc & object_maskc]

[69]: truth_redshift_prf = [] ## primary truth index; the one with closest_
↳ magnitude in the more-to-1 cases
for i, id in enumerate(group_idf_21):
    indf, = np.where( (resultsf['group_id'] == id) & truth_maskf)
    truth_indf = resultsf['row_index'][indf]
    matchesf = truth_fdata_all['mag_r'][truth_indf]
    mag_diffsf = np.abs( matchesf -_
↳ object_fdata['mag_r_cModel'][object_idxf_21[i]])
    indf, = np.where( mag_diffsf == mag_diffsf.min())
    truth_redshift_prf.append(truth_fdata_all['redshift'][truth_indf][indf[0]])

truth_redshift_prf = np.array(truth_redshift_prf)

truth_redshift_prc = [] ## primary truth index; the one with closest_
↳ magnitude in the more-to-1 cases
```

```

for i, id in enumerate(group_idc_21):
    indc, = np.where( (resultsc['group_id'] == id) & truth_maskc)
    truth_indc = resultsc['row_index'][indc]
    matchesc = truth_cdata_all['mag_r'][truth_indc]
    mag_diffsc = np.abs( matchesc -
↳object_cdata['mag_r_cModel'][object_idxc_21[i]])
    indc, = np.where( mag_diffsc == mag_diffsc.min())
    truth_redshift_prc.append(truth_cdata_all['redshift'][truth_indc][indc[0]])

truth_redshift_prc = np.array(truth_redshift_prc)

```

```

[86]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(14,6))

ax1 = fig.add_subplot(121)
ax2 = fig.add_subplot(122)

ax1.set_xlabel('True Redshift', fontsize=16)
ax1.set_ylabel('Photoz_mode', fontsize=16)

ax2.set_xlabel('True Redshift', fontsize=16)
ax2.set_ylabel('Photoz_mode', fontsize=16)

ax1.scatter(truth_fdata_all['redshift'][truth_idxf_11],
↳object_fdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxf_11], s=3, label='1-to-1 match')
ax1.scatter(truth_redshift_prc, object_fdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxf_21],
↳s=20, label='1-to-more match')

ax2.scatter(truth_cdata_all['redshift'][truth_idxc_11],
↳object_cdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxc_11], s=3, label='1-to-1 match')
ax2.scatter(truth_redshift_prc, object_cdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxc_21],
↳s=20, label='1-to-more match')

ax1.axis('equal')
ax2.axis('equal')

ax1.legend(prop={'size':16})
ax2.legend(prop={'size':16})

h = ax1.set_title('Field Galaxies', fontsize=16)
h = ax2.set_title('Cluster Galaxies', fontsize=16)

plt.tight_layout()

```


3.4 quantify the photo-z outliers

```
[100]: z_diff= np.abs(truth_fdata_all['redshift'][truth_idxf_11] -
    ↪object_fdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxf_11])
out, = np.where( z_diff/(1+truth_fdata_all['redshift'][truth_idxf_11]) > 0.15)
print('outliers in the pure sample for field galaxies:')
print(len(out), '/', len(z_diff), '=', len(out) / len(z_diff))
```

outliers in the pure sample for field galaxies:
186 / 1369 = 0.1358655953250548

```
[101]: z_diff= np.abs(truth_redshift_prf - object_fdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxf_21])
out, = np.where( z_diff/(1+truth_redshift_prf) > 0.15)
print('outliers in the blended sample for field galaxies:')
print(len(out), '/', len(z_diff), '=', len(out) / len(z_diff))
```

outliers in the blended sample for field galaxies:
11 / 70 = 0.15714285714285714

```
[102]: z_diff= np.abs(truth_cdata_all['redshift'][truth_idxc_11] -
    ↪object_cdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxc_11])
out, = np.where( z_diff/(1+truth_cdata_all['redshift'][truth_idxc_11]) > 0.15)
print('outliers in the pure sample for cluster galaxies:')
print(len(out), '/', len(z_diff), '=', len(out) / len(z_diff))
```

outliers in the pure sample for cluster galaxies:
121 / 1274 = 0.09497645211930926

```
[103]: z_diff= np.abs(truth_redshift_prc - object_cdata['photoz_mode'][object_idxc_21])
out, = np.where( z_diff/(1+truth_redshift_prc) > 0.15)
print('outliers in the blended sample for cluster galaxies:')
```

```
print(len(out), '/', len(z_diff), '=', len(out) / len(z_diff))
```

outliers in the blended sample for cluster galaxies:
25 / 109 = 0.22935779816513763

[]:

.7 Jupyter Notebook: Ellipse Matching

match_ellipse_demo

April 29, 2022

1 Demo: Detect overlapping between two ellipses

Last verified to run: 2022-04-29

```
[1]: import numpy as np
import matplotlib
matplotlib.use('TkAgg')
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline
from matplotlib.patches import Ellipse
```

1.1 The Ellipse Equation:

following the definition on [wikipedia](#), but swapping B and C:

$$Ax^2 + By^2 + Cxy + Dx + Ey + F = 0$$

where

$$A = a^2 \sin^2 \theta + b^2 \cos^2 \theta,$$

$$B = a^2 \cos^2 \theta + b^2 \sin^2 \theta,$$

$$C = 2(b^2 - a^2) \sin \theta \cos \theta,$$

$$D = -2Ax_0 - Cy_0,$$

$$E = -Cx_0 - 2By_0,$$

$$F = Ax_0^2 + Cx_0y_0 + By_0^2 - a^2b^2.$$

x_0, y_0 are the coordinates for the ellipse center, a, b the semi-major/minor axis and θ the position angle (the angle between the major axis and ra for the extragalactic catalog, and between the major axis and CCD x axis for the object catalog).

modify the definition to AC2017: shrink the parameters CDE by half,

$$C = C/2, \quad D = D/2, \quad E = E/2,$$

and modify the Ellipse Equation accordingly:

$$Ax^2 + By^2 + 2Cxy + 2Dx + 2Ey + F = 0.$$

```
[2]: def ellipse_equation(x, y, A, B, C, D, E, F):
      return A*x**2 + B*y**2 + 2*C*x*y + 2*D*x + 2*E*y + F

def ab2AB(a, b, theta, x0, y0):
    ### a, b, in any length units; theta in degrees ###
    sin = np.sin(np.radians(theta))
    cos = np.cos(np.radians(theta))

    A = (a*sin)**2 + (b*cos)**2
    B = (a*cos)**2 + (b*sin)**2
    C = 2*(b**2 - a**2)*sin*cos
    D = -2*A*x0 - C*y0
    E = -C*x0 - 2*B*y0
    F = A*x0**2 + C*x0*y0 + B*y0**2 - (a*b)**2
    C, D, E = C/2, D/2, E/2

    return [A, B, C, D, E, F]
```

1.2 Ellipse Overlapping Detection

The function `is_overlapping` provides a linear algorithm to detect overlapping ellipses, following [AC2017](#).

```
[3]: def is_overlapping(p1, p2):
      A1, B1, C1, D1, E1, F1 = p1
      A2, B2, C2, D2, E2, F2 = p2

      M1 = [[A1, C1, D1], [C1, B1, E1], [D1, E1, F1]]
      M2 = [[A2, C2, D2], [C2, B2, E2], [D2, E2, F2]]

      l0 = np.linalg.det(M2)
      l1 = (np.linalg.det([[A1,C2,D2], [C1,B2,E2], [D1,E2,F2]]) +
            np.linalg.det([[A2,C1,D2], [C2,B1,E2], [D2,E1,F2]]) +
            np.linalg.det([[A2,C2,D1], [C2,B2,E1], [D2,E2,F1]])) / 3
      l2 = (np.linalg.det([[A2,C1,D1], [C2,B1,E1], [D2,E1,F1]]) +
            np.linalg.det([[A1,C2,D1], [C1,B2,E1], [D1,E2,F1]]) +
            np.linalg.det([[A1,C1,D2], [C1,B1,E2], [D1,E1,F2]])) / 3
      l3 = np.linalg.det(M1)

      delta1 = np.linalg.det([[l3, l2], [l2, l1]])
      delta2 = np.linalg.det([[l3, l1], [l2, l0]])
      delta3 = np.linalg.det([[l2, l1], [l1, l0]])
      discriminant_P = np.linalg.det([[2*delta1, delta2], [delta2, 2*delta3]])

      if (discriminant_P >=0) and ((l1>0) or (l2>0)):
```

```

    return False ## not over-lapping
else:
    return True

```

1.3 Draw some examples

```

[11]: def draw_ellipse(ax):

    x1, y1 = np.random.uniform(-1,1,2) ## center of ellipse 1
    a1, b1 = np.random.uniform(0,1,2)
    theta1 = np.random.uniform(0, 180) ## in degrees

    if b1 > a1:
        a1, b1 = b1, a1

    x2, y2 = np.random.uniform(-1,1,2) ## center of ellipse 2
    a2, b2 = np.random.uniform(0,1,2)
    theta2 = np.random.uniform(0, 180) ## in degrees

    if b2 > a2:
        a2, b2 = b2, a2

    p1 = ab2AB(a1, b1, theta1, x1, y1)
    p2 = ab2AB(a2, b2, theta2, x2, y2)

    ellipse1 = Ellipse((x1,y1), width=2*a1, height=2*b1, \
                        angle=np.degrees(theta1), facecolor='r', \
                        edgecolor='k', alpha=0.5, linewidth=1)
    ellipse2 = Ellipse((x2,y2), width=2*a2, height=2*b2, \
                        angle=np.degrees(theta2), facecolor='b', \
                        edgecolor='k', alpha=0.5, linewidth=1)

    ax.add_artist(ellipse1)
    ax.add_artist(ellipse2)

    if is_overlapping(p1, p2):
        ax.set_title('ellipses overlapping')
    else:
        ax.set_title('not overlapping')

```

```

[15]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(8,4))
ax1 = fig.add_subplot(121, xlim=(-2,2), ylim=(-2,2))
ax2 = fig.add_subplot(122, xlim=(-2,2), ylim=(-2,2))

draw_ellipse(ax1)

```

```
draw_ellipse(ax2)

ax1.set_xticks([])
ax1.set_yticks([])

ax2.set_xticks([])
ax2.set_yticks([])

plt.tight_layout()
```

ellipses overlapping

not overlapping

